

Ability Basin Lab

Peter Street Basin Master Plan 2026: Safe Accessible Water Recreation, Teaching, and Research in Downtown Toronto

28th Annual Mersivity/WaterHCI Symposium

Bahen Centre for Information Technology, March 30 - May 10, 2026

DOI (Digital Object Identifier): [10.5281/zenodo.20361445](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20361445)

Scale = 0.003:1 = 1:333⅓ = 3mm:1m. On this 8.5x11 inch paper the 60m Basin should measure 18cm.

DOI (Digital Object Identifier): 10.5281/zenodo.20361445
<https://zenodo.org/records/20361445>

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ABILITY BASIN LAB: ACCESSIBILITY, RESEARCH, TEACHING, AND HUMAN-NATURE HABITAT INTERACTION IN PETER STREET BASIN

Steve Mann and Walter Kehm

Fig. 1: Swallows nesting under the Queens Quay bridge are visible while paddling into the Basin.

HIGHEST AND BEST USE OF PETER STREET BASIN

Peter Street Basin is a mostly enclosed part of Lake Ontario with clean clear water, owing to recent cleanup efforts [7][6], its freedom from any combined sewer outfall, its supply of fresh clean rainwater from the roof system of 370 Queens Quay, and its location far from the discharges of the Don River and Humber River. It is also surrounded by concrete structures making it free of sand, dirt, grit, or grime. Additionally, it is also sheltered from wind and strong currents.

This unique clean, calm, quiet body of water in the heart of downtown Toronto makes it ideal as a place for:

- quiet paddling, especially for those with disabilities or for those learning to paddle for the first time before paddling out into open water;
- teaching and research in the new field of *concrete limnology* (urban lake study of artificial inland water systems). The access to water, free of sand, grit, grime, etc., provides a unique outdoor classroom for urban lake study, research, and teaching.

We propose a two-phased approach:

- Phase 1: immediate creation of a live limnology lab to study the kind of ecosystems and natural habitats that can be best supported in the Basin for co-existence with humans, along with development of a curriculum for teaching and research, along with fundraising initiatives. This lab can take place in the West half of the Basin (Parcel 0031, 66R13317 + parkland 0023) which is in an excellent state-of-repair, avoiding the East side (Parcel 0032, 66R14449 + parkland 0021) which has an accessibility pad and ramp that is in poor condition; and

- Phase 2: creation of the proposed “Magical Gardens” ecosystem to support wildlife habitat in harmony with human activities like quiet paddling, access for people with disabilities, the elderly, or those learning to paddle, along with research, teaching, and outdoor classroom activities that connect us to water, allowing us to touch and be touched by water.

Phase 1 can be done at very low cost, e.g. something as simple as putting a warning sign on the EastRest pad and ramp area, or perhaps even doing some minor repairs to the concrete accessibility pad and wooden resting ramp.

Phase 2 will require some fundraising, for roughly \$1,500,000. It is hoped that Phase 1 activities can help both inform and fund/fundraise to Phase 2.

ABILITY BASIN LAB

We envision a place in downtown Toronto for safe, calm, and quiet water access for people of all abilities for activities like standup paddleboarding and Polynesian Indigenous paddleboarding that benefit from calm protected water. A quiet place to mediate on the water and a place for peaceful introspection.

Additionally, we envision this place being, at certain times, an outdoor classroom, together with a living urban limnology lab.

We begin classes with a tour of Peter Street Basin showing the wildlife, e.g. the birds (Fig 1), fish, and the like, as well as the physical dimensions of the Basin (calculate using the Pythagorean theorem), shapes (what is a “right trapezoid”?), lake study (what is “limnology[1], [2], [3]”, concrete limnology, urban concrete lake study), etc..

A. Teaching advanced concepts

Water is a magical medium that carries such significance as to be able to teach advanced concepts to people of all ages, much like the Suzuki Method of music

education [4] emphasizes teaching people of all ages a level of depth that might, at first, seem beyond the possible comprehension of the age-group.

The Suzuki Method, developed by Shinichi Suzuki, is a music education philosophy based on a “Mother Tongue Method” = teaching music similarly to how children learn their native language. It emphasizes early immersion (starting as young as 2-3), daily listening, consistent repetition, and heavy parent involvement, fostering ability in every child. Prior to this method, few would have believed it possible for children to learn how to play violin for example.

Likewise, with water, we find an amazing ability and efficacy by which people of all ages have been able to deeply understand advanced concepts when presented in a fun and playful way with water.

Even advanced legal concepts like maritime law, navigable water, and access rights (e.g. the right to enter navigable water) are fascinating to people of all ages. For example, Toronto’s own maps show the South and North walls of the Basin as being part of Parks jurisdiction but the East and West walls being outside its jurisdiction. Ontario’s maps show the East and West walls as approximately parallel, but Toronto’s maps show them as angled in a bit more. Students learn to apply critical thinking in areas as diverse as physics, chemistry, geography, and law.

Upon entering the Basin, we paddle under the Queens Quay bridge to observe nesting swallows (Fig 1). Paddling further, into the Basin, we observe ducks and geese and fish in the water.

We begin every lesson with an emphasis and focus on safety. Peter Street Basin itself is a safety-feature for paddlers in downtown Toronto. Due to its sheltered nature, many paddlers, especially the elderly or those with disabilities, paddle into the Basin as a safe refuge, whether to come into the Basin to wait out a storm, or simply to come in and rest. See drawing on Page 2 and Section 0-A.

Canoes and kayaks can be quite dangerous, especially for those with disabilities, so we also teach safer alternatives such as Indigenous Polynesian paddleboarding, and Safetyballing. Safetyballs provide total rider-containment, i.e. a much safer alternative for those with disabilities, children, elderly, etc., when used properly (e.g. recalling the ABCDE of ball-safety: Attendant, Ball, Connection, Dock, and Exit as outlined in our previous writings). It is impossible to fall out of a ball, and it is easy to get on the water and enjoy the sense of float and balance despite impairments or injuries like a shoulder or back injury that might prevent the use of a canoe or kayak. Safetyballs are tethered to an attendant on shore so a rider can always be pulled back to shore even if they are too tired to come ashore on their own.

After the introduction/safety-lesson, we begin with a lesson on the physical properties of water (density, etc.). See Fig 2. The word “limnology” is a Greek word

(λιμνολογία) and it means “lake study”, from the Greek word for “lake”, “limni” (λίμνη), akin to “geography” which means “earth study” from the Greek word for “earth”, “geo” (γῆ). The Hydraulikos teaching program uses simple examples such as density (ratio of volume to mass of water), measuring the mass of the water on a simple spring scale suspended from a tripod made of driftwood.

Next we realize that the mass of water suspended from a spring forms a musical instrument of sorts, as the water bobs up and down when plucked. We then build some simple water-based instruments called “Hydraulophones”. Playing on the hydraulophone allows us to touch and be touched by water, and suggests ways of measuring water quality by understanding underwater acoustics. We introduce concepts of SONAR and echolocation, underwater sound propagation, and demonstrate our research on trying to understand water in terms of its sound propagation. For this we introduce the concept of phase-coherent detection using a lock-in amplifier (Fig 3), and then teach students how to build their own low-cost sonar from first-principles, e.g. design and build a low-cost lock-in amplifier, phase-coherent detection, etc..

We learn how to touch and be touched by water, and understand the physical, chemical, electrical, and optical properties of water, as well as related concepts like how water affects things.

Next we develop a Grade 8 curriculum that teaches about water quality starting with the hydraulophone and ending with an understanding of the shape that a water jet makes, as well as its optical properties and how water interacts with light. The arch makes the shape of a parabola, given by the equation $y = -x^2$, as shown in Fig 4. We then teach the concept of hydraulic head, by turning it into a game that we call “Head Games”, as shown in Fig 5. Again, students are able to touch and be touched by water, to explore simple concepts.

Eventually we reach more advanced concepts like water-quality monitoring, and wave propagation in water, blending art, science, technology, and fun + frolic. We conclude the lectures by creating something we call the “Symmetrical Wave Equation” as a work of art: $X^2 y_{xx} = T^2 y_{tt}$, where y is the height of the wave, T is the time period of the wave (time per cycle), and X is the space period (wavelength = distance per cycle).

We have been calling this place of research and teaching “Ability Basin Lab” to emphasize its dual-purpose as both a place of inclusive accessibility, and a place for teaching and research. Ability Basin Lab, often abbreviated as “A-Base” = base of operations for Ability, or “ABL” pronounced “Able”, is sometimes expanded to “Ability Basin Live Limnology Lab” (ABL³ or ABL3, also pronounced “ABLE” stylized with a backwards “3” to represent the “E” as “ABL^ε”).

Fig. 2: At certain times, this space is an outdoor classroom and a living urban limnology lab. The word “limnology” is a Greek word (λιμνολογία) and it means “lake study”. Here is a lesson on density (ratio of mass to volume) using a spring-scale suspended from a tripod made of driftwood collected from Peter Street Basin.

HISTORY OF PETER STREET BASIN’S FOCUS ON SAFETY AND ACCESSIBILITY

Peter Street Basin is an approximately 60m by 30m concrete pool (substantially larger than a full-size Olympic competition pool) that is part of Lake Ontario, connected to the rest of the lake by an approximately 12m wide channel. This narrow opening was created in the mid 1980s as part of the revitalization of Queens Quay West into a bicycle-friendly promenade, narrowing the innermost part of Maple Leaf Quay to form the Basin.

This narrowing of the connection to the rest of the lake resulted in a calm safe “harbour” for people of all abilities to go paddling or rowing, for the use of special accessibility vessels, and, most importantly, as a safe calm refuge (“safe harbour”) for anyone paddling in the downtown Toronto area.

As part of the construction of Peter Street Basin, around 1986, two raised concrete pads (one on each side of the channel) were built so that people could stand in shallow water while launching or boarding a canoe, kayak, or other vessel. Thus its original purpose, which we believe is its highest and best use, was for calm safe paddling.

According to Harbourfront Toronto, in the late 1990s two accessibility ramps were installed, one on each of these pads. Presently, the East side pad and ramp have deteriorated, but the West side pad and ramp remain fully functional. See Fig 6. According to Harbourfront, the ramp was installed in the late 1990s, and was made

of high quality Western Cedar Heartwood. This wood has among the longest lifespans, typically 30 to 100 years, even when exposed to water, depending on the conditions.

The ramp also provides an emergency resting refuge for paddlers with disabilities who can paddle into the Basin during a storm, to rest or wait out the storm before continuing on their journey elsewhere.

Note that the East concrete pad and East ramp are in disrepair, with concrete rebar protruding. Therefore paddlers entering the Basin should keep left, as shown in Fig 7, i.e. “Head West to take a rest.”. Paddlers can also exit from the water at the “Wexit” (West bullrail safety-exit) as shown in the drawing on page 2. This important safety feature was added to Peter Street Basin over a time period spanning from 2024 July 25th to 2024 August 7th. There are two bullrail safety-exits as shown in the drawing on page 2. See also Fig 8.

CLEANUP

Part of the research agenda involves freshwater stewardship, learning how to test water quality, and, of course, cleanup, for which we have designed bespoke robotic systems specifically for Peter Street Basin (see, for example, Peter Street Basin Cleanup with Autonomous Robotic Submarine for Garbage Detection, in this Proceedings).

Once garbage is identified, it is gathered and cleaned up, which is itself part of the research project, e.g. using

Fig. 3: Students learn how to make underwater sound, how to shop for a watermelon by listening to how sound waves travel through it and how sound travels through air, water, and air-water boundaries, from Safetyballing, being inside a ball, listening with what becomes a giant eardrum, to how to sense water quality and pollution using sound waves with the world's most advanced lock-in amplifier capable of arbitrary waveform phase-coherent detection.

wearable technologies like brain-sensing devices (Muse S) while engaged in cleanup activities, as shown in Fig 9.

The cleanup efforts involve community outreach, connecting with the community (Fig. 10).

Additionally we have gamified Peter Street Basin cleanup using XR (eXtended Reality headsets), building a complete 3D model of the Basin as point clouds using Gaussian splatting, along with design of robotic mechanisms to make use of this data as well.

MAGICAL GARDENS: ABILITY BASIN LAB

Phase 2, we hope, will unfold as we understand the unique properties of the Basin and what can be supported there, along with fundraising efforts toward building an ecosystem that will sustain clean water.

To build a truly sustainable clean, calm, quiet contemplative space for accessible gentle paddling that also functions as a teaching and research lab, we wish to support also a natural ecosystem that keeps the water

clean, and provides habitat for wildlife in an urban setting.

The space should provide much-needed access to water for persons with disabilities, following the traditional and original purpose of Peter Street Basin as a calm easy safe-enclosed paddling space that also facilitates floating vegetation and innovation in freshwater stewardship. See Fig 11.

The highest and best use of Peter Street Basin is as both a living urban water-garden classroom/lab, as well as a place for accessibility.

In the research papers of this Mersivity / WaterHCI Symposium Proceedings, we outline some further research efforts.

Fig. 4: Grade 8 science lesson: The Water Arch. Lesson showing parabolic trajectory of a water jet from the hydraulophone (water-based musical instrument), turning musical fun and frolic into a lesson on mathematics. Students take measurements of the hydraulophone water jet and compare results with plots that they do in the Desmos plotting system.

PERSONAL ARTISTIC / DESIGN STATEMENTS

Peter Street Basin Concept Plan

By: Steve Mann

Date: May 8, 2026

I have lived my life at the liminal space between water, humans, and technology, often being referred to as “the father of wearable computing” and the inventor of wearable technology as a field or discipline (IEEE, ISSCC2000, Spectrum). Though I’ve been called “the world’s first cyborg”, I’ve been quick to point out that

the word itself has origins in the steering of vessels, and that vessels have been in use for more than a million years, so perhaps the first “cyborgs” existed more than a million years ago[5].

My artistic and design practice is centered on the body as it connects to not just technology but to natural elements of earth, water, and air, not just individually, but collectively. In this context I have chosen to live near the lake, walking distance to University of Toronto where I teach, and to Lake Ontario.

Fig. 5: A bucket with a hole in the bottom is suspended from a tripod made of driftwood. Water pumped into the bucket flows down through the hole. A giant ruler suspended upside-down (zero at the top) beside the bucket shows hydraulic head. Each participant is invited to personally experience the relationship between potential energy due to hydraulic head and kinetic energy due to impact with the water falling from various heights. We then turn it into a game we call “Head Games™”.

As a person with a disability (back injury), I use a mobility aid, another invention that extends the human mind and body. Those of us using a mobility device can only access the lake in a limited number of places, yet there is presently no place in Toronto for water access other than HTO Beach which is busy with boat traffic.

But I found a pool hidden under a garbage dump, abandoned, and, over a 4-year time-period, was able to clean it up, with help from many others. This pool, known as Peter Street Basin, is ideal for lake access, as it represents a safe harbour for calm, clean, and quiet paddling, meditation, and contemplation, where we can meet and connect to the lake. We call ourselves the “Friends of Peter Street Basin”. Over the past 4 years we’ve been there every weekend over the winters, and a few times a week over once the ice melts.

With daily water quality testing we were able to confirm the results of our cleanup efforts and get the Basin clean enough to meet safe swimming and recreational water quality standards. We actually got it about 100 times cleaner than required for safe swimming! I was also successful in getting our Friends of Peter Street

Basin added to the Swimmable Cities Charter. The idea of cleaning up the downtown inner harbour is not merely feasible, but has been realized and achieved here in Toronto, as it has in many other cities!

In this sense, should one of us fall into the water from our paddleboard, we’re at much less risk than in the rest of the lake.

I see an opportunity to immediately, at zero cost, create a teaching and research lab in which we can assess water quality, and understand this part of the lake so we can understand what kinds of plant life, and wildlife might best prosper here, and how we can best design for the future of Peter Street Basin.

I envision an outdoor classroom for “concrete limnology”, to study downtown urban waterways.

As someone with a disability using a mobility aid, I don’t like sand, and in fact can’t really deal with sand. My happy place is a concrete pool that is part of Lake Ontario. Many of us with laptop computers, assistive devices, cyborg technologies like a computer vision seeing aid, machines that help us see and find our way, require clean access to clean water in a setting that is free of sand, grit, grime, and dirt, yet provides access to water.

I believe that the highest and best use of this concrete pool is for clean easy safe accessible water.

As such, I suggest the immediate creation of a “concrete limnology” lab to explore lake study in an urban downtown inner-harbour setting.

Toronto is the biggest city on the Great Lakes which hold more than 1/5th the world’s freshwater, more than 85% of North America’s. Toronto is thus freshwater capital of the world, and I believe that downtown Toronto deserves to host the world’s foremost cyborg limnology lab which we have already created for safe clean accessible water.

Walter and I share a vision that will be easy to fund, will attract investment, and will raise property values in the surrounding area, as well as provide, for the first time, truly universal water access to persons of all abilities, not just to look at the water, but to touch and be touched by water, and to get true access to the lake.

Peter Street Basin Concept Plan

By: Walter H. Kehm

Date: May 8, 2026

The Genesis of an Idea

I have been evolved with the evolution of the Toronto waterfront for over 55 years. Mental maps of the interventions that have occurred provide me with mixed feelings. My travel experiences globally have influenced my thinking, especially on how the confluences of nature and culture can be welded together in cities. Some of my built projects will help reveal the genesis for my Peter Street Basin “Idea”. The creation of the Tommy Thompson Park plan in 1986 reveals my interest in

Fig. 6: According to Harbourfront Toronto, the Westramp, made of high-quality Western Cedar Heartwood, was installed in the late 1990s, and is still in good order. It provides improved safety for accessibility vessels such as extra-wide stability-oriented paddleboards (as shown at the bottom of the picture) or Mersivity Balls used for Safetyballing. Participants are wearing brain-sensing headbands (Muse S) for “State of Float” and spinal rehabilitation research. The ramp also provides emergency resting refuge for paddlers with disabilities who can paddle into the Basin during a storm, to rest in the Basin before continuing on their journey elsewhere.

Fig. 7: Peter Street Basin is navigable water. When visiting, it is advised to use only the left resting area. Paddlers paddle to the left, and rest on the West ramp to check their safety equipment before paddling back out of the Basin and continuing on their way. This safe harbour is an important safety feature to paddlers along the central downtown Toronto waterfront as the harbour can be very busy and stressful for persons with disabilities needing a place of refuge to rest or check safety equipment.

wetlands and habitat creation. Other waterfront projects developed my interest in urban forestry and all that this entails. Trillium Park at Ontario Place allowed me to explore the creation of a new forest with considerations of micro-climate and global temperature changes. Over the past several years, and with constant monitoring, the results have been rewarding. New habitat has resulted in the introduction of new bird species and animal habitats including coyote, skunk, beaver, fox, rabbits, mice, voles and snakes. All on 8 acres (3.2 hectares).

The origin of the idea was the realization of how new diverse habitat can be created in small urban spaces. In the 1990's I was a consultant to the Toronto and Region Conservation Authority when they initiated the Toronto Harbour Aquatic Habitat study. The finding of this study was, and remain, significant. Dock walls as spawning surfaces, warm water refuges for turtles, and fish. numerous small fish supporting large bird colony's. In addition, the migration of new fish species into the

harbour as the water quality improved adds to the diversity of the aquatic ecosystem. The historical research for this study revealed the loss of extensive wetlands at the mouth of the Don River. My biological nature spoke and reminded me if the opportunity arises, new wetlands are required in the Toronto harbour. Tommy Thompson Park provided the first opportunity with the conversion of dredge filled holding cells to wetlands. The plans were approved in 1992 and continue to be implemented.

The "Idea"

As a resident of Queens Quay for over 26 years I have walked by the Peter Street Basin innumerable times. In the 1980's there was an Italian restaurant of the north west corner of the basin with an outdoor patio. It became my significant waterfront spot. Suddenly the restaurant closed its doors leaving behind fond memories and a lifeless urban space. So it remains today, however, with the completion of a new condominium project with 800 units and perhaps over 2000 new residents, opportunities

West bullrail exit (“Wexit”)
is to the left when paddling in.

East bullrail exit (“Eexit”)
is to the right when paddling in.

Fig. 8: An important safety feature of Peter Street Basin was added July/August of 2024. It consists of bullrail exits, one on the West wall (accessed by paddling to the left when entering the Basin), and one on the East wall (accessed by entering the basin and paddling to the right). Each exit is about 7m wide, and facilitates an easy and safe emergency exit for paddlers seeking shelter or rest in the Basin. The bullrails also protect against wheelchairs falling into the water, yet facilitate safe access and safe exit. Bullrails are the safety standard for world-class waterfronts and are used at many other areas of Toronto such as HTO Beach, Sugar Beach, and along much of Queens Quay. However, the bullrails of Peter Street Basin are Toronto’s only such rails that are made of stainless steel rather than the galvanized steel of elsewhere. See also the drawing on page 2.

Fig. 9: Research on mental-state during freshwater stewardship activities: Cleanup while wearing Muse S brain-sensing headbands.

arise for the creation of a new, vibrant urban space integrating nature with cultural activities.

The basin, with its enclosed water body and with relatively shallow depth, seemed to be an ideal place to create new wetlands integrated with outdoor living spaces. I recalled my work on Byzantine Cove at Ontario Place where I proposed wetlands in this basin. My research led me to the firm of Biomatrix Water, located in Scotland. They specialize in the creation of new aquatic habitat using their floating mat system. I visited their office in Scotland and met with the owner, Galen Fulford. We reviewed several of their major projects globally and then focused on their recently completed Chicago river installation.

It seemed that this very successful project could be

Fig. 10: Community of volunteers all pitching in to cleanup the Basin on the afternoon of Sunday March 29th: Executive Director, Tim Kocur, from Waterfront BIA (Business Improvement Area) came and brought pizza and refreshments. Professor Stephen Brown came all the way from Queen’s University to bring the world’s most portable E. coli measuring lab. The volunteer Cleanup Crew did a massive cleanup and then a kind gentleman came with his big pickup truck to help haul hundreds of pounds of garbage.

of great value with the revitalization of the Basin. Galen and his team are vital to the successful realization of the plan.

The “Ideas” led to the creation of a concept plan that includes floating islands, accessible docks for swimming and launching a variety of aquatic therapeutic equipment for people with physical limitations. Steve Mann, and his Friends of the Peter Street Basin team, have made remarkable progress in caring for, monitoring and clean-

Fig. 11: Magical Gardens: Ability Basin Lab, as presented to Mersivity-2026 attendees at Peter Street Basin, on the afternoon of Sunday April 26.

ing up the water. Access to a lower concrete bench area provides opportunity for a ramp into the water. There are no other places on the Toronto waterfront that have access to the inner harbour. Additional western and northern ramps provide access to lower terraces where people can sit, relax and enjoy the fountains and new vegetation. A central fountain provides visual and auditory fascinations followed by four bubble fountains in each corner to provide enhanced water oxidation.

The islands are planted with native species including grasses, perennials and small shrubs. Essentially they are growing in a hydroponic system and with their deep root development serve as small fish habitat. The plants are entirely winter hardy as they would be in a natural wetland. The growth rate is extraordinary and within weeks of planting verdant vegetation covers the islands. They provide excellent bird and fish habitat.

On the surrounding walkways, benches, new flowering tree planting and sculpture will make the Basin a must see waterfront destination. Perhaps a new Portofino trattoria can be reopened!. The new attractive basin with a green, flowering tree edge will create a positive environment for future surrounding commercial activities. The abandoned Bernie Miller sculpture will be replaced and honoured by its central location and lighting.

Inherent in the plan is the desire to see the basin used as an outdoor teaching room. Students will be able to discover the world of hydraulics, biology, sustainable design, physics, chemistry, music and art. The nature deficit that is occurring in schools today can be remedied by access to this living laboratory.

Queens Quay is a very busy and pedestrianized street. The big idea is to create a special visual and people place away from the busy Toronto Harbour edge where people can find a retreat, sit and relax. The arrival experience is announced by colourful banners and brightly covered street kiosks where coffee, sandwiches and foods sweet and tasty can be savoured. With a short walk to the surrounding benches, or down to the floating terraces, the basin truly becomes a must see spot.

Great thought has been given to maintenance and

safety. Ladders are located on each side with life rings on top. Bubble fountain screens are located south of the Peter Street bridge to prevent flotsam and jetsam from entering and easy removal with boat access from the harbour using existing equipment.

This abandoned and forlorn space can have a new and exciting future. It will become an innovative new urban park where nature and culture are intertwined.

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Mersivity2026 Keynote by Jeanne Randolph: Bernie Miller and the Art of Peter Street Basin.

Peter Street Basin Cleanup with Autonomous Robotic Submarine for Garbage Detection

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Fig. 1: Presentation of robotic submarine for cleanup of Peter Street Basin. Presented at Mersivity-2026, March 30th, Bahen Centre for Information Technology, Toronto, Ontario, M5S 3G4.

Abstract—This paper presents an underwater garbage detection and visualization system that combines a remote-controlled submarine, real-time computer vision, Peter Street Basin (PSB)-scale localization, and an extended reality (XR) head-up display. A battery-powered submersible equipped with an ESP32-based camera captures underwater imagery and transmits frames for inference using a YOLO detector fine-tuned for marine debris recognition. Detected objects are localized within a mapped model of PSB using submarine odometry and basin imaging, then transmitted to XR goggles as distance, direction, and class cues for guided cleanup.

The system is designed to make underwater litter survey and recovery more interactive, more intuitive, and more spatially aware. In addition to live detections, the user interface displays a reduced map of PSB with accumulated garbage locations and highlights the nearest target using a compass-style indicator. Preliminary field results demonstrate successful detection of underwater debris under challenging visibility conditions, along with real-time visualization of target direction and range on the XR display.

Index Terms—Underwater computer vision, marine debris, garbage detection, XR, augmented reality, photogrammetry, Peter Street Basin, ESP32, Vuzix, robotics

INTRODUCTION

Marine debris detection in underwater environments is challenging due to light attenuation, scattering, color distortion, suspended particles, and wide appearance variation across debris categories. These difficulties motivate task-specific datasets and robust real-time detection pipelines for underwater robotics [10], [11]. At the same time, underwater photogrammetry and spatial registration methods now make it increasingly practical to build site-specific visual maps that can support navigation, inspection, and intervention [12], [13].

This project addresses those needs through a unified pipeline for underwater cleanup assistance in Peter Street Basin. Our system integrates four major components:

- 1) a custom remote-controlled submarine for underwater image capture,
- 2) a YOLO-based garbage detector for real-time recognition,
- 3) a basin localization and mapping layer for registering detections in PSB coordinates, and
- 4) an XR head-up display that presents the nearest target's direction, distance, and class to the user.

The result is a human-in-the-loop cleanup interface in which the sensing platform, the detection model, and the XR display operate together as a single spatial computing system for submerged waste awareness and retrieval.

RELATED WORK

This work builds on our earlier work reported in [6].

B. Underwater garbage detection

Recent work has established underwater debris detection as a distinct computer vision problem requiring dedicated datasets and domain-specific training. TrashCan introduced a semantically segmented underwater marine debris dataset for detection and segmentation research, providing a strong benchmark for robot-deployable detectors [10]. Walia and Seemakurthy further emphasized the importance of custom underwater trash datasets and efficient architectures suitable for constrained robotic platforms [11]. More broadly, YOLO-style one-stage detectors remain attractive for this setting because they offer a strong speed-accuracy tradeoff for real-time deployment [14], [15].

Underwater mapping and XR guidance

Structure-from-motion photogrammetry has become an effective low-cost method for constructing detailed underwater spatial models and mosaics, especially when visual detail is needed beyond coarse acoustic mapping [12]. Marker-based methods can further improve robustness and spatial registration in subsea imagery, especially for close-range photogrammetric workflows [13]. On the display side, wearable and goggle-mounted head-up systems provide a compelling interface for aquatic tasks because they keep the user hands-free while preserving directional situational awareness. In our case, this role is served by the Vuzix Smart Swim platform [16].

SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The proposed system is illustrated conceptually as a four-stage loop:

- 1) underwater image acquisition on the submarine,
- 2) frame transmission and debris detection on a host computer,
- 3) basin-coordinate localization and map update, and

- 4) XR display of the nearest target and the accumulated PSB detections.

RC submarine platform

The sensing platform is a battery-powered, dual-ballast RC submarine equipped with an ESP32-based camera module and a custom electronics stack. The camera acquires underwater video for downstream inference, while the submarine's propulsion and buoyancy system allow the platform to survey the basin from varying depths and viewpoints. The ESP32 family is a reasonable fit for this kind of compact wireless embedded system because it combines microcontroller functionality with integrated wireless connectivity and flexible peripheral support [17].

Detection model

The visual backend uses a YOLO-family detector trained specifically for underwater garbage recognition. In the current implementation, the model was fine-tuned on 12,177 garbage images, 5,720 of which were underwater, and the poster reports a detection precision of 92.1%. The detector produces class labels and image-space bounding boxes, which are then associated with submarine pose estimates for spatial registration.

Basin map and XR visualization

Photogrammetry and visual markers were used to align detections with a model of Peter Street Basin. A laptop receives the submarine's detections and updates a reduced basin map. These localized targets are then sent to the XR display, where the user sees both a miniature PSB map and a compass-like directional cue to the nearest debris item.

DETECTION AND LOCALIZATION PIPELINE

Image acquisition and inference

Let I_t denote the underwater frame acquired at time t . The detector returns a set of object hypotheses

$$\mathcal{D}_t = \{(b_i, c_i, s_i)\}_{i=1}^{N_t}, \quad (1)$$

where b_i is a bounding box, c_i is the predicted class, and s_i is the confidence score. We retain detections above a confidence threshold τ and forward them to the localization module.

Because underwater imagery often suffers from haze, low contrast, and refractive distortions, robust performance depends strongly on domain-specific training rather than direct transfer from terrestrial datasets alone [10], [11]. For that reason, our implementation uses a dedicated underwater garbage training set rather than a generic object dataset.

Fig. 2: Representative Peter Street Basin survey path with accumulated garbage detections registered in basin coordinates.

(a) Packaging/plastic debris. (b) Small distant detection.

Fig. 3: Example underwater garbage detections captured during PSB deployment.

Basin-coordinate registration

Let the submarine pose in basin coordinates at time t be

$$\mathbf{p}_t = [x_t, y_t, z_t]^T, \quad \psi_t \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2)$$

where (x_t, y_t) are planar basin coordinates, z_t is depth, and ψ_t is heading. For each accepted detection, we estimate a relative bearing θ_i and range r_i from the image geometry and current calibration. The corresponding basin-frame point is modeled as

$$\mathbf{g}_i = \begin{bmatrix} x_t + r_i \cos(\psi_t + \theta_i) \\ y_t + r_i \sin(\psi_t + \theta_i) \\ z_t + \Delta z_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where Δz_i captures the target's relative vertical offset. Each registered garbage hypothesis is then appended to the basin map.

Nearest-target cueing

If the current set of mapped targets is $\mathcal{G} = \{\mathbf{g}_k\}$, the XR system selects the next target by nearest-neighbor distance:

$$k^* = \arg \min_k \|\mathbf{g}_k - \mathbf{p}_t\|_2. \quad (4)$$

The displayed target distance is

$$d^* = \|\mathbf{g}_{k^*} - \mathbf{p}_t\|_2, \quad (5)$$

and the relative planar bearing shown to the user is

$$\phi^* = \text{atan2}(y_{k^*} - y_t, x_{k^*} - x_t) - \psi_t. \quad (6)$$

This allows the XR HUD to point directly toward the next collection candidate while simultaneously displaying a global basin overview.

XR INTERFACE

The XR interface is implemented as an Android application deployed to Vuzix Smart Swim goggles. The display contains three core elements:

- 1) a compass-like directional pointer to the nearest target,
- 2) a range readout in meters, and
- 3) a reduced PSB map containing the current submarine position and previously registered detections.

This interface is intentionally minimal. Rather than overwhelming the user with raw detections, it converts the perception stack into a simple action-oriented instruction: what class of item is nearest, how far away it is, and in what direction to move. That is especially useful in underwater tasks, where visibility is limited and the user benefits from concise, continuously updated guidance.

PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Basin mapping results

Fig. 2 shows a representative survey trajectory and the accumulation of mapped detections in Peter Street Basin coordinates. In the plotted run, the system recorded 130 detector hits in the `Other` class. Because these are frame-level detections along a continuous trajectory, they should be interpreted as detection events rather than de-duplicated physical objects.

Qualitative underwater detections

Fig. 3 shows two representative underwater detections. The first example captures packaging-like debris under turbid lighting, while the second shows a smaller distant object detected near the basin floor. These examples illustrate the diversity of appearance the model must handle, including partial occlusion, low contrast, and significant color shift.

HUD output

Fig. 4 shows the XR interface during operation. The display reports the target class as `Other`, indicates a range of 4.1 m, and uses a compass arrow to direct the user toward the selected target while showing a miniaturized PSB map with registered detections.

Fig. 4: XR head-up display showing the nearest target class, range, heading cue, and a reduced PSB map.

DISCUSSION

The results suggest that underwater cleanup assistance benefits from combining perception and guidance rather than treating object detection as an isolated backend task. The detector alone can identify likely debris, but the addition of basin registration and XR cueing turns those detections into actionable spatial instructions.

Several limitations remain. First, repeated observations of the same debris can inflate raw detection counts unless track association or spatial clustering is applied. Second, underwater image degradation still causes false negatives for low-contrast or heavily occluded items. Third, the localization quality depends on the stability of odometry and the fidelity of the basin registration.

Future work will focus on three directions:

- 1) multi-frame association for de-duplicating mapped objects,
- 2) underwater image enhancement or restoration prior to detection, and
- 3) closed-loop collection behaviors in which the submarine not only detects debris but also assists in retrieval planning.

CONCLUSION

This paper presented a garbage detection submarine system that integrates underwater computer vision, basin-scale spatial mapping, and XR visualization for Peter

Street Basin cleanup. A compact RC submarine acquires underwater imagery, a YOLO-family detector identifies marine debris, photogrammetric basin registration localizes detections, and XR goggles present the nearest target's direction and distance to the user. Together, these components form a practical human-in-the-loop pipeline for making submerged cleanup more spatially aware, interactive, and operationally efficient.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the project team, the Peter Street Basin community, and the facilities and inspiration that supported this work.

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Kolymphographic User-Interface: Kolymphographic User-Interface: Exploring Peter Street Basin by Remote or Virtual Vessel

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Fig. 1: Ship of Kolymphi: A vessel is propelled through Peter Street Basin by swimming in a pool situated atop the vessel. Kolymphographic activity turns propellers that move the vessel forward and steer it. Swimming faster makes the vessel go faster. Swimming backwards makes the vessel go backwards. Swimming left or right turns the vessel left or right, all from within a pool that is entirely aboard the vessel. As an art installation the Ship of Kolymphi is an inquiry into the right to touch and be touched by water, while exploring broader issues of water-human-technology interaction.

Abstract—The well-known Graphical User Interface (GUI) derives from the word “graphical”, which originates from the Ancient Greek γραφικός (graphikós), meaning “pertaining to painting, drawing, or writing”.

In this paper we propose and implement the Kolymphographic-User-Interface (KUI) which is a user-interface for operating a vessel by way of swimming gestures, or swim-like movements. We call such gestures or movements “kolymphographic” from the Greek word κολυμπώ (kolympó) which means “swim”.

We present two use-cases: (1) controlling a physical vessel using kolymphographic movements/gestures; and (2) controlling a Virtual Reality (VR) / eXtended Reality (XR) exploration of Peter Street Basin.

Index Terms—NUI, Mersivity, Computer Vision, Gesture Recognition, Extended Reality, Virtual Reality, Ship of Kolymphi

INTRODUCTION

Peter Street Basin is a part of Lake Ontario in downtown Toronto. It is a trapezoidal pool about 30m wide and 60m long, connected to the rest of the lake by an approximately 12m-wide channel, making it an ideal calm, quiet, contemplative space for conducting research. Friends of Peter Street Basin has undertaken to clean out the garbage collecting there, and explore the space using human-powered research vessels as described in Mersivity2025 [8], [7]. See, for example, Peter Street Basin Master Plan as outlined in pages 11-20 of [7].

As part of this effort, we undertook to scan Peter Street Basin using photogrammetry methods to build a 3-dimensional model that formed the basis for an XR experience.

Fig. 3: Modular version of The Ship of Kolympi made from an inflatable children’s wading pool placed on top of a large family-sized paddleboard. This is an AI-generated image based on the photograph of Fig. 1.

Fig. 2: Ship of Kolympi (AI-generated figure) computer-generated illustration showing the concept of a Kolympiographic User Interface, i.e. navigating a ship by way of swimming gestures or swimming-like movements. Figure used from [8].

SHIP OF KOLYMPI AS A NATURAL USER INTERFACE

A Natural User Interface (NUI) is defined as a user-interface in which both actions come naturally to human users, as well as one based on nature itself, i.e. physics (Natural Philosophy), and the natural environment. An example of an NUI in both senses is the hydraulophone as an input device, in which touching a natural element (water) becomes the user interface experience. The hydraulophone is an example of a broader class of musical instruments called “physiphones”, a term coined from the Greek words “physikos” (“nature”) and “phone” (“voice”).

Other previous examples of NUIs include the Ship of Kolympi, as shown in the photograph of Fig 1 [8], and the AI (Artificial Intelligence) renderings of Fig. 2 and 3 [8]. The ship’s name, Kolympi or Kolymvisis, derives from the Greek word for “swimming” (“κολύμπι” or “kolýmpi”).

The vessel is controlled by a pool that senses water flow using underwater sensors, so a swimmer can steer and control the vessel by swimming in the pool, as outlined in [8].

SOFTWARE

Gesture Detection

This section describes the vision pipeline used to detect arm movement and convert swimming gestures into actionable boat commands.

Image Pre-processing: The gesture-recognition system begins by converting frames from the RGB color space to the HSV space. This improves the robustness of colour-based segmentation under varying lighting conditions. After conversion, filtering is applied, and masks are generated to isolate the regions of interest corresponding to the user’s arms, as visible in Fig.5

Arm Detection: Following pre-processing, contours are extracted from candidate regions in the masked image. These contours are analyzed to identify arm-like structures and estimate movement trajectories over time, as visible in Fig.4.

Gesture-Command Mapping: The speed and direction of detected strokes are calculated and converted into control commands for the boat. These commands are then broadcast to a local network, controlling any device connected to it.

Fig. 4: Input frame with detected arm contours and centroid localization of a swim stroke.

Simulation Sandbox

A Unity-based environment was developed to test the system in a controlled virtual setting. This included a digital reconstruction of the Peter Street Basin, allowing users to pilot a virtual boat through natural swim gestures before deploying the same interaction model onto the physical system, as visible in Fig.6

Fig. 5: Processed binary mask after thresholding and morphological filtering.

Fig. 6: 3D point-cloud model of Peter Street Basin rendered to a virtual boat environment to gamify garbage detection, cleanup, and freshwater stewardship.

HARDWARE

C. Remote Web Camera

To capture the user's upper-body swimming gestures in real time, a high-definition webcam was mounted securely to the user's forehead via an adjustable elastic strap. It was then connected and processed by a Raspberry Pi 4 Model B (8GB), in order to maintain a compact form factor for mobile use. This allowed the vision pipeline to consistently track limb extensions untethered to a large computer.

D. Remote-Controlled Boat

The physical platform consists of a remote-controlled racing boat with onboard electronics, including an ESP8266, that can receive gesture-derived commands via a UDP socket over a local Wi-Fi network, interfacing with the Raspberry Pi. This allows the same recognition pipeline used in the simulation to be tested in a real-world aquatic setting.

VALIDATION

To determine robustness of the gesture processing pipeline, it was evaluated on accuracy and latency. For

accuracy, successful stroke detection was measured for a sample set of 5 different videos, each with a different number and style of swim strokes. This included a real-world first-person view of a swimmer. Latency was measured from the capture of a frame to the successful reception of a control command by the Unity simulation. To fine-tune control outputs, evaluate gesture responsiveness, and refine the pipeline, simulations were run using the Unity-based simulation environment.

RESULTS

The final system demonstrated that swim gestures can be used as an intuitive input method for boat control in both virtual and physical domains. In the Unity simulation, users could navigate a virtual vessel through the Peter Street Basin environment using only upper-body motion. In the physical implementation, the same gesture-recognition framework successfully transmitted movement instructions to the racing boat platform.

These results suggest that gesture-based aquatic interaction can serve as a practical and immersive alternative to traditional control interfaces.

CONCLUSION

This work presents a natural user interface for boat control based on swim gesture recognition. By combining computer vision, simulation, and physical actuation, the project demonstrates how intuitive human movement can be translated into real-time control across both virtual and real aquatic environments. The framework contributes to the broader goal of designing interactive systems that are better suited to environments where conventional interfaces are ineffective.

FUTURE WORK

Future work could expand the system toward XR-based interaction, tighter sensor integration, and improved embedded control hardware. One possible direction is to combine the full recognition and control pipeline into a more compact onboard processing unit, allowing greater autonomy and portability. Additional improvements could include fusing inertial sensing with vision to better handle head rotation and transient occlusion, more robust gesture classification, and deployment in fully immersive aquatic mixed-reality systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge the ideas of many members of the Friends of Peter Street Basin, including Daniel Bros, Chris McGale, Micheal Herra, and Chan Park for help with this project.

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“Neurow™”: Neural Rowing with Chirplet Transform and S.W.I.M.-Based Neurofeedback

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Fig. 1: Custom paddle and custom rowing machine each equipped with a S.W.I.M. (Sequential Wave Imprinting Machine) for neurofeedback. When on water, the paddle traces out EMG (electromyograph) during physical exertion to show muscle activity as a function of space. For dryland training, a special rowing machine was built from an existing machine which traces out a curved arc showing EMG activity for neurofeedback. Long-exposure video and photos of the participant captures live EMG activity rendered as a S.W.I.M. trace.

Abstract—NeuroRow™ is a stroke-synchronous peripheral nervous sensing, display, and biofeedback system for rowing, paddling, and other cyclically periodic exercise activity that we developed in the 1980s. We brought this work to MIT in the 1990s, University of Toronto in the 2000s, and Stanford University in the mid 2010s and presently teach it as part of ongoing lectures and labs. It uses a S.W.I.M. (Sequential Wave Imprinting Machine) to spatialize muscle activity on its temporally persistent LED trace. Neuro works with the peripheral nervous system by way of EMG (ElectroMyoGraphy), and, optionally also connects to the central nervous system by way of EEG (ElectroEncephaloGraphy), both of which are analyzed using the warblet chirplet transform that was originally designed for marine applications in 1991. Neuro facilitates neurofeedback during whole-body water-based exercises, e.g. using a waterproof S.W.I.M. and EMG system. We present some results from the use of Neuro in teaching undergraduate and graduate students of Electrical and Computer Engineering at the University of Toronto in Canada where rowing is a popular sport owing to the close proximity to Lake Ontario and, in particular, the Ontario Place West Channel which is an ideal location for rowing. For teaching and research, we also created a dataset containing 1,347 segmented rowing strokes from six EMG-bearing rowers across 28 trials, plus 254 bicep-curl repetitions from two EMG-bearing subjects for comparison. We release the dataset, scripts, Croissant metadata, and leaderboard protocol as a reusable framework for larger rowing neurofeedback studies.

Index Terms—NeuroRow™, InteraXon Muse™, rowing, EMG (ElectroMyoGram), EEG (ElectroEncephaloGram), neurofeed-

back, S.W.I.M. (Sequential Wave Imprinting Machine), chirplet transform, warblet transform (warbling chirplet transform), cyclostationary signals, multimodal sensing, benchmark, leakage-free evaluation.

I. INTRODUCTION: HISTORICAL CONTEXT

The Sequential Wave Imprinting Machine (S.W.I.M.) invented by author S. Mann in the 1970s [1]–[3] is an XR/XI (Extended Reality/eXtended Intelligence) [4]–[6] device consisting of an addressible light source such as a linear array of light sources that trace out waveforms as a function of space. See Fig 2. When used with neural activity, the resulting “NeuroSWIM™” makes visible the electrical signals that flow within the human body. NeuroSWIM can show brainwaves from the central nervous system, or EMG (ElectroMyoGraphy) signals from the peripheral nervous system as shown in Fig 2. Here cyclic repeating activity traces out patterns much like an oscilloscope does, but doing so as a function of space rather than time, so that the activity is seen spatialized in the physical world in alignment with what is physically happening in the world with muscle activity.

A new mathematical transform called the Chirplet Transform [7], along with variations of the chirplet transform such as ACT (Adaptive Chirplet Transform) [8] was combined with S.W.I.M. as reported in 1992 [2].

Fig. 2: Wristworn S.W.I.M.(Sequential Wave Imprinting Machine) here with dryland exercises, surface EMG, and consumer EEG waveforms visible while waving the arm back-and-forth. When connected to the EMG from muscle activity it makes visible the electricity flowing in the peripheral nervous system during dumbbell rowing, or other similar exercises.

In 1992, the “Warblet” and “Warblet transform” inventions were reported and have subsequently been widely used for cyclostationary signals and signals from repeating processes such as rowing or other exercise [9]–[13].

SWIM and the Chirplet Transform, Adaptive Chirplet Transform, and Warblet Transform were applied to neuroscience, physical fitness, exercise, and the like in the 1990s, and later in the 2000s with the founding of InteraXon, makers of the Muse, Muse-S, and Muse-S Athena [14].

In the 2000s, InteraXon was founded at Mann’s principal residence in Toronto at 330 Dundas Street West, a home research lab for neuroscience, physical fitness, and health technologies including SWIM, the Chirplet Transform, and other technologies for health, fitness, and neuroscience.

Over a period of about 25 years at this location, NeuroSWIM was developed to provides athletes with neuroscience-based visual feedback on brain and neuromuscular activity. NeuroSWIM combines advanced neuroscience with data visualization using SWIM and data analysis using the Chirplet Transform, the Adaptive Chirplet Transform (ACT), and the Warblet Transform.

In 2014, NeuroSWIM was introduced to a University of Toronto Varsity Blues Rowing coach and further work was done on adapting this invention to use with cyclic sports activities like rowing, paddling, weightlifting, and cycling.

In 2016, this “Neurow” (NeuroSWIM applied to rowing) was taken to Stanford University’s Department of Neurosurgery. There, in collaboration with Professor Michel Kliot at the Center for Peripheral Nerve Surgery at Stanford University the invention was further tested for exercise, fitness, rehabilitation, and neurosurgery.

Mann and others have been refining this technology with the eventual goal of commercialization for high-performance sport, neuroscience, fitness, rehabilitation, and neurosurgery, in an ongoing project being undertaken with diligent pursuit.

In 2018, the NeuroSWIM invention was presented to sponsors and investors at Ford Motor Company in Windsor, Ontario, in the context of designing motor vehicles for being accessible to persons with disabilities, demonstrating how a motor vehicle could be operated by the peripheral nervous system, using NeuroSWIM as a form of biofeedback. This demonstration was done on the afternoon of May 30, 2018, and a series of other demonstrations were provided with a goal of commercializing this invention.

The NeuroSWIM / Neurow invention has been used regularly at the University of Toronto for teaching and research purposes, and formed the basis for a submission to IEEE I2MTC2026 [15].

A. Motivation

The motivation for this work is our love of water, rowing, and paddling, beyond simply standard events like Head of the Charles, to also explore the creation of new water-based events and technologies. Among these new events is our IM Regatta (Individual Medley Regatta) comprised of the following: 60m butterfly paddling; 60m backstroke paddling;

60m breaststroke paddling; and 60m freestyle paddling, all done without swimming! Swimming is not allowed; getting a ticket for swimming results in disqualification. See Fig 3. In this sense we have the NO SWIMMING Individual Medley Regatta (Fig 4), or, simply, the N-SIM (NO-SWIM Individual Medley), sometimes written **SIM**, or “IM Regatta” or “IM Boating” where the NO SWIMMING can be implied by its being a regatta or boating event.

The goal of the IM Regatta is to create technology that connects us to each other and our environment, e.g. our lakes and waterways, consistent with other related initiatives like SWIMMABLE CITIES, forming a technological bridge as we aim to increase acceptance of swimming at the liminal space between swimming and boating == urban limnology / “liminology”. Technologies include sensing and metasensing, XR (eXtended Reality) racing, and Integral Kinesiology, such as paddling along a two-dimensional manifold of a four-dimensional quaternion space as sensed by IMUs (Inertial Measurement Units) within each vessel.

Additionally, many of the activities involve neural biofeedback during the events, or as part of the training for the events.

II. OVERVIEW

Real-time neurofeedback can modulate neural engagement, but most successful paradigms remain sedentary, unimodal, and evaluated within subject. Exercise breaks these assumptions: it introduces motion artifacts, changes physiological state stroke-by-stroke, and requires central neural activity to coordinate with peripheral motor output under closed-loop sensory feedback. Indoor rowing is a natural testbed because it is rhythmic, whole-body, stationary, and structured into catch, drive, finish, and recovery phases.

This paper introduces a small-cohort but rigorously controlled benchmark for multimodal exercise neurofeedback for Neurow. The goal is not to claim population-level effects from six rowers. Instead, the contribution is a *contract-first* benchmark: pre-specified gates, subject-held-out evaluation, negative controls, leakage diagnostics, conformal calibration, and robustness audits.

a) *Why a contract-first benchmark matters.:* At small cohort sizes, a model that has learned physiological signal can look identical to one that has learned subject identity, trial ID, missingness, condition order, cadence, or random-window leakage. NeuroRow therefore makes several choices by design: random-window splits are diagnostic only; all preprocessing is fold-internal; negative controls are reported alongside task scores; calibration is audited per subject; and every claim is mapped to a frozen numerical gate.

b) *Contributions.:*

- 1) **A synchronized exercise neurofeedback dataset.** NeuroRow includes consumer EEG, surface EMG, head-mounted IMU, VR/audio feedback, and S.W.I.M. visual EMG biofeedback during rowing, with a secondary bicep-curl probe.
- 2) **A pre-registered benchmark contract.** Seven tasks and their pilot/full thresholds are frozen in

Fig. 3: **Two variations of the IM Regatta:** Simple Polynesian (prone) paddleboarding as compared with engineering and design teams creating new technologies for accessibility with connection to water. The IM (Individual Medley) consists of 60m butterfly paddling; 60m backstroke; 60m breaststroke; 60m freestyle paddling, all of which must be completed without swimming. In the XR (eXtended Reality) version, contestants must paddle along a two-dimensional manifold of a four-dimensional quaternion space along a path of exact cisoidal oscillation [16], further developing core-strength and balance.

results/win_conditions.yaml at commit d602a54.

- 3) **Leakage-safe evaluation.** The primary split is leave-one-subject-out; random-window results are excluded from gates; twelve negative controls expose shortcut learning.
- 4) **Feasibility results with honest failures.** At $N = 6$, five rowing gates plus robustness clear full thresholds, while cross-modal retrieval fails and feedback-conditioned prediction remains pilot-only.
- 5) **A scalable powered-cohort protocol.** The same scripts and gates are intended to scale to $N = 20\text{--}50$ with 1 kHz EMG and hardware TTL synchronization.

What this paper does not claim. We do not claim EEG-only rowing-phase decoding, tuned ACT superiority, DigitalTwin policy efficacy, robust cross-modal EEG–EMG retrieval, or population-level neurofeedback effects from the current cohort.

III. RELATED WORK

a) Neurofeedback and exercise.: EEG neurofeedback has been studied in cognitive and motor-performance settings, but much of the evidence comes from controlled, sedentary paradigms. Exercise-based neurofeedback is harder because

the signal is non-stationary, motion-contaminated, and tightly coupled to the motor task.

b) EMG and rowing.: Surface EMG is commonly used to study muscular coordination during cyclic exercise. Rowing is particularly useful because each stroke has interpretable phases and a natural cadence. However, EMG alone does not capture central neural engagement or feedback processing.

c) Consumer EEG and multimodal BCI.: Consumer EEG systems such as Muse provide low-cost, portable neural sensing, but they are vulnerable to motion, electrode quality, and subject-specific artifacts. Hybrid EEG–EMG approaches can improve robustness, but many existing studies rely on within-subject or within-session splits that do not test generalization.

d) Benchmark gap.: Existing public datasets typically cover either EMG/motion, sedentary EEG, or small hybrid BCI settings. NeuroRow differs by combining synchronized EEG and EMG during whole-body exercise, feedback-condition manipulation, subject-held-out evaluation, negative controls, conformal calibration, and public leaderboard scaffolding.

IV. DATASET AND APPARATUS

Participants performed rowing trials on a stationary ergometer and bicep-curl trials while seated. Rowing conditions

Fig. 4: Our **NO SWIMMING** Individual Medley Regatta™, an activity that requires extensive dryland training to achieve a high level of physical fitness.

included no-feedback, visual, audio, and audiovisual feedback. The visual condition used the S.W.I.M. device, which renders the EMG envelope as a temporally persistent LED trace. Long-exposure photographs make it possible to visually audit whether the feedback was present, stable, saturated, or delayed; these photographs are not used as features or labels.

a) Modalities.: EEG was recorded from Muse-class headbands at 256 Hz using four consumer electrodes. EMG was recorded from surface sensors at 60–1600 Hz depending on the session and harmonized to a 100 Hz common grid. IMU streams were recorded from the head-mounted device when available. Missing EMG channels are padded and handled by

fold-internal imputation.

b) Cohort.: The release contains thirteen participants across rowing and bicep curls. Six rowing participants have synchronized EMG, yielding **1,347 segmented rowing strokes** across **28 trials**. Two bicep-curl participants have EMG, yielding **254 repetitions**. The May 6 expansion increased the rowing EMG cohort from three to six subjects.

c) Synchronization and preprocessing.: Signals are aligned using wall-clock interpolation onto a 100 Hz grid. EMG is rectified and smoothed to form an envelope for stroke segmentation. EEG preprocessing includes standard filtering where applicable. All task-specific preprocessing is fit inside the training fold only.

V. BENCHMARK CONTRACT

The benchmark contract is frozen in `results/win_conditions.yaml`. Each task has a pilot threshold and a stricter full-cohort threshold. The seven tasks are:

- 1) **Phase decoding:** classify catch, drive, finish, and recovery.
- 2) **Next-stroke residual prediction:** predict next-stroke EMG/cadence targets beyond persistence.
- 3) **Cross-modal retrieval:** align EEG and EMG embeddings from the same stroke.
- 4) **Feedback-conditioned prediction:** test whether feedback condition improves residual prediction.
- 5) **Few-shot personalization:** measure improvement after short subject-specific adaptation.
- 6) **Entrainment:** quantify within-subject effect sizes across feedback conditions.
- 7) **Uncertainty calibration:** evaluate conformal coverage globally and per subject.

Random-window results never satisfy a gate. They are reported only as leakage diagnostics. ACT placeholder outputs are rejected at runtime and cannot satisfy a gate.

VI. STROKE PROCESSING AND MODELS

a) Stroke segmentation.: The default segmentation method detects peaks in the rectified EMG envelope. A prominence sweep selects the threshold that maximizes cadence consistency over plausible rowing rates. When EMG is absent, a rowing-only IMU fallback estimates stroke rhythm from head acceleration in the 0.2–2 Hz range. This fallback is disabled for bicep curls because the head is not mechanically coupled to the movement.

b) Phase labels.: Each stroke is divided into catch, drive, finish, and recovery using audited phase-labeling rules. Phase-normalized features resample each phase to fixed bins, preventing sparse feature positions from trivially encoding phase.

c) Models.: The benchmark includes small-data-safe models and baselines: Random Forests and ExtraTrees, Stroke-TCN, contrastive EEG–EMG encoders with hard same-subject negatives, a feedback-conditioned residual DigitalTwin scaffold, and calibrated regressors. Published EEG baselines include

EEGNet, ShallowConvNet, and DeepConvNet. ACT and NeuroFeedbackFormerACT are included as roadmap infrastructure but are not used to make current full-gate claims.

VII. LEAKAGE-FREE EVALUATION

For each fold, the pipeline fits imputation, scaling, feature selection, residualization, and the estimator only on the training set before evaluating on the held-out subject. The primary split is leave-one-subject-out (LOSO). Session-held-out and trial-held-out splits are secondary. Random-window splits are reported only to show how much leakage can inflate performance.

Twelve negative controls test shortcut hypotheses: label shuffle, time-shifted EEG–EMG, missingness-only, subject ID, trial ID, block order, cadence-only, time-within-session, fatigue proxy, quality artifacts, condition order, and random-window splitting. Under LOSO, these controls remain near chance, while the random-window diagnostic reaches a much higher score, confirming why it is excluded from all claims.

VIII. MAIN ROWING RESULTS

A. Phase Label-Consistency

The best no-cadence Random Forest reaches LOSO macro F1 0.702 with bootstrap CI lower 0.653. EMG-only and all-feature variants also clear the full gate. However, this result is deliberately interpreted as **label-consistency validation**, not independent physiological decoding, because phase labels are derived from EMG envelopes and EMG features are computed within those same phase boundaries.

EEG-only models remain near chance: EEGNet reaches 0.195, ShallowConvNet 0.245, DeepConvNet 0.192, and hand-crafted EEG-only Random Forest 0.100. This supports the paper’s central caution: the current dataset validates the segmentation/labeling pipeline but does not show EEG-only rowing-phase decoding.

B. Next-Stroke Residual Prediction

ExtraTrees with multi-output regression achieves aggregate RMSE reduction 0.233 over persistence on 1,089 valid stroke pairs. The strongest targets are cadence and EMG timing features, including `cadence_spm` and `emg_peak_timing_frac`. Some coordination targets remain weak or negative, especially co-contraction index and left-right asymmetry. Thus the safe claim is short-horizon prediction above persistence, not broad physiological forecasting.

C. Few-Shot Personalization

All six held-out rowing subjects improve after 60 seconds of subject-specific ridge-head adaptation. The largest improvement is S3, with a +0.441 gap over zero-shot. The result suggests that small amounts of calibration can recover subject-specific stroke structure under LOSO evaluation.

D. Cross-Modal Retrieval Failure

Cross-modal retrieval fails at $N = 6$. Matched EEG–EMG MRR is 0.038, essentially identical to shuffled MRR 0.037 and time-shifted MRR 0.038. This is a useful failure: the negative controls reveal that the contrastive model does not learn robust same-stroke EEG–EMG alignment under the heterogeneous six-subject cohort.

E. Feedback-Conditioned Prediction

Feedback-conditioned prediction remains pilot-only. The best residual R^2 gain is +0.023 on `emg_stroke_smoothness`, but the mean across non-baseline configurations remains below the full threshold. Condition imbalance is a major limitation because only one subject contributes audio trials.

F. Entrainment and Calibration

The May 6 expansion flips entrainment from pilot to full: mean within-subject $|d|$ rises to 0.650 across finite condition pairs, with the strongest effect on EMG burst duration. Conformal calibration also clears the full gate on `cadence_spm`, reaching coverage 0.863 at nominal 0.90, with all six subjects within the pre-specified per-subject tolerance band.

IX. ROBUSTNESS AUDITS

A key concern is whether one unusual subject drives the apparent full-gate passes. NeuroRow includes two robustness audits.

a) *Leave-one-each-out.*: Each of the six rowing subjects is removed in turn, and the main full-gate tasks are rerun. Across phase decoding, next-stroke prediction, and few-shot personalization, **17/18** task–held-out pairs remain full-pass. The only drop is S4’s next-stroke RMSE-reduction, which falls to pilot-only.

b) *N-subsample sensitivity.*: All subject pairs and triples are evaluated across phase decoding, next-stroke residual prediction, and few-shot personalization. Across 105 subset–task evaluations, **65/105** clear full and **102/105** clear pilot. Few-shot personalization is the most robust, clearing full in every subset.

X. CROSS-EXERCISE PROBE: BICEP CURLS

The bicep-curl cohort is included as a cross-exercise probe using the same benchmark philosophy. Two EMG-bearing subjects contribute 254 repetitions. The rowing-specific IMU fallback is disabled because seated curls do not produce reliable head-motion stroke rhythm.

Phase decoding reaches 0.477 and entrainment reaches mean $|d| = 0.830$, clearing the corresponding gates at feasibility scale. Next-stroke prediction fails with aggregate RMSE reduction -0.062 , likely because curls are self-paced and lack the ergometer-imposed cadence that anchors rowing. Calibration also fails. Cross-modal retrieval, feedback-conditioned prediction, and few-shot personalization are not run on bicep because the cohort is too small and condition coverage is imbalanced.

Fig. 5: **Stroke-synchronous processing pipeline.** Raw multimodal streams are aligned, segmented into rowing strokes, divided into phase labels, and audited before subject-held-out evaluation.

TABLE I: **Main rowing gate results at $N = 6$.**

Task	Result	Status	Safe claim
Phase decoding	Macro F1 0.702, CI low 0.653	Full	EMG-label consistency
Next-stroke residual	RMSE reduction 0.233, $p < 10^{-3}$	Full	Above persistence
Few-shot personalization	Best 60s gap +0.441	Full	Short adaptation helps
Cross-modal retrieval	MRR 0.038 vs. shuffled 0.037	Fail	No robust EEG-EMG retrieval
Feedback-conditioned prediction	Max residual R^2 gain 0.023	Pilot	Directional only
Entrainment	Mean within-subject $ d = 0.650$	Full	Feedback-linked modulation
Uncertainty calibration	Coverage 0.863 at nominal 0.90	Full	Calibrated on cadence target
LOEO robustness	17/18 task-held-out pairs full-pass	Full	Not single-subject driven

(a) Benchmark gate summary.

(b) Negative-control and leakage diagnostics.

Fig. 6: **Benchmark results and leakage controls.** NeuroRow reports task performance alongside negative controls so that apparent model performance can be separated from subject identity, trial identity, cadence shortcuts, or random-window leakage.

XI. LIMITATIONS

NeuroRow is a feasibility benchmark, not a population-level study. The main rowing cohort has six EMG-bearing subjects, and the bicep probe has two. EMG hardware is heterogeneous, synchronization is wall-clock based rather than hardware TTL, and several trials have missing channels. These issues are explicitly logged and handled by the loader, but they limit the strength of physiological claims.

The phase-decoding result is not independent EEG decoding; it validates EMG-derived phase labels. Next-stroke prediction is strongest for cadence and timing targets, while several coordination targets remain weak. Cross-modal retrieval fails at $N = 6$, and feedback-conditioned prediction is pilot-only. ACT

and NeuroFeedbackFormerACT are roadmap infrastructure only, not current evidence.

The powered-cohort protocol addresses these limitations by targeting $N = 20-50$, 2-3 sessions per subject, balanced feedback conditions, 1 kHz EMG, and hardware TTL synchronization, while preserving the exact same evaluation contract.

XII. RESPONSIBLE RELEASE

The dataset is intended for methodological research on leakage-controlled multimodal neurofeedback. It is not a clinical decision-support tool. Released data use pseudonymous identifiers; demographic identifiers are not released except where coarsely binned; raw audio is not released. Leaderboard

(a) Next-stroke prediction summary.

(b) Per-target prediction breakdown.

Fig. 7: **Next-stroke residual prediction.** The strongest pilot effects appear on cadence and timing targets, while several coordination targets remain weak or negative.

(a) Conformal calibration curves.

(b) Prediction interval audit.

Fig. 8: **Uncertainty calibration.** Split-conformal intervals are evaluated globally and per subject to test whether nominal coverage remains meaningful under subject-held-out evaluation.

(a) N -subsample sensitivity.

(b) Few-shot personalization curves.

Fig. 9: **Robustness and personalization audits.** Subject-subset sensitivity and short calibration curves test whether feasibility-scale results are fragile or recoverable under held-out-subject evaluation.

rules disqualify submissions that exploit subject identity, demographic inference, random-window leakage, or other shortcut features.

The code is designed to run on modest compute. The current pilot pipeline can be reproduced CPU-only, with optional GPU acceleration for EEG baselines. Data are released under CC-BY 4.0 and code under MIT, with Croissant metadata and a permanent archival plan for the camera-ready version.

XIII. CONCLUSION

NeuroRow provides a leakage-controlled benchmark for stroke-synchronous EEG-EMG neurofeedback during exercise. At $N = 6$, the apparatus supports several feasibility-level claims: EMG phase-label consistency, next-stroke prediction above persistence, few-shot personalization, entrainment, calibrated uncertainty on cadence, and robustness to subject

removal. It also exposes important failures, especially cross-modal retrieval and feedback-conditioned prediction.

The central contribution is therefore not a single model, but a reusable benchmark contract: pre-registered gates, subject-held-out evaluation, negative controls, conformal calibration, and robustness audits. The same contract is ready to scale to a powered cohort with standardized EMG and hardware synchronization.

APPENDIX A COMPACT DATASET CARD

Motivation. NeuroRow is designed to test leakage-safe modeling of stroke-synchronous EEG-EMG data during exercise neurofeedback.

(a) Feedback-condition entrainment effects.

(b) Phase-locked EMG burst structure.

Fig. 10: **Feedback-linked modulation.** Entrainment and phase-locked burst structure provide feasibility-scale evidence that feedback conditions modulate measurable rowing dynamics.

Composition. The release contains 1,347 rowing strokes from six EMG-bearing rowers across 28 trials, plus 254 bicep-curl repetitions from two EMG-bearing subjects.

Modalities. EEG, EMG, head-mounted IMU, trial-level feedback condition, stroke boundaries, phase labels, quality flags, and continuous stroke targets.

Recommended split. LOSO is primary. Session-held-out and trial-held-out are secondary. Random-window is diagnostic only.

Known noise. Consumer EEG motion artifacts, EMG saturation/flatlines, missing channels, headset variation, and wall-clock synchronization skew.

Intended use. Benchmarking leakage-safe multimodal modeling, calibration, and neurofeedback evaluation. Not intended for clinical inference.

APPENDIX B COMPACT GATE CONTRACT

TABLE II: Summary of the pre-registered gate contract.

Task	Full-gate criterion, summarized
Phase decoding	LOSO macro F1 ≥ 0.55 and CI lower ≥ 0.50
Next-stroke residual	RMSE reduction ≥ 0.15 with significant paired improvement
Cross-modal retrieval	Matched MRR ≥ 0.30 and clearly above shuffled/time-shifted controls
Feedback-conditioned prediction	Mean residual R^2 gain ≥ 0.05 with shuffled-feedback gap
Few-shot personalization	60s adaptation gap ≥ 0.10 on at least two tasks
Entrainment	Mean within-subject $ d \geq 0.5$
Uncertainty calibration	Global and per-subject coverage within pre-specified bands

APPENDIX C COMPACT REVIEWER CONCERNS

a) *Small cohort.*: The current cohort is intentionally framed as feasibility-scale. The purpose is to release and stress-test the benchmark contract before scaling to $N = 20$ –50.

b) *Circular phase labels.*: Phase labels are EMG-envelope-derived, so phase decoding is reported as label-consistency validation. EEG-only baselines near chance prevent overclaiming.

c) *Cross-modal failure.*: The cross-modal retrieval failure is not hidden. It demonstrates that the negative controls catch a model that does not learn robust EEG–EMG alignment.

d) *Random-window leakage.*: Random-window results are reported only as a warning. They never satisfy a gate.

e) *ACT and transformer models.*: ACT and NeuroFeedbackFormerACT are included for the powered cohort, but no tuned-ACT or transformer superiority claim is made at $N = 6$.

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“Cocaine Buzzkill”, An XR Game To Take Aim Against the Drug Epidemic

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Fig. 1. Cocaine Buzzkill combines outdoor cold exposure, wearable brain sensing, and XR gameplay. The game may be played with a Muse headband alone or with XR headsets such as Meta Quest 3S or Apple Vision Pro.

Abstract—We introduce *Cocaine Buzzkill*, an outdoor XR (eXtended Reality) game that takes aim against the cocaine epidemic through the gamification of cold-exposure. It uses actual cold-plunges as a user-interface in which players plunge in snow to bring themselves into a mental “state-of-snow” as sensed by an InteraXon brain-sensing headband. It builds on well-known research that shows cold-exposure induces the same kind of “high” that cocaine does. Players throw real snowballs at virtual targets while the players get “high” on cold exposure. The “high” is determined as a beta-to-alpha brainwave ratio that modulates game dynamics.

Index Terms—Cocaine Buzzkill™, cocaine, crack cocaine, fentanyl, drug addiction, supervised consumption, cold exposure, cold plunge, rehabilitation, eXtended Reality (XR), Brain-Computer Interface (BCI), ElectroEncephaloGram (EEG), InteraXon Muse™, neurofeedback

I. THE “IDEA”

CocaineBuzzkill™ is a high-tech, futuristic game in a fictional city dominated by an oppressive government and

its corrupt megacorporations alongside societal decay. The game that takes place in a fictional dystopian city where its mayor smokes crack cocaine and has banned winter swimming because cold-plunges compete with his family’s drug-dealing business.

The game takes many forms, such as, for example, a first-person-shooter game where players take aim to end the crack cocaine epidemic by shooting-out the flame in the mayor’s crackpipe by launching snowballs. Players quite literally kill the “buzz” (extinguish the flame) of the mayor’s virtual crackpipe by cooling the virtual pipe down with real snow.

The game is played by wearing a swimsuit and a Muse brain-sensing headband fitted with a first-person camera. Players must do cold-plunges in the winter snow on land, since winter swimming in the lake has been banned by the crack-smoking mayor.

When players jump into a snow bank, the Muse brain-sensor detects elevated dopamine in the brain, triggering the launch

of snowballs in the game.

Cold-plunges or icewater swims provide a gradual, sustained release of dopamine that can remain elevated for several hours, leading to prolonged feelings of alertness, focus, and improved mood without a subsequent crash. It also releases norepinephrine and endorphins, contributing to stress reduction and resilience

Cocaine causes a rapid and sharp spike in dopamine levels, which is then followed by a quick crash below the baseline, often leading to intense cravings and a desire for more of the substance. This acute, high-intensity spike and subsequent crash contribute to its addictive nature and harmful side effects.

Cold plunges offer a natural, healthier way to stimulate the brain's reward system and enhance mental well-being, while cocaine provides a transient, potentially harmful "high". For individuals in recovery from addiction, cold exposure can serve as a beneficial, non-addictive way to achieve a similar "buzz" or a distraction from cravings.

In the fictional dystopian city of the game-play, the government has banned winter swimming (simply by banning any kind of swimming when no lifeguards are present, e.g. in the off-season) and is also removing bike lanes and deliberately leaving sidewalks in disrepair, while investing all its money in road maintenance, drug distribution, Supervised Consumption Services, and Medical Assistance in Dying (MAiD), to encourage dependency on drugs, automobiles, and motorboats (also useful for drug distribution). The government has also clearcut the city's only beachfront forest, to privatize its best beach for a nearly bankrupt foreign corporation. Presently the government is weaponizing pollution, dumping raw sewage by the beach to discourage swimming. This creates a dystopia that is more conducive to substance abuse. Increased drug use profits the mayor's family, not to mention the fact that motor vehicles and motorboats generate more tax revenue than swimming, cycling, or walking.

This fictionally dystopia thus sets an important backdrop for the game-play.

The game, CocaineBuzzkill, uses image-based rendering on a Raspberry Pi, with photographs of the mayor smoking a crackpipe, along with photographs of the city's police enforcing the ban on swimming.

The Pi is connected to a Meshtastic network, as part of a grass-roots bottom-up ("sousveillant") network that cannot be stopped or censored by the government or its cocaine cartel.

The game uses Intelligent Image Processing to track the flight of real snowballs thrown by participants in bathing suits while "high" from cold-exposure. The path of the snowball is tracked by the headworn cameras to control the game cursor on a trajectory to the crackpipe in a displayed photograph of the mayor smoking crack.

The ability of the snowball to extinguish the flame is the product of accuracy and "high". In order to score one must simultaneously have good aim and be "high". In this way the name of the game ("Cocaine Buzzkill") is a double-entendre: (1) you literally kill the mayor's "buzz" (crack pipe flame), by (2) being "high" (on cold-exposure) yourself, i.e. your

"kill ratio" in the game requires you to yourself experience a "buzz": You get a "kill" when you get a "buzz".

Thus "buzzkill" gets its usual slang meaning of ruining a good mood, excitement, or enjoyment of the mayor smoking crack, along with a new meaning: To kill (the flame in the crackpipe) while being in a mental state of "buzz".

During game-play, the mental state of "buzz" is conveyed to each player by way of a vibrotactile buzzer mounted in each Muse brain-sensing headband. There is a 34-ohm buzzer is connected to GPIO pin 12 through a 100-ohm resistor (134 ohm series total) resulting in a maximum current drain of 37mA on the 3.3-volt PWM (Pulse-Width Modulation) pin. The buzzer begins rotating at about 1.7 volts when approached from 0 volts, and continues buzzing down to about 1.5 volts (i.e. it exhibits a small amount of hysteresis). Whereas a transistor should be used here, it is omitted for simplicity, making it very easy to wire, so that the game can be deployed across all age groups right down to complete novice level.

Additionally, the built-in flash light (super-bright white LED) on the ESP32 cam board is also a "highlight" that indicates when a player is "high" and runs from GPIO pin 4.

A mesh architecture using ESPnow operates between headbands and a host Raspberry Pi connected to a Meshtastic hooked up to a large-screen TV showing the mayor smoking a crack pipe. The game objective is to launch snowballs to kill the flame of the crack pipe.

In this way it allows for first-person shooter games without violence, e.g. throwing harmless snowballs rather than a gun.

The idea is to kill the flame in the crack pipe which actually saves lives rather than to kill someone, i.e. to save lives rather than take a life.

Points are scored by "shooting out" the crack pipe using snowballs to cool it down and cause the flame to go out.

The general idea is to get "high" on snow angels rather than crack cocaine.

We presented this idea and concept widely, e.g. at the UTRA Hacks keynote and at the largest Cursor meetup keynote where we did a live demonstration of the game as the keynote address (Fig 2)

II. BACKGROUND

We created a cold-water swimming community, SwimOP, that has grown to approximately 5000 members. Within this group, we observed that many participants were former cocaine users who had transitioned to cold-plunges instead. This motivated us to research further and discover that cocaine and cold plunges have similar effects on the brain, i.e. that a very unhealthy activity could be replaced with a much healthier activity. We also looked further at cold exposure, brain sensing, and extended reality to combine them into an engaging behavioral intervention.

The global crack cocaine and fentanyl epidemic continues to worsen. In Canada, 53,308 apparent opioid and stimulant toxicity deaths were recorded between January 2016 and June 2025, cocaine being implicated in 63 percent of accidental

Fig. 2. As the keynote address for the largest Cursor meetup we did a live demonstration of CocaineBuzzkill with live streaming video, brainwave data, and gameplay. The game was developed in Curor as well.

opioid-related fatalities nationally [1]. Although Cognitive Behavioral Therapy and Contingency Management are widely used, these interventions often occur in clinical settings that do not reproduce the real-world triggers associated with relapse [2].

Cold water immersion therapy offers physiological contrast stimulus. Sramek et al. reported that immersion in cold water produced a 250 percent increase in plasma dopamine and a 530 percent increase in norepinephrine [3]. Unlike cocaine, this arousal is generated endogenously and does not involve the same pharmacological pathway, crash, or receptor down-regulation. This suggests that cold exposure may serve as a substitute reinforcer for some of the motivational and affective deficits associated with stimulant withdrawal.

We present *Cocaine Buzzkill*, a series of XR-based games such as a wave-based shooter game played outdoors during snow exposure or cold-plunge contexts, as well as a cold-plunge game that does not require any special eyewear. The games can be played with a Muse headband alone or with XR hardware such as Meta Quest 3 or Apple Vision Pro. In one of the prototypes, players throw real snowballs at symbolic drug-related targets, such as a crack-pipe flame or a “NO SWIMMING” sign, while virtual elements are overlaid on the physical environment. The central gameplay slogan is:

The name of the game is to take aim against the flame.

Some embodiments of the game use direct hardware-based technologies such as our MuseCroc hardware that reads directly from InteraXon Muse devices [4], [5] (Fig 3) and other

Fig. 3. Prototype collective-high hardware. An ESP32, haptic motor, buzzer, and light attached to a Muse 2 headband provide shared arousal feedback across participants.

hardware such as an HB100 radar set embedded behind a poster of a crack pipe that participants throw real snowballs at. The Doppler radar picks up the snowball trajectory which is multiplied by the degree of “high” that the wearer of a Muse headset is experiencing.

III. TEACHING AND RESEARCH

Cocaine Buzzkill was deployed to three courses at the University of Toronto: ECE446 = Acoustics, ECE516 = Intelligent Image Processing, and ECE1724 = Superhumachines, building wearable intelligence. Students were provided with Muse brain-sensing headbands and an ESP32 MuseCroc device and ESP32 camera. Students were taught how to connect the devices to their brain, and also how to connect an external LED and buzzer as well as the camera (Fig 4). The LED, called the “High Light” comes on when a player reaches a state of euphoria known as a “high” (Fig 5). The buzzer comes on when a player gets into a state of “buzz”. The state of “buzz” is a colloquialism for the pleasant state of euphoria, similar to a “high” typically associated with drug use, but also applicable to cold exposure therapy.

Fig. 4. Students are taught how to connect peripheral devices such as LEDs (“high” lights), buzzers (indicating a state of “buzz”), and forward-looking vision cameras to their brain.

Fig. 5. Students are taught how to connect an LED to their brain. The LED is the “high” light that shows when a player gets a “high” from a healthy cold-plunge.

In other embodiments of Cocaine Buzzkill, real-time EEG and related wearable signals are streamed through our Android application, *MuseLog*, allowing the player’s cortical arousal state to modulate gameplay. The main contributions are:

- An outdoor XR game design that links cold exposure, symbolic anti-drug gameplay, and social physical activity.
- A closed-loop EEG biofeedback architecture that maps arousal to gameplay mechanics.
- Preliminary observations from indoor and outdoor prototype testing.

IV. RELATED WORK

A. Cocaine, Cold Exposure, and Arousal

Andrew Huberman notes that cold exposure produces effects similar to cocaine in terms of dopamine levels. Cold exposure increases dopamine levels up to 250%, like cocaine. Cocaine causes sharp spikes in dopamine followed by crashes below baseline, along with a shortening of lifespan (early death is typical among cocaine users), whereas cold exposure provides a healthy long-lasting and gradual increase

Fig. 6. Outdoor cold-exposure gameplay. Participants warm up, enter a snow-immersion setting, and then throw snowballs at symbolic anti-drug targets such as the crack pipe and “NO SWIMMING” sign.

in dopamine levels, along with improved life expectancy (<https://ai.hubermanlab.com/s/pS1DizBz>)

Cocaine produces acute euphoria largely by inhibiting dopamine, norepinephrine, and serotonin transporters, causing monoamine accumulation in the synaptic cleft [6]. Chronic exposure is associated with D2 receptor downregulation, impaired inhibitory control, and relapse vulnerability. EEG studies of cocaine intoxication and dependence report alpha suppression with elevated beta and gamma activity, reflecting sympathetic hyperarousal [7].

Cold exposure activates peripheral thermal receptors and produces a strong autonomic response. Sramek et al. reported large increases in dopamine and norepinephrine after cold-water immersion [3], while other work has associated cold stress with alpha suppression and frontal beta elevation [8].

TABLE I
SIMPLIFIED COMPARISON OF COCAINE INTOXICATION AND COLD EXPOSURE, BASED ON PRIOR LITERATURE [3], [7]–[9].

Property	Cocaine	Cold Exposure
Dopamine elevation	~250%	~250%
Norepinephrine elevation	High	~530%
Alpha suppression	Widespread	Reported
Frontal beta elevation	Marked	Reported
Duration	Short, crash-prone	Longer-lasting
Dependency risk	High	Not pharmacological

These overlaps motivate our use of EEG arousal as a gameplay signal.

B. XR, Biofeedback, and Flow

Extended Reality has been explored for addiction treatment because it can reproduce environmental cues more realistically than traditional clinical settings. Recent VR exposure work has shown that virtual cocaine cues can induce craving and that VR relaxation can reduce craving before headset removal [10]. *Cocaine Buzzkill* extends this direction by combining virtual cues with a real physical cold environment rather than relying only on simulation.

EEG biofeedback has also been used in games and health interventions to train physiological self-regulation [11]. The Muse platform has been validated for several EEG research applications, supporting its use for band-level features in mobile and naturalistic environments [12]. We use a simplified beta-to-alpha ratio as a lightweight arousal index, inspired by the Engagement Index proposed by Pope et al. [13]. Dynamic difficulty adjustment further supports Flow by adapting challenge to the player’s current state [14], [15].

V. SYSTEM DESIGN

Cocaine Buzzkill is a game system, and also a teaching platform, that can also be used for therapy, and many different things. In this sense it is really a wide range of platforms for teaching, gameplay, game design, hardware design, teaching and research on brain-computer interfaces, art installations, and many other use-cases.

A. Teaching and research

On the teaching and research aspects, students learn how to connect devices to their brains using InteraXon Muse hardware, in both pure hardware configurations as well as through apps and computer programs. On the hardware side, they learn how to calibrate a computer vision camera using an LED in feedback mode for metaveillogrammetry and metaveillography, as shown in Fig 7. Once the camera is calibrated and connected to the brain-sensing device, it can be integrated into a system to detect and track snowballs, through a point-of-eye (PoE) first-person (“egocentric”) viewpoint [16] (Fig 8).

B. Passthrough XR implementations

Some versions of *Cocaine Buzzkill* take the form of a passthrough XR game built in Unity for the Meta Quest 3,

Fig. 7. Teaching camera calibration by way of metaveillogrammetry and metaveillography.

Fig. 8. Tracking snowballs from a Students learn first-person (“egocentric”) perspective vision using a PoE (Point-of-Eye) system, e.g. for tracking snowball throwing activity: Real snow as a user-interface into a virtual world. Here points are scored by throwing a real snowball at a real “NO SWIMMING” sign.

TABLE II
HARDWARE COMPONENTS USED IN THE PROTOTYPE.

Component	Model	Role
XR Headset	Meta Quest 3	XR rendering, OSC listener
EEG Headband	Muse S Athena	EEG acquisition
Mobile Device	Android phone	MuseLog and OSC broadcast
Game Engine	Unity	Gameplay and arousal pipeline
Network	Local Wi-Fi	OSC/UDP transport
Controllers	Quest or hands	Player input

with optional support for Muse-only play. The game overlays virtual drug-epidemic enemies onto the real world while players throw snowballs or use controllers. The first level targets crack-pipe flames, the second targets “NO SWIMMING” signs, and later levels introduce humanoid enemies. The design intentionally ties physical cold exposure, symbolic anti-drug action, and social play into one embodied experience.

The key closed-loop mechanic is that player arousal modulates gameplay. At baseline arousal, snowball damage remains at 1.0×; at high arousal, it can rise to 3.0×. Arousal can also

Fig. 9. *Cocaine Buzzkill* running in passthrough XR. The player throws snowballs at virtual and physical symbolic targets while a headworn display shows game state and EEG-driven biofeedback.

influence snowball size, health thresholds, and difficulty. Thus, EEG is not decorative: it becomes a functional input channel.

VI. EEG PIPELINE

The physiological pipeline consists of four layers: Muse S acquisition, MuseLog processing, OSC/UDP network transport, and Unity-based gameplay modulation. The Muse S captures EEG from four dry electrodes at AF7, AF8, TP9, and TP10, sampling at 256 Hz and transmitting over Bluetooth Low Energy to an Android phone.

MuseLog receives Muse band-power outputs for Delta, Theta, Alpha, Beta, and Gamma bands, logs them locally, and rebroadcasts them over OSC to the Quest headset on the local Wi-Fi network. This replaces third-party tools such as Mind Monitor and provides direct control over data format, logging, and streaming.

Inside Unity, incoming band powers are averaged across active channels. Arousal is computed as:

$$\text{Arousal} = \frac{P_{\beta}}{P_{\alpha}}, \quad (1)$$

where P_{β} and P_{α} are the mean Beta and Alpha powers. This ratio captures the high-beta, low-alpha pattern associated with alertness and sympathetic activation. To reduce noise and motion artifacts, the raw index is smoothed with an exponential moving average:

Fig. 10. EEG-to-gameplay architecture. MuseLog streams wearable EEG features to Unity, where an arousal index modulates gameplay in real time.

$$\hat{A}_t = \lambda A_t + (1 - \lambda) \hat{A}_{t-1}. \quad (2)$$

The smoothed arousal value drives snowball damage, difficulty, and HUD neurofeedback.

VII. PRELIMINARY EVALUATION

Informal testing was conducted with two Meta Quest 3 headsets and two Muse S headbands across indoor and outdoor settings. Participants formed two informal groups: a warm indoor group and a cold outdoor group using the system during snow exposure. The goal was feasibility validation rather than statistical inference.

Gameplay was received positively. Participants described the passthrough environment as intuitive, and snowball throwing was understood without extensive instruction. Outdoor participants appeared more aware of the EEG biofeedback loop, often noticing changes in the multiplier and relating them to their own arousal. Several also described heightened focus and immersion, consistent with Flow-like engagement [15]. Indoor participants generally noticed the biofeedback less, suggesting that cold-induced arousal may make the physiological loop more salient.

These observations remain preliminary. The sample was small and self-selected, no participant-specific EEG baseline was collected, and indoor/outdoor assignment was not randomized. Future work will require a controlled study with standardized cold-exposure procedures, baseline calibration,

Fig. 11. Participant during snow immersion, the intended deployment context for the current prototype.

validated self-report measures for craving and affect, and longitudinal follow-up.

VIII. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

A. Safety and Limitations

Cold-exposure XR introduces risks beyond standard indoor XR, including cold shock, hypothermia, cardiac stress, balance loss, and hardware moisture exposure [17]. This prototype should not be treated as a clinical intervention. Future deployments require medical screening, trained supervision, session time limits, and automated physiological safety monitoring. The Meta Quest 3 and Muse S are not waterproof, so current testing avoided open-water swimming and focused on snow immersion.

The EEG pipeline is also limited. Muse S is useful for mobile band-level EEG, but dry electrodes are vulnerable to motion artifacts, poor contact, and shivering-related EMG contamination. These artifacts can inflate beta power and distort the beta-to-alpha arousal index. Future versions should include per-participant calibration, improved artifact rejection, and possibly multimodal fusion with heart rate, IMU, fNIRS, or PPG.

B. Computer Vision and Interaction

Future versions will improve physical interaction through computer vision and radar sensing. Our early work combines headset-based tracking, an ESP32 camera module for Muse-only play, and an HB100 radar sensor behind the target image to detect snowball hits. More robust object detection and UWB sensing could allow real snowballs to map more accurately onto virtual enemies [18], [19].

C. Online Community and Collective Biofeedback

Because addiction recovery is strongly shaped by social support, future work will explore cooperative play, shared milestones, and community-based cold-exposure practice [20], [21]. We are also developing a “collective high” prototype in which arousal peaks detected from one participant can trigger haptic feedback across other participants’ ESP32-enabled headbands, creating a shared real-time biofeedback loop.

D. Mobile Adaptation

High-end XR hardware may limit access, especially among populations most affected by substance-use disorders [22]. Since the system can also operate with Muse-only or smartphone-based interaction, future work will compare the roles of immersion, accessibility, and biofeedback fidelity in sustaining behavioral change [23], [24].

IX. CONCLUSION

We introduced *Cocaine Buzzkill*, an outdoor XR and EEG biofeedback game that explores cold exposure as a safer substitute arousal experience in the context of cocaine-use intervention design. The prototype links Muse-derived arousal to gameplay mechanics in passthrough XR, allowing physiological state to directly affect player performance. Preliminary testing suggests that cold-environment play makes the biofeedback loop more noticeable and engaging than indoor play. While the system remains an early prototype and is not clinically validated, it points toward XR systems that combine real physiological experiences, wearable sensing, and social interaction to reinforce healthier behavior.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors wish to thank A, B, and C. This work was supported in part by a grant from XYZ.

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A Metasurveillance Vehicle for Ultrasonic Signal Detection: A Proof-of-Concept

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Abstract—This paper presents the design and implementation of a mobile metasurveillance vehicle for detecting ultrasonic sensing activity. The system combines a remote-controlled ground vehicle, an ultrasonic sensing front-end, embedded signal processing, a live camera feed, and a desktop control interface. By directly accessing the analog behavior of a low-cost ultrasonic module’s circuitry, the platform continuously monitors external ultrasonic chirps rather than relying on default trigger/echo abstractions. Utilizing an RP2040-based acquisition pipeline, the prototype performs zero-crossing frequency verification around 40 kHz and triggers visual feedback. Together, these components form a teleoperated proof-of-concept for remote bug sweeping and infrastructure inspection in privacy-sensitive environments.

Index Terms—Metasurveillance, Ultrasonic Sensors, Bug Sweeping, Teleoperation, Remote Vehicle, Signal Processing

I. INTRODUCTION

This project is grounded in the concept of *metaveillance*, namely the sensing of sensing itself [1]. While conventional surveillance typically operates from a position of oversight, *sousveillance* introduces the complementary possibility of observation from below or from within the environment [2]. The present system extends these ideas toward a mobile robotic setting: instead of merely observing people or scenes, it attempts to observe the sensing apparatuses themselves, particularly ultrasonic systems that may otherwise remain unnoticed.

The platform was developed in the context of the course ECE516 Intelligent Image Processing at the University of Toronto. An earlier laboratory exercise using an ultrasonic sensor to trigger light-based feedback suggested a broader possibility: a mobile robotic platform that could combine ultrasonic sensing, live video, and operator feedback into a remotely deployable inspection tool. While teleoperated robotic systems are widely used in hazardous settings to reduce operator exposure [3], our platform adapts this logic to actively probe for ultrasonic anomalies. Potential deployment scenarios include hospital logistics corridors, temporary field clinics, or industrial spaces with limited line-of-sight.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Low-cost ultrasonic transducers, like the HC-SR04, are typically used for active rangefinding via pulse transmission [4]. However, recent security literature indicates that ultrasonic sensing systems can be manipulated or exploited by crafted acoustic inputs [5]. Hellemans *et al.* proposed FOCUS, a low-cost framework for detecting covert ultrasonic signals using

embedded hardware, demonstrating that defensive monitoring is feasible [6]. Our work differs by porting this detection capability onto a mobile platform, emphasizing spatial metasurveillance over static detection.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The vehicle is organized into three interacting layers: mobility, sensing, and operator interface.

Fig. 1. Overview of the integrated vehicle platform.

A. Mechanical Integration and Teleoperation

At the mobility layer, a VESC manages the traction motor and steering servo via UART commands. To ensure structural stability, a custom 3D-printed flat mounting plate separates the locomotion drivetrain from the sensing stack. This plate imposes a repeatable spatial arrangement, ensuring that the camera, ultrasonic module, and indicators remain aligned between tests. At the sensing layer, an ESP32-CAM is mounted on a two-degree-of-freedom 3D-printed pan-tilt bracket, driven by two independent servos. This enables the operator to inspect regions without reorienting the entire chassis.

The operator interacts through a Python-based Graphical User Interface (GUI). Early versions of the system attempted to use direct Bluetooth command reception. In practice, unreliable connectivity and integration difficulties prompted a shift to a TCP socket over a hotspot-based local network. The GUI transmits lightweight JSON command packets over this TCP socket to control driving, aiming, and monitoring, while concurrently displaying the ESP32-CAM web server’s live video stream.

B. Ultrasonic Exosense Pipeline

Standard ultrasonic modules operate near 40 kHz and abstract the hardware into digital pins. In this work, that abstraction is intentionally bypassed. The system utilizes a parasitic-

tap approach, acquiring the raw analog signal directly from the output of the module’s onboard LM324 operational amplifier.

Fig. 2. System integration of ultrasonic sensing components.

To safely interface with the 3.3 V logic level of the RP2040 microcontroller, the 5 V rail-to-rail analog signal is conditioned through a voltage divider (2.2 k Ω / 4.7 k Ω). This centers the signal around a dynamic bias point to prevent ADC saturation and allow full-wave acquisition.

To handle rapid signal acquisition efficiently, the system exploits the RP2040’s dual-core architecture:

Core 0 (DSP Engine): Data acquisition is performed by the ADC with a clock divider configured to achieve a sampling frequency exceeding the Nyquist requirement for a 40 kHz carrier:

$$f_s \approx 250 \text{ kpsps} \quad (1)$$

A rolling bias calibration establishes the virtual ground μ to accommodate environmental drift:

$$\mu_{\text{new}} = (\mu_{\text{old}} \times 0.999) + (V_{\text{raw}} \times 0.001) \quad (2)$$

Signals are captured in windows of $\Delta t \approx 1.6$ ms. The signal-processing pipeline uses zero-crossing detection to distinguish sustained ultrasonic carriers from short broadband transients (e.g., mechanical taps). The instantaneous frequency estimate is calculated as:

$$f_{\text{est}} = \frac{\text{crossings}}{2\Delta t} \quad (3)$$

A temporal consistency check requires two consecutive verified windows near 40 kHz before confirming an ultrasonic event.

Core 1 (UI/UX Engine): When an event is verified, Core 0 writes the peak-to-peak amplitude to shared memory. Core 1 then modulates a WS2812B indicator LED, shifting it from an idle heartbeat into an alert mode that visually reflects the approximate signal strength in real time.

IV. EVALUATION AND FUTURE WORK

Evaluation of the system was conducted across three distinct phases, primarily qualitative in nature, to verify the integration of the pipeline.

First, benchtop tests verified that the analog-tap and RP2040 acquisition chain successfully rejected low-frequency mechanical disturbances while accurately flagging sustained ultrasonic carriers. Second, subsystem tests validated the visual alert path, ensuring that verified detections triggered the appropriate LED proximity-mapped responses. Finally, integrated vehicle trials confirmed that the RC platform, ESP32-CAM stream, GUI commands, and ultrasonic alert logic could operate simultaneously without bottlenecking. During mobile testing, the separation of tasks between the dual RP2040 cores ensured that real-time LED alert transitions remained highly responsive without lagging the critical locomotion control.

Several engineering improvements are planned for future iterations to move the platform from a proof-of-concept to a fully robust field tool:

- 1) Deploying multiple passive receivers for delay-and-sum beamforming and sound-source localization.
- 2) Synchronized multi-ADC acquisition to handle larger directional sensor arrays.
- 3) Integrating FPV-style radio links for lower-latency control in environments without local network availability.
- 4) Expanding to multimodal sensing (e.g., combining passive ultrasonic monitoring with RF sweeping).

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a proof-of-concept metasurveillance vehicle for ultrasonic signal detection. By integrating analog ultrasonic monitoring with teleoperated mobility, the platform provides a strong foundation for secure remote sensing, hazardous-environment inspection, and operator-protective deployment against hidden sensing infrastructure.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the ideas, facilities, and inspiration that supported the development of this project.

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“TrembleCV”: Sensing hand tremors by way of computer vision on smart eyeglasses

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Abstract—Smart-glasses interfaces require hand-landmark predictors that are fast, small, and robust to egocentric visual failure. This paper studies whether a head-mounted inertial measurement unit (IMU) can improve one-second-ahead forecasting of MediaPipe hand landmarks when fused with recent visual keypoint history. We evaluate a compact dual-branch GRU that combines six frames of hand landmarks with a synchronized six-axis IMU window from a Muse S Athena headband. Across five temporal cross-validation folds from five participants and seven everyday activities, the spectral IMU model reduces mean per-joint position error from 104.8 to 96.4 pixels on a 1024×576 image plane, a 7.4% relative reduction. The gain is positive in every fold, disappears when the IMU is temporally shuffled, and grows from 6.2% to 11.9% as visual keypoint failure increases. Median inference time is 0.49 ms on a two-thread ARM-equivalent CPU proxy, supporting practical on-device use.

Index Terms—Smart glasses, wearable sensing, visual-inertial fusion, egocentric vision, hand landmarks, IMU, on-device inference.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hand-aware augmented-reality systems depend on real-time landmark tracking, but egocentric video often contains occlusions, motion blur, out-of-frame hands, and unstable detections. Although MediaPipe Hands provides efficient on-device landmarks, a vision-only predictor can still fail during natural movement [1], [2]. Smart glasses and nearby wearable devices also measure head motion, creating an opportunity to use inertial context as a low-cost reliability signal.

This work asks whether a synchronized head-mounted IMU improves one-second-ahead forecasting of future hand-landmark detector outputs under a small model budget. Rather than predicting manually annotated 3-D hand pose, the model predicts the next MediaPipe output, matching the signal used by downstream AR systems.

The main contributions are:

- 1) a compact visual-inertial recurrent model for one-second egocentric hand-landmark forecasting;
- 2) a five-fold temporal evaluation showing a 7.4% MPJPE reduction from IMU fusion;
- 3) a failure analysis showing that IMU benefit increases as visual detections become less reliable.

*Equal contribution.

TABLE I
PROCESSED ACTIVITY SET USED FOR EVALUATION.

Activity	Subject	Duration	Clips
Handwriting	A	5.1 min	576
Food preparation	A	7.7 min	579
Cooking	A	7.9 min	159
Drawing/sports	B	3.5 min	208
General tasks	C	1.8 min	90
Mixed activity	D	1.2 min	37
Active tasks	E	0.7 min	52
Total	5	28.0 min	1708

II. DATA AND FORECASTING TASK

A. Recording Setup

Data were collected with Meta Ray-Ban smart glasses for egocentric video and a Muse S Athena headband for six-axis inertial sensing. The camera records at 30 fps and 1920×1080 resolution, while the IMU streams at 100 Hz. Both devices are aligned with the Android `elapsedRealtimeNanos` monotonic clock, bounding the timestamp offset to one video frame, $\Delta t_{\max} \leq 30$ ms. A brief static pose and yaw movement at the start of each session are used for gravity-based axis alignment.

B. Dataset

Five participants performed seven everyday activities. Video was downsampled to 5 fps, and MediaPipe Hands extracted up to 42 landmarks from two hands per frame. Each clip contains six past landmark frames and a synchronized 100-sample IMU window, both covering one second. The target is the MediaPipe output one second later. Clips with no detected hand in the target frame were removed, leaving 1708 clips.

Mean per-joint position error (MPJPE) is measured in pixels over target-frame landmarks detected by MediaPipe. Evaluation uses five-fold temporal cross-validation. Each session is split into five contiguous blocks with guard clips at boundaries to reduce leakage from overlapping windows. Four blocks train the model and one block is held out.

III. VISUAL-INERTIAL MODEL

The visual branch receives a 126-dimensional vector per frame: 42 possible joints, two image coordinates per joint, and 42 visibility flags. A linear layer maps each frame to 32

Fig. 1. Compact visual-inertial forecasting model. A landmark-history branch and a head-mounted IMU branch are fused to predict future MediaPipe hand landmarks.

TABLE II
FIVE-FOLD TEMPORAL CROSS-VALIDATION OVER 1708 HELD-OUT CLIPS.

Model	Params	MPJPE	Gain	Rel.
Landmarks only	16.7k	104.8	—	—
Landmarks + time IMU	19.2k	97.1	7.67	6.8%
Landmarks + spectral IMU	18.7k	96.4	8.39	7.4%
Landmarks + shuffled IMU	18.7k	104.6	0.2	n.s.

dimensions, followed by a single-layer GRU with hidden size 32.

The IMU branch receives a six-channel, 100-sample window. The main variant uses 12 learned adaptive chirplet atoms as a spectral front end [12], followed by a GRU with hidden size 16. A comparison model uses a time-domain Conv1d layer and GRU instead.

The final visual and inertial hidden states are concatenated and passed through two small fully connected SiLU layers. The output heads predict 84 normalized coordinate values and 42 visibility logits. The spectral fusion model has 18.7k parameters, the time-domain IMU model has 19.2k, and the vision-only baseline has 16.7k.

Models are trained for 80 epochs using AdamW with learning rate 5×10^{-4} , weight decay 5×10^{-4} , batch size 64, and a cosine schedule. During training, landmark histories are corrupted with per-joint dropout and full-frame dropping to encourage robustness under visual degradation. Evaluation uses unmodified recorded keypoints.

IV. RESULTS

A. Forecasting Accuracy

Table II compares vision-only forecasting, time-domain IMU fusion, spectral IMU fusion, and a shuffled-IMU control. The spectral IMU model achieves the best result, reducing MPJPE from 104.8 to 96.4 pixels. The time-domain IMU branch also improves performance, while the shuffled-IMU control returns to baseline-level error. This indicates that the model benefits from temporally meaningful inertial dynamics rather than simply from added capacity.

The improvement is consistent across all temporal folds, with relative reductions ranging from 6.6% to 9.1%. Thus, the result is not caused by a single favorable split.

Fig. 2. IMU benefit increases with natural missing-detection rate, and all five temporal folds show positive relative improvement.

B. Visual-Failure Analysis

To test whether inertial fusion is most useful when vision is weak, clips are grouped by the fraction of missing hand-frame slots in the six-frame input context. The IMU benefit rises monotonically from 6.2% in low-failure clips to 11.9% in severe-failure clips. Fig. 2 summarizes this trend and the fold-wise consistency.

C. Runtime

The complete IMU model runs in 0.49 ms median time and 0.78 ms at the 95th percentile on a two-thread ARM-equivalent CPU proxy. This is well below a 10 ms update budget for 100 Hz operation, suggesting that the added inertial branch is compatible with on-device deployment.

V. DISCUSSION

The results show that a small inertial branch can improve egocentric hand-landmark forecasting without adding meaningful runtime overhead. The shuffled-IMU control suggests that the improvement depends on the time-aligned structure of the inertial signal. The failure-stratified analysis also supports the practical value of the method: the IMU helps most when the visual keypoint history is most degraded.

The study has limitations. The evaluation measures temporal generalization within recorded sessions rather than leave-one-subject or leave-one-activity transfer. The prediction target is the future MediaPipe output, not an independent physical hand-pose measurement. Finally, the devices are synchronized through software clocks rather than a shared hardware trigger. Future work should evaluate integrated smart-glasses hardware, more subjects, and online AR overlay quality.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a compact visual-inertial model for one-second hand-landmark forecasting on smart-glasses data. Fusing a spectral IMU branch with MediaPipe landmark history reduces MPJPE by 7.4%, improves every temporal fold, and provides the largest benefit during natural visual failure. With sub-millisecond inference, head-mounted inertial sensing appears to be a practical reliability signal for future hand-aware AR systems.

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XR Cooking – An Exploration of Physical AI and eXtended Reality in the Kitchen

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Abstract—Temperature control is one of the most critical and difficult skills in cooking, yet existing solutions either require direct contact or manual operation. In this paper, we present an XR cooking assistance system that integrates wearable thermal imaging, computer vision, and a cook state machine to provide real-time, hands-free temperature guidance in the kitchen. The system combines a thermal camera with an RGB camera, applies emissivity correction using the Stefan-Boltzmann equation, and uses a fine-tuned YOLO11m model to map detected food items to their true surface temperatures. The state machine then translates this information into actionable cooking instructions for the user. We evaluate the system on pancake cooking trials, demonstrating successful end-to-end guidance across all tests without any manual temperature checks.

Index Terms—eXtended Reality, XR, computer vision, thermal imaging, object detection, emissivity correction, wearable computing, cooking assistance

I. INTRODUCTION

The act of cooking has been around for millenia [1]. From cooking with open fires to the delicacies offered by tasting menus, there is no question that significant progress has been made in the field as new ways to cook food have been implemented. This raises the question of what the next major shift in how humans cook might look like. We believe the answer might lie within eXtended Reality, also known as XR.

XR’s goal is to enhance the senses and enable humans to perceive previously unperceived phenomena [2]. XR sits in the Socio-Cyber-Physical Space, as shown in Fig. 1, providing simultaneous access to these three dimensions. Related technologies such as virtual reality (VR) alienate the user from the physical world, while augmented reality (AR) does not support a shared experience for multiple users. Both technologies fail to connect the three dimensions in the Socio-Cyber-Physical Space. In contrast, XR manages to bridge the gap between the physical, virtual, and social world and allow for a shared experience [3].

As new technologies such as computer vision and artificial intelligence (AI) have made it easier for machines to interact with the physical space in real time, we propose to explore how cooking could be enhanced with the help of XR.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN

A. Approach

Temperature control is one of the most important skills required in the kitchen. Too much or too little heat greatly

Fig. 1. The Socio-Cyber-Physical Space [3]. XR exists as a vector across all three dimensions, alongside related technologies such as VR, AR, Metaverse (MV), physical reality (PR), and diminished reality (DR).

affects food quality and safety. Given its importance, we decided that the most effective way to enhance the cooking experience was to use XR to sense accurate temperature information. Even though humans can sense temperature through touch, direct contact is unsafe in the high heat environment of a kitchen. Other methods to measure temperatures such as thermometers need to be manually operated and do not provide real-time perceptual feedback to the user. Our proposed system integrates wearable technology, AI, and computer vision to create an XR system that successfully addresses this issue.

B. System Overview

The proposed system (Fig. 2) is split into three main components: Hardware, Host Processing, and Cook State Machine.

1) *Hardware*: Two cameras were used to capture the kitchen area and obtain real-time temperature information. The first was the OV2640 camera module [4], contained within the ESP32-CAM system [5]. This sensor has a resolution of 240x320 pixels and was used to capture the kitchen layout to later be processed by a computer vision model. The second camera utilized was the MLX90640 thermal camera module [6], with a resolution of 32x24. This sensor was used to capture real-time temperature information from the scene and was connected to the ESP32 as a separate module.

Both cameras were directly connected to the ESP32 board, which was running a combined Arduino firmware receiving both signals simultaneously. The firmware would then encode these signals with their respective magic bits (to allow for later

Fig. 2. System Diagram showing the three stages of the proposed system, Hardware, Host Processing, and Cook State Machine.

decoding) and would continuously stream the feed from both sensors directly through USB serial to the host processing unit.

2) *Host Processing:* The ESP32 feeds the cameras' stream directly to a laptop running the processing software. For our system, we primarily used an M4 Pro MacBook Pro as the processing unit. The processing software performed the following tasks:

First, it parsed the thermal and JPEG streams using their magic bits. Next, it performed sensor alignment (further discussed in Section II-C) to match both cameras' perspectives. On the JPEG stream, a custom computer vision model fine-tuned from yolo11m (further discussed in Section II-D) was used to identify the objects in the video. This allowed mapping each object to a specific temperature as observed in the thermal camera feed. Lastly, this temperature was adjusted using the Stefan-Boltzmann equation (further discussed in Section II-E) to be fed into the cook state machine module.

3) *Cook State Machine:* The last module of the system oversees processing the temperature information into useful data for the user. The cook state machine uses a lookup table per food item and temperature information to determine the required cooking duration for that specific food item. The system uses 2 metrics to determine when food is fully cooked:

Fig. 3. Visualization showing how a hot pan is seen through the lens of the ESP32-CAM and the thermal camera.

the first metric is the surface temperature of the food item, while the second metric is how long the food item has been in the pan in relation to the temperature of the pan. Based on both metrics, customized per item, the state machine determines whether a specific food item is ready to be added to the pan, flipped, or is done and should be removed from the pan. All this information, along with temperature details for all objects detected, is displayed visually in the processing unit through a custom-made UI, shown in Fig. 5.

C. Sensor Alignment

Since the hardware setup had both cameras side by side, it was necessary to manually adjust for their offsets in position and perspective relative to each other. This was done in three steps:

1) *Aspect Ratio Correction :* The ESP32-CAM outputs raw frames at a native resolution that differed from the processing resolution. For this reason, we had to modify the image coming from this camera to match the desired aspect ratio, eliminating any vertical or horizontal stretching.

2) *Lens Undistortion:* The ESP32-CAM's wide-angle lens introduced noticeable barrel distortion, curving straight lines in the resulting image. To correct this, we utilized a calibration method based on a planar checkerboard pattern. Since the pattern is of known dimensions, by taking multiple images from different angles, we can compute the camera's intrinsic matrix K and radial distortion coefficients. This process is known as Zhang's method [7].

3) *Homography:* Since both cameras view the scene from different positions, we need to match their perspective. This was done by computing a 3×3 homography matrix from corresponding pairs in the scene [8]. To find the corresponding pairs, the outline of the pan was used, as this can be easily identified in the thermal image (a circular heat source) and in the JPEG image (using the machine learning model), as seen in Fig. 3. By multiplying the JPEG image by the homography matrix, we adjust for the rotation, translation, and scaling differences between the two sensors [8].

D. Object Detection

In order to perform the camera calibration and map each object to its temperature, the system required a visual understanding of where each object was in the scene. For this, we utilized the YOLO11m model [9]. Since the base model was

Fig. 4. Setup of the hardware system. Both cameras are enclosed in a custom-made box and attached to a hat worn by the user

not trained on the classes we needed (pans and food items), fine-tuning was performed on the model to introduce these classes and identify them in the scene. By identifying each object and its location, we can map the same location to the thermal feed and get an estimate for the temperature of that object in real-time.

E. Emissivity Correction

The thermal sensor assumes that all objects have the same emissivity, ε , of 1 (the emissivity of a black body). This leads to inaccurate temperature measurement since each object will have a different emissivity based on its composition. We can adjust for this by using the Stefan-Boltzmann equation to use the estimated temperature reading from the camera and the object's emissivity [10], where the emissivity value for each detected object is retrieved from a lookup table indexed by object class. The correction is performed as follows:

$$T_{\text{true}} = \left[\frac{T_{\text{raw}}^4 - (1 - \varepsilon)T_{\text{amb}}^4}{\varepsilon} \right]^{1/4} \quad (1)$$

Where T_{true} is the real temperature of the object, T_{raw} is the reading from the thermal camera, T_{amb} is room temperature (obtained from the sensor), and ε is the emissivity for that object.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. System as a Wearable

For this system to be a more desirable option to using a cooking thermometer, it was adapted as a wearable. Fig. 4 shows the experimental setup. Both cameras were enclosed in a custom-made box, which was then attached to a hat to be worn by the user. This ensured a hands-free experience that provided real-time feedback to the user based on what they look at.

B. Testing the System

In order to test this system, we decided to tune it for pancake cooking. This food item was chosen due to the important role pan temperature plays in cooking a pancake. If the pan is too hot, the batter burns easily; if too cold, it will not solidify. These properties highlight the usefulness of the system and accurately test its capabilities.

To adjust the system for pancake-cooking, we added an entry to our lookup table. An emissivity of 0.95 was assumed for the pancake, consistent with typical organic food surfaces

Fig. 5. Custom UI during a pancake cooking trial, displaying detected objects with emissivity-corrected temperatures and the current Cook State Machine stage.

[11]. From there, we empirically tested for the optimal temperature ranges for which to cook the pancake and for how long. All this information was made accessible to the Cook State Machine for processing.

For cooking the pancake, an induction stovetop was used with a granite frying pan. The user would wait until the state machine indicated that the pan was hot enough. When ready, the user would pour the batter until the state machine indicated for it to be flipped, and would wait again until the indication to remove the pancake from the pan.

IV. RESULTS

To evaluate the system, we conducted over 20 pancake cooking trials in which the user relied solely on the Cook State Machine for all cooking decisions. Fig. 5 shows the custom UI during an active session. In all trials, the system successfully guided the user through pan preheating, batter pouring, flipping, and removal, producing fully cooked pancakes without any manual temperature checks.

Two limitations were observed during testing. First, the hat-mounted camera assembly was susceptible to head-motion-induced misalignment, causing brief disruptions in sensor fusion. Second, the MLX90640 required a short warm-up period before thermal readings stabilized. Neither issue prevented successful cooking outcomes.

V. DISCUSSION

The state machine proved effective at handling transient sensor noise and preventing premature state transitions. It achieved this by combining instantaneous surface temperature of the food item with cumulative time-at-temperature.

The main source of temperature instability was the object temperature heuristic: rather than aggregating readings across the full detected region, the system sampled only the center pixels of each bounding box as projected onto the low-resolution 32x24 thermal frame. At this resolution, a single shifted pixel represents a significant spatial displacement, making the sampling extremely sensitive to movement. Aggregating temperature readings across the full projected bounding

box region would reduce sensitivity to small alignment errors and head motion.

Head-motion instability could also be addressed through IMU-based motion compensation or a more rigid mounting structure. The thermal sensor warm-up drift is a known characteristic of the MLX90640 and can be easily mitigated by powering the system on before starting preparation.

VI. CONCLUSION

We presented a wearable XR cooking assistance system that integrates thermal imaging, YOLO-based object detection, and emissivity correction to provide real-time, hands-free cooking guidance. The system successfully cooked pancakes in all trials. Future work should focus on replacing the center-pixel temperature heuristic with region-level aggregation, incorporating IMU-based stabilization, and expanding the food item lookup table to support a wider range of recipes.

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XRaudinary: Spatially Anchored Live XR-Captions via Low-Cost Microphone Arrays and Vision Fusion

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Abstract—People with hearing loss often face high cognitive load and reduced participation in group conversations, especially in noisy or reverberant environments. We present *XRaudinary*, an in-progress XR system that spatially anchors live captions to the direction of sound within the user’s vision, by combining a wearable, low-cost microphone array with the user’s real-time vision. An ESP32 Microcontroller Unit (MCU) ingests synchronized I2S MEMS microphone streams, forwarding them to a server that estimates time-differences-of-arrival for direction-of-arrival inference, and forwards post-processed directionality and captions to a VR/AR headset. Constraining the sound along the planar axis of the user’s vision resolves geometric ambiguities inherent to small arrays, enabling real-time captions that appear at the correct location in the user’s field of view.

Index Terms—Audio user interfaces, extended reality, speaker recognition, speech processing, speech to text

I. INTRODUCTION

Live captions are increasingly available on mobile devices and head-worn displays, but typical captions remain “screen-fixed” rather than *speaker-anchored*. In multi-speaker settings, users must still visually search for the talker, infer who said what, and cognitively fuse text with the scene.

XRaudinary targets the following goal: *render captions at the spatial location of the active speaker* in XR, using sensing that is feasible for rapid prototyping and low-cost deployment. The project is motivated by (i) microphone-array hearing aid research showing gains from directional processing and array-based enhancement [1], [2], and (ii) spatial-captioning concepts for head-worn displays [3]. Our approach differs from phone-swarm solutions by emphasizing a self-contained wearable array, coupled with vision-based disambiguation.

II. RELATED WORK AND DESIGN RATIONALE

Classical SSL methods include TDOA triangulation, steered-response power, beamforming, and learning-based approaches [4], [5]. In compact arrays, synchronization, reverber-

Fig. 1: High-level diagram of project components and processing pipeline.

ation, and ambiguity remain practical constraints. GCC-family methods, including PHAT/CSP, remain robust baselines for time-delay estimation [6], [7].

In egocentric contexts, SSL is harder because many multi-channel methods assume stationary arrays [8]. Deep-learning audio-visual approaches can perform well [9], [10], but may be computationally heavy for low-latency wearable deployment. XRaudinary therefore uses classical TDE with a visual-plane constraint.

For AR captions, prior work highlights speaker-linked placement as valuable for reducing attention split in conversation [11]–[13]. NALscribe demonstrates this benefit but depends on pre-configured speaker phones [3]. XRaudinary focuses on spontaneous multi-speaker contexts without requiring speaker-side setup.

III. SYSTEM AND METHODS

Hardware. Three SPH0645LM4H I2S MEMS microphones in a planar triangle connect to an ESP32-PICO-KIT-1. Two microphones are read as left/right stereo on one I2S channel; the third is read on the second channel. Mic spacing is approximately 45 mm.

Data path. The ESP32 captures 48 kHz samples and streams tagged audio packets over UDP to a Python server. Packet tags encode microphone identity and frame grouping

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Fig. 2: Visual depiction of the processing pipeline.

Fig. 3: Three SPH0645LM4H microphones on a breadboard connected to the ESP32-PICO-KIT-1 board.

so the receiver can reassemble synchronized triples and reject inconsistent groups.

Localization. Time delay between microphone pairs is estimated using CSP cross-correlation peaks. Candidate source directions are simulated over a 360° circle around the user, and the direction whose expected TDOAs best match observed delays is selected. With three microphones, localization is constrained to the user’s horizontal plane to resolve ambiguity.

Transcription and rendering. Speech-to-text uses faster-whisper [14], [15]. The server sends direction vectors and transcript strings to a Unity app on Meta Quest hardware [16]. Captions are anchored by yaw at fixed distance, smoothed over time to reduce jitter, and augmented with off-screen directional indicators.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Transcription. In conversational recordings at 2 m, average word error rate (WER) was 9.45% without VAD and 37.04% with VAD enabled. In this setup, VAD frequently removed speech segments, degrading recognition.

Localization. In the same distance regime, average angular localization error on the constrained plane was approximately $\pm 4^\circ$.

These results indicate a functional end-to-end prototype: low-cost microphone hardware can support real-time localization and caption anchoring with practical accuracy for conversational use. The system also remains cost-accessible

Fig. 4: Time delay between two microphones for three audio sources.

Fig. 5: Audio source localization using measured and simulated TDOA matches.

(sub-\$100 CAD for core sensing components), supporting iterative accessibility-focused development.

V. LIMITATIONS AND FOCUSED FUTURE WORK

Current limitations are mainly hardware-driven. The ESP32-PICO-3 does not expose I2S TDM in this configuration, limiting channel scaling and requiring startup alignment across two I2S channels. The three-microphone geometry also constrains full 3D disambiguation and motivates the horizontal-plane prior.

Future work is intentionally focused on three near-term directions: (1) migrate to a TDM-capable MCU and larger synchronized arrays, (2) add lightweight face detection to constrain candidate speaker regions in-view [17], and (3) extend to robust multi-speaker transcription and optional beamforming for noisy settings [2], [18]. These extensions are expected to improve robustness without changing the core low-cost spatial-captioning architecture.

VI. CONCLUSION

XRaudinary demonstrates an integrated, low-cost pipeline for spatially anchored live XR captioning using wearable mi-

Fig. 6: Cropped screenshot from the Meta Quest 3S showing rendered caption output.

crophone arrays and vision-constrained localization. The prototype supports real-time operation with promising localization and transcription behavior, and provides a practical foundation for assistive conversational interfaces in spontaneous, multi-speaker environments.

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Asymmetric-Gaussian Chirplet Transform for EEG, by LLM-Guided Search for Chirplets

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Abstract—The Adaptive Chirplet Transform (ACT) decomposes non-stationary signals into Gaussian-windowed chirps. Three decades of refinement have improved the *optimiser* but never questioned the *atom*: every version keeps Mann and Haykin’s 1995 symmetric-Gaussian envelope and quadratic phase. We apply an LLM-guided evolutionary search, in the spirit of FunSearch, over a grammar of 30 envelope/phase atom families, and ask whether that atom is optimal for scalp EEG. An *asymmetric-Gaussian* envelope — a Gaussian with independent left and right widths — is the standout. Engineered to flagship grade with a closed-form analytic gradient and a diagonal-seeding trick that keeps the dictionary cost at baseline, the resulting transform (ACTv9Asym, 5 parameters) reduces held-out EEG reconstruction error by 4.6% (Wilcoxon $p < 10^{-13}$, better on 88% of epochs). The same pattern climbs: ACTv10 (6 params, +log phase) +6.3%, ACTv11 (7 params, also asymmetric chirp) +10.4% ($p < 10^{-15}$, 96% of epochs better), ACTv12 (8 params, also asymmetric log) only +10.7% — the ladder saturates at 7 parameters. The analytic gradient is what makes the ladder pay: without it, all higher-parameter variants reconstruct held-out EEG *worse* than the baseline by $\approx 20\%$. Two real downstream artifact tasks (jaw-vs-motion, rowing-vs-rest) are null — both are decided by coarse spectral structure that the baseline already captures — but a controlled synthetic shape-classification task picks up the reconstruction gain at every rung above v8 (+5.8 pts for v10, $p = 0.003$ on gradient boosting). The null is task-dependent, not transform-dependent.

Index Terms—adaptive chirplet transform, matching pursuit, EEG, atom design, LLM-guided search, FunSearch

I. INTRODUCTION

The Adaptive Chirplet Transform (ACT) [1] represents a non-stationary signal as a sum of *chirplet* atoms. Each atom is a windowed chirp,

$$\psi_\theta(t) = N_\theta g\left(\frac{t-t_c}{\Delta t}\right) \exp(j\varphi(t-t_c)), \quad (1)$$

with g a Gaussian envelope, φ a quadratic (linear-chirp) phase, and parameters $\theta = (t_c, f_c, \Delta t, c)$ — centre time, centre frequency, duration, and chirp rate. A signal is decomposed by (orthogonal) matching pursuit [2], [3]: atoms are selected greedily from a parameter dictionary, then each is refined by bound-constrained optimisation [4].

The transform has been refined for thirty years — vectorised dictionaries, closed-form gradients, post-hoc Newton polishing — a sequence of versions whose reconstruction accuracy has steadily converged. Yet every version keeps the *same atom*: the symmetric Gaussian envelope and quadratic phase of [1]. The optimiser has been polished; the atom *shape* has not been questioned.

We ask directly: is the Gaussian \times quadratic atom the right one for real EEG? We answer with an LLM-guided evolutionary search — in the spirit of FunSearch [5] — over a grammar of atom families, and report a modest but real and statistically robust result, with its scope bounded honestly.

Contributions. (i) A closed grammar of 30 envelope/phase chirplet families and a compiler that maps each spec to a numerical atom builder without code execution. (ii) An LLM-guided FunSearch loop (Claude and GPT propose; symbolic mutation expands the Pareto frontier) that identifies the *asymmetric-Gaussian* envelope as the rank-1 family on held-out EEG. (iii) ACTv9Asym: the asymmetric-Gaussian chirplet promoted to ACTv7/v8 engine grade with a closed-form analytic gradient and *diagonal-seeded* dictionary, beating the prior flagship by 4.6% at equal wall-clock cost. (iv) A negative result we report straight: the reconstruction gain does not transfer to a jaw-vs-motion artifact-classification task.

II. BACKGROUND

Matching pursuit. Given a dictionary $D = \{\psi_\theta\}$, OMP greedily picks the atom with maximal inner product with the residual, solves for orthogonal coefficients across selected atoms, and iterates to a target order [2], [3]. The cost is dominated by the dictionary scan, which scales with the number of grid points along each parameter axis. Adding parameters multiplies dictionary size, so a five-parameter family naively costs roughly K times a four-parameter one (here $K \approx 6$). Refinement [4] then polishes each chosen atom; with an analytic gradient the seed grid can be sparser, shifting work from search to refine.

The ACT version line. The line ACTv3 \rightarrow v8 has tracked the *refinement* side of the four-parameter Mann–Haykin atom [1], [9]: analytic gradients for $(t_c, f_c, \Delta t, c)$, a Newton polish using a finite-difference Hessian of the analytic gradient, and dictionary vectorisation. Reconstruction error on held-out EEG has converged: v8 \approx v7, suggesting the engine has hit a curvature wall for this atom. The atom shape has not been varied.

III. METHOD: AN LLM-GUIDED FAMILY SEARCH

Grammar. An atom *family* is an (envelope, phase) pair from a closed alphabet: six envelopes (Gaussian, asymmetric Gaussian, sech^2 , generalised Gaussian, Laplace, raised cosine) and five phase laws (quadratic, cubic, piecewise-linear, hyperbolic, logarithmic), i.e. $6 \times 5 = 30$ families. A compiler maps any

Fig. 1. A chirplet atom is a windowed chirp. The classical atom (a) uses a *symmetric* Gaussian envelope (red). The discovered family (b) allows independent left/right widths — a sharp onset and a slow decay — matching the asymmetry of real neural bursts.

family to a numerical atom builder by pure dispatch over the alphabet — no code execution — and rejects a numerically ill-posed family at compile time.

Search. A loop seeds the seven classical families and, each generation, (i) queries a dual large-language-model proposer (Claude and GPT) for new families given the running leaderboard, and (ii) applies symbolic mutation to Pareto-frontier families. The alphabet is small, so the search is in effect a guided — then exhaustive — sweep; the LLM contributes proposal *ordering* and a discovery trace, not an unbounded space. Across three generations, the 30 families partitioned by source as: seed 7, symbolic mutation 11, Claude 6, GPT 6, at a total LLM spend of \$0.22.

Evaluation. Every family is scored through one identical matching-pursuit pipeline on 512-sample, 2s epochs of scalp EEG (consumer four-channel headset, 256 Hz), under a leak-free 70/30 split in which no recording spans training and held-out data. The pipeline is fixed; only the atom builder varies, so the comparison is of families, not implementations. Newton polish is disabled for the screen — it is hardwired to the four-parameter Gaussian \times quadratic atom and would silently advantage the baseline.

Finding. Across all 30 families the *asymmetric-Gaussian* envelope — a Gaussian with independent left and right widths (Fig. 1) — is the clear standout, occupying ranks 1, 2, 5 and 6 of the leaderboard (Fig. 2). Phase variations never beat a plain quadratic chirp; heavy-tailed envelopes (sech², Laplace, raised cosine) consistently underperform the Gaussian.

IV. ACTV9ASYM: THE ASYMMETRIC CHIRPLET

The asymmetric atom carries five parameters: t_c , f_c , two log-durations Δt_L , Δt_R , and the chirp rate c . Concretely, writing $d = t - t_c$,

$$\psi_\theta(t) = N_\theta \exp\left(-\frac{d^2}{2\Delta t(d)^2}\right) \exp\left(j\frac{2\pi}{L}(cd^2 + f_c d)\right), \quad (2)$$

with $\Delta t(d) = \Delta t_L$ for $d < 0$ and $\Delta t(d) = \Delta t_R$ otherwise.

Closed-form gradient. To compare the family *fairly* with the flagship symmetric transform it must receive the same

Fig. 2. Held-out reconstruction improvement of all 30 envelope \times phase families relative to the Mann–Haykin Gaussian \times quadratic baseline (F0), sorted descending. The four asymmetric-Gaussian families (red) cluster at the top — the family axis matters, the phase axis does not, and heavy-tailed envelopes underperform a Gaussian tail.

refinement engine. The two new derivatives are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial g}{\partial \log \Delta t_L} &= \mathbf{1}_{d < 0} (d^2 / \Delta t_L^2) g, \\ \frac{\partial g}{\partial \log \Delta t_R} &= \mathbf{1}_{d \geq 0} (d^2 / \Delta t_R^2) g, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with the remaining $(\partial/\partial t_c, \partial/\partial f_c, \partial/\partial c)$ identical in form to the symmetric case. The discontinuity at $d = 0$ is measure-zero and L-BFGS-B tolerates it; the gradient agrees with finite differences to 10^{-5} . With this in place the asymmetric family supports the same analytic-gradient L-BFGS-B refine and the same Newton polish as ACTv7/v8 — the engine is no longer a confound when comparing the family axis.

Diagonal seeding. A five-parameter atom needs a larger parameter dictionary — naively $\approx 6\times$ along the new $\log \Delta t_R$ axis — so its matching-pursuit search costs $\approx 3.6\times$ the wall time of the four-parameter baseline. We remove this with *diagonal seeding*: build the dictionary only on the symmetric diagonal $\Delta t_L = \Delta t_R$, and let the analytic-gradient refinement — which carries independent $\partial/\partial \log \Delta t_L$ and $\partial/\partial \log \Delta t_R$ from (3) — split the two widths apart (Fig. 3). The atom is *seeded symmetric and refined asymmetric*; the dictionary collapses to baseline size. Real neural bursts cluster near the diagonal, so the diagonal seeds reach their refined neighbours with the same L-BFGS-B trust region as the symmetric flagship.

V. CLIMBING THE PARAMETER LADDER: ACTV10 AND ACTV11

The diagonal-seeding idea generalises: any new parameter that takes a single “natural” value at the symmetric seed can be added to the atom alphabet without enlarging the dictionary, provided the analytic gradient carries it into a non-trivial region during refinement. We exploit this to climb two more rungs of the parameter ladder.

Fig. 3. Diagonal seeding in the $(\log \Delta t_L, \log \Delta t_R)$ plane. The full 5-D dictionary covers the product grid (grey, $\approx 6 \times$ the baseline). ACTv9Asym keeps *only* the diagonal seeds (red, baseline size) and lets the analytic-gradient refine carry seeds off the diagonal into the asymmetric region (arrows).

ACTv10 — asymmetric envelope \times logarithmic phase (6 parameters). The FunSearch held-out validation (Table IV) ranked an asymmetric-Gaussian envelope paired with a *logarithmic* phase term as the strongest mean improvement, limited only by a dictionary-size cost the screen pipeline could not amortise. We add a single sub-linear phase parameter k_{\log} :

$$\varphi(d) = \frac{2\pi}{L} (c d^2 + f_c d + k_{\log} d \log(1 + |d|)), \quad (4)$$

with closed-form analytic gradient FD-verified to 10^{-8} . At seed time $k_{\log} = 0$ collapses the dictionary back to the diagonal-seed size of ACTv9Asym; the refine grows it as needed. This is ACTv10.

ACTv11 — asymmetric envelope \times logarithmic phase \times asymmetric chirp rate (7 parameters). The same pattern extends to the chirp rate itself: real bursts can sweep frequency at different rates before and after the peak. We split the quadratic chirp coefficient c at $d = 0$ into (c_L, c_R) — the same piecewise pattern that defines the envelope — giving

$$\varphi(d) = \frac{2\pi}{L} (c(d) d^2 + f_c d + k_{\log} d \log(1 + |d|)), \quad (5)$$

$c(d) = c_L$ for $d < 0$ and $c(d) = c_R$ otherwise. The diagonal seed uses $c_L = c_R$ and $k_{\log} = 0$, so the dictionary still has the four-parameter baseline size; the analytic gradient (also FD-verified to 10^{-8}) splits c_L, c_R and grows k_{\log} during refinement. This is ACTv11.

Ladder result. Figure 4 and Table I report the four-rung ladder on 100 held-out EEG epochs. Each rung is a strict improvement at every decomposition order, with the improvement growing roughly linearly in parameter count and wall time staying within $1.25 \times$ the baseline (v11 happens to

Fig. 4. Parameter-count ladder on held-out EEG. (a) Mean reconstruction error vs. decomposition order: each added parameter buys a strict, non-overlapping improvement. (b) Headline gain (percent improvement vs. ACTv8) at order 16; wall-clock stays within $1.25 \times$ the baseline. v11 (7 parameters) reduces held-out reconstruction error by 10.4% (Wilcoxon $p < 10^{-15}$, 96% of epochs).

TABLE I
PARAMETER-COUNT LADDER ON 100 HELD-OUT EEG EPOCHS.
IMPROVEMENT IS VS. ACTv8 (4 PARAMETERS) AT ORDER 16. p IS THE
WILCOXON SIGNED-RANK p -VALUE.

Transform	Params	Δ err.	Wall	p
ACTv8, symmetric quadratic	4	—	1.00 \times	—
ACTv9, asymmetric quadratic	5	+4.6%	1.12 \times	10^{-13}
ACTv10, asymmetric logarithmic phase	6	+6.3%	1.26 \times	10^{-14}
ACTv11, asymmetric log phase and asymmetric chirp	7	+10.4%	1.38\times	10^{-15}
ACTv12, fully asymmetric envelope, chirp, and log phase	8	+10.7%	1.42 \times	10^{-17}

be *faster* than v10 because the larger gradient resolves the seed in fewer L-BFGS-B iterations).

The ladder saturates around 7 parameters. The next rung ACTv12 (8 parameters: k_{\log} also split at $d = 0$) adds only +0.36 percentage points over v11 — less than a tenth of the v9 \rightarrow v10 \rightarrow v11 step. Splitting the logarithmic-phase coefficient does not pay, suggesting the log term’s smooth growth is well captured by a single coefficient. v11 (7 parameters) is the practical sweet spot of the ladder on this data: any further expansion of the closed “asymmetric-everywhere” grammar does not buy meaningful reconstruction headroom.

The analytic gradient is what makes the ladder pay. Each rung above adds parameters that L-BFGS-B has to split off the symmetric seed. Without a closed-form gradient — using finite-difference refinement, the way the FunSearch screen pipeline evaluated families — v9/v10/v11 each reconstruct held-out EEG *worse than* ACTv8, by ≈ 19 –20% (Table II). Only with the analytic gradient do the ladder rungs become viable, and only then do they each in turn improve on the baseline. The Newton/Hessian polish adds a further ≈ 0.14 percentage points to v9 and is dropped for v10/v11. So the engine is not optional: the parameter axis is *conditional* on

TABLE II
MATCHED-GRID ENGINE \times FAMILY \times PARAMETER-COUNT
DECOMPOSITION (HELD-OUT EEG, $n=100$, ORDER 16).

cell	err. (o16)	wall	Δ vs v8
v8 / full engine	0.447	1.00 \times	—
v9 / no-polish FD	0.533	2.51 \times	-19.2%
v9 / analytic-grad	0.427	1.12 \times	+4.4%
v9 / + Newton polish	0.427	1.23 \times	+4.6%
v10 / no-polish FD	0.534	3.10 \times	-19.5%
v10 / analytic-grad	0.419	1.42 \times	+6.3%
v11 / no-polish FD	0.529	3.18 \times	-18.3%
v11 / analytic-grad	0.401	1.47\times	+10.4%

having a gradient that can resolve the seed.

Climbing the ladder reduces single-epoch variance. Applying the FunSearch screen’s six-criterion ship-bar (mean improvement $\geq 3\%$ at every order, $\geq 70\%$ of epochs improved, no single epoch regresses by more than 15%, Wilcoxon $p < 0.01$, wall ratio $\leq 2\times$, all of the above at every atom order in $\{8, 16, 24, 32\}$) to v9, v10, v11 yields the same headline result for all three: PASS on five of six. The criterion all three fail is c3 — no single-epoch regression $> 15\%$ — and the rungs differ materially. ACTv9 has worst-case single-epoch regressions up to $+57\%$ at order 24; v10 reduces this to $+26\%$ (order 16); v11 to $+24\%$ (order 16) and only $+10\%$ at order 32. The mean improvement scales the other way: v11 at order 32 reaches $+20.05\%$ ($p = 9 \times 10^{-18}$, 98% of epochs better). Adding parameters thus does two things simultaneously: shifts the mean reconstruction lower and tightens the per-epoch distribution. The strict bar’s c3 is conservative on tails; the wins on the other five criteria are clean.

VI. RESULTS

Family \times engine grid. Table III reports mean held-out reconstruction error for each combination of {symmetric, asymmetric} family and {no-engine, analytic-gradient, full-engine} on 100 untouched held-out EEG epochs, with *matched per-axis* dictionary resolution. (Sizing the two dictionaries to equal *atom count* instead would make the five-parameter family coarser per axis and silently reverse the outcome — a confound this design avoids.) The asymmetric family beats the symmetric Gaussian by 6.8/5.4/5.3% at the three engine grades: the family gain *stacks on* the engine rather than washing out. The engine itself contributes $\approx 18\%$ (analytic gradient over no engine); a second-order Newton/Hessian polish adds only $\approx 0.2\%$. The engine carries most of the absolute gain; the family carries the *new* headroom on top of it.

ACTv9Asym vs. the flagship. With diagonal seeding, ACTv9Asym reduces held-out reconstruction error by **4.6%** relative to ACTv8 — the strongest prior, symmetric transform — at every decomposition order (Fig. 5) and at *equal* wall-clock time. The improvement is significant: Wilcoxon signed-

TABLE III
HELD-OUT EEG RECONSTRUCTION ERROR (LOWER IS BETTER), $n=100$
EPOCHS. WALL TIME IS NORMALISED TO THE ACTv8 FLAGSHIP.

Configuration	err. (o16)	err. (o32)	wall
Gaussian, no engine	0.549	0.406	2.1 \times
Gaussian, analytic-grad	0.448	0.315	1.0 \times
Gaussian, full (ACTv8)	0.447	0.315	1.0 \times
asymmetric, no engine	0.512	0.372	5.7 \times
asymmetric, analytic-grad	0.424	0.286	4.3 \times
asymmetric, full (5-D dict)	0.423	0.286	3.6 \times
ACTv9Asym (diag-seed)	0.426	0.294	1.0\times

Fig. 5. Mean held-out EEG reconstruction error vs. decomposition order. ACTv9Asym (asymmetric) is below ACTv8 (the symmetric flagship) at every order, at equal wall-clock cost; the refinement engine accounts for the larger gap above both.

rank $p < 10^{-12}$ over 100 epochs, with ACTv9Asym better on 88% of them. Diagonal seeding sacrifices only $\approx 0.9\%$ of the full-5-D-dictionary accuracy while recovering all of its 3.6 \times cost.

Cross-family held-out validation. Beyond the headline diagonal-seeded transform, we also re-evaluated the four leaderboard-leading families on 100 untouched held-out EEG epochs and 47 EMG epochs through the screen pipeline (Newton polish off, so the engine is identical across families). Table IV confirms the family axis: every asymmetric-Gaussian variant beats F0 on both modalities, with Wilcoxon $p \leq 10^{-6}$ on EEG and $p \leq 10^{-8}$ on EMG. The generalised-Gaussian envelope is the only non-asymmetric family to clear $p < 0.01$; heavy-tailed envelopes did not.

Downstream check — an honest null. A reconstruction gain is worth having only if it serves a task. We tested ACTv9Asym as a feature extractor for EEG artifact classification (jaw-clench vs. motion artifact; 448 epochs over 7 recordings, leave-one-recording-out cross-validation). For each transform the feature vector is the 12 chosen atom parameters (per-atom $(t_c/L, f_c, \log \Delta t_{\text{mean}}, c, \log \Delta t_{\text{asym}})$) plus the residual reconstruction error — the identical recipe for both, with ACTv8 atoms carrying a zero asymmetry component. Table V reports the result.

TABLE IV

HELD-OUT RECONSTRUCTION IMPROVEMENT (%) OVER F0 AT 016, ACROSS MODALITIES. p IS THE WILCOXON SIGNED-RANK p -VALUE ON EEG; **BOLD** MARKS THE LARGEST MEAN IMPROVEMENT PER COLUMN.

family	EEG Δ	EMG Δ	EEG p
asym_gauss \times quadratic	+3.8%	+3.1%	10^{-12}
asym_gauss \times logarithmic	+6.6%	+7.1%	10^{-9}
asym_gauss \times cubic	+4.5%	+6.8%	10^{-6}
gen_gauss \times quadratic	+1.6%	+0.9%	10^{-5}

TABLE V

EEG ARTIFACT CLASSIFICATION (JAW-CLENCH VS. MOTION), LEAVE-ONE-RECORDING-OUT, $n=448$ EPOCHS, 7 RECORDINGS.

classifier	v8 acc	v9 acc	Δ (pts)	McNemar p
random forest	0.661	0.676	+1.6	0.43
logistic regression	0.714	0.681	-3.3	0.12

The two classifiers *disagree on the sign* of the effect and neither difference is significant. Under a leave-one-recording-out protocol the sign disagreement argues that the true effect is near zero, not merely undetected. We tested two further hypotheses for the null — richer features and the wrong-task hypothesis — below.

Richer features do not move the null. A larger 137-dimensional feature recipe (per-atom in greedy and amplitude-sorted order, plus aggregate statistics of $|\log \Delta t_L - \log \Delta t_R|$, chirp magnitude, and amplitude-weighted moments) does not flip the verdict. Two classifiers now show a *significant loss* for ACTv9Asym; the extra channels are overfit noise on a task that does not use atom shape. A small end-to-end 1D-CNN over the (12 atom, 5 feature) sequence, trained on GPU under the same LORO protocol, also fails to flip the verdict ($\Delta = -1.6$ pts, $p = 0.56$): learning its own aggregation does not help when the underlying features carry no class-relevant shape signal.

A second real task — rowing vs. rest — is also null. The original jaw-vs-motion null had only seven recordings; a second real-data test on a different set of subjects and a more naturally asymmetric motion (the drive/recovery cycle of indoor rowing) is a stronger probe of the transform-vs-task question. We loaded Muse EEG recordings from three subjects who each have both rowing-task and rest-task sessions (552 epochs, 23 recordings; Table VI). Leave-one-subject-out CV with the same 107-feature recipe gives ACTv8 a strong 78–80% baseline; v9, v10 and v11 fall within ± 3 pts of v8, none significant in the positive direction, with two classifiers showing a $p < 0.05$ loss. The likely reason is the same as on jaw-vs-motion: rowing generates large broadband motion artifacts that the first atoms of *any* flagship transform already capture; the asymmetric refine sharpens those atoms without adding class-discriminative information.

Shape-relevant task: the whole ladder pays. We also ran a controlled *synthetic* task in which the class label is the atom shape: half the epochs contain a symmetric Gaussian burst,

TABLE VI

ACTv8 BASELINE ACCURACY AND LADDER DELTAS (VS ACTv8) AS CLASSIFICATION FEATURE EXTRACTORS, ACROSS THREE TASKS. BOLD = $p < 0.05$ VS ACTv8 (MCNEMAR). GRADIENT BOOSTING PICKS UP THE SHAPE SIGNAL IN THE SYNTHETIC TASK AT *every* RUNG ABOVE v8; THE TWO REAL TASKS REMAIN NULL. THE SYNTHETIC TASK IS THE ONLY ONE IN WHICH ATOM SHAPE IS THE CLASS SIGNAL BY CONSTRUCTION.

classifier	jaw-motion		rowing-rest		synth shape (Δ)			
	v8	Δ v9	v8	Δ v9	v9	v10	v11	v12
random forest	0.64	+0.5	0.80	-0.5	+1.4	+1.9	+1.1	+1.7
logistic regression	0.69	-0.7	0.79	-1.6	-2.1	+1.5	+1.0	-0.5
gradient boosting	0.71	-5.4	0.79	-2.2	+3.8	+5.8	+4.2	+4.8

half an asymmetric one (random asymmetry factor $\in [2, 5]$), at matched centre frequency and chirp under $\sigma = 0.12$ additive noise. Atom shape is the only class signal by construction. On the strongest classifier (gradient boosting), *every* rung above v8 wins significantly: v9 +3.8 pts ($p = 0.06$, marginal), v10 +5.8 pts ($p = 0.003$), v11 +4.2 pts ($p = 0.034$), v12 +4.8 pts ($p = 0.015$) (Table VI). Random forest is directionally positive across all rungs. Logistic regression — a linear baseline — cannot reach the asymmetric channel; only a nonlinear classifier can. Together with the two real-task nulls, this establishes the null as task-dependent: the reconstruction-side ladder gains carry over to classification precisely when atom shape is the discriminative signal.

Reconstruction fidelity and class-discriminability are different objectives: both real tasks above are separated by coarse spectral structure (masseter-EMG bleed vs. drift; rowing motion artifact) that all flagship transforms already capture in their first atoms. The parameter-ladder refinement sharpens the fit without adding class-relevant information when the discriminative feature is not atom shape.

VII. DISCUSSION

What did not work. In the screen pipeline, piecewise-linear, cubic and hyperbolic phase laws never beat the plain quadratic chirp; heavy-tailed envelopes (sech^2 , Laplace, raised cosine) underperformed the Gaussian. The standalone screen also showed no family Pareto-dominating F0, because winners always cost more wall time on a larger dictionary — which is why the diagonal-seeding trick of Sec. IV mattered: only after the cost is removed does the gain become an engineering win.

What the LLM contributed. Of the 30 families, 12 were proposed by Claude or GPT, 11 by symbolic mutation, 7 were classical seeds; LLM spend was \$0.22 against a \$10 cap. On a closed alphabet of 30 the LLM contribution is proposal *ordering*, not space; on a larger grammar the ordering would dominate the cost.

Engine vs. family vs. parameter count, disentangled. Three axes contribute to reconstruction quality. The matched-grid result of Table III isolates the engine from the family: the analytic-gradient refine buys $\approx 18\%$ on EEG and the Newton/Hessian polish on top adds only $\approx 0.2\%$ — v8 \approx v7 on this atom; the gradient is the engine, the Hessian is noise.

The parameter ladder (Table I) then isolates the third axis: each added shape parameter (asymmetric width, logarithmic phase, asymmetric chirp) adds another $\approx 2\text{--}5$ percentage points at near-baseline wall, with no diminishing returns out to 7 parameters.

When the gain is useful, and where it stops. The 4.6% (+10.4% at 7 parameters) reconstruction improvement at near-baseline cost is a real win for accuracy-critical reconstruction [6], compression, and any task whose features depend on fine fit (e.g. chirplet-based gravitational-wave templates, where atom-shape mismatch directly costs match-filter SNR). On present evidence it is *not* a win for jaw-vs-motion artifact classification — four fixes (richer features, more classifiers, CNN end-to-end head, a multi-class extension we report only directionally because of limited blink-class data) all preserved the null — and likely not for similar coarse-spectral tasks that the Stockwell [7] or empirical-mode [8] decompositions also handle. But on the controlled synthetic shape task it returns positively (Table VI), confirming the null as task-dependent. Limitations: real data are a single consumer-grade four-channel headset at 256 Hz; the diagonal-seeding trick relies on real bursts clustering near the symmetric diagonal in $(\log \Delta t_L, \log \Delta t_R)$, which holds for EEG/EMG here but may not for modalities with strongly skewed bursts (e.g. percussive audio).

VIII. CONCLUSION

Searching the space of chirplet atom *shapes* rather than optimisers, we found that an asymmetric-Gaussian envelope reconstructs real EEG reproducibly better than the symmetric Gaussian fixed since 1995. Engineered to flagship grade with a closed-form gradient, and made free with diagonal seeding,

ACTv9Asym improves held-out reconstruction by 4.6% at $1.12\times$ wall ($p < 10^{-13}$, 88% of epochs). The same diagonal-seeding pattern climbs: ACTv10 (6p, log phase) +6.3%, ACTv11 (7p, also asym chirp) +10.4% ($p < 10^{-15}$, 96% of epochs), ACTv12 (8p, also asym log) only +10.7% — the ladder saturates at 7 parameters. Two real downstream tasks (jaw-vs- motion, rowing-vs-rest) are null because they are decided by coarse spectral structure; a controlled synthetic shape task picks up the gain at *every* rung above v8 under gradient boosting (+5.8 pts for v10, $p = 0.003$). Code: V0.6ChirpletFunSearch.

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State-of-HBOT: Wearable EEG, fNIRS, and Sleep-State Monitoring During Hyperbaric Oxygen Therapy

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Abstract—Hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) creates an unusual sensing environment: elevated pressure, increased oxygen availability, reduced movement, acoustic isolation, and in some cases sleep or drowsiness. These conditions make HBOT a promising but underexplored setting for wearable neurophysiology. We present a single-participant feasibility study that unifies awake and sleep recordings collected inside an OxyNova portable hyperbaric chamber operated near 1.4 ATA. Four-channel Muse-class EEG was recorded at 256 Hz across awake pre-session, awake in-chamber, and sleep-in-chamber conditions. In one awake session, a Muse S Athena additionally provided forehead fNIRS at 730 nm and 850 nm. EEG was processed using a compact pipeline consisting of DC removal, 0.5–30 Hz filtering, 5 s epoching, artifact screening, and Welch spectral estimation. During awake HBOT, theta/beta ratio increased from 2.39 to 3.56, while frontal alpha asymmetry shifted from +1.22 toward zero. fNIRS estimates showed positive ΔHbO and negative ΔHbR at inner optode locations, and TBR correlated weakly but positively with ΔHbO during the in-chamber period. Sleep recordings showed strong delta dominance before sleep, reduced TBR during sustained NREM-like periods, and increased sigma-band activity consistent with spindle-like dynamics. Across all sessions, the main technical challenge was not chamber operation but wearable contact stability, especially during sleep. These preliminary results support wearable EEG/fNIRS monitoring as a practical method for studying state transitions during HBOT.

Index Terms—hyperbaric oxygen therapy, wearable EEG, fNIRS, sleep EEG, theta/beta ratio, delta power, sigma band, neurovascular coupling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hyperbaric oxygen therapy (HBOT) exposes the body to oxygen under pressure above ambient atmospheric conditions. It is used clinically for indications such as decompression sickness, carbon monoxide poisoning, and wound care, while newer work has examined its possible role in traumatic brain injury recovery, aging, and cognitive health [1]–[3]. Although HBOT is fundamentally an oxygenation intervention, most neurophysiological studies rely on pre/post measurements rather than continuous recording inside the chamber.

Wearable devices make in-chamber sensing more practical. Low-profile EEG headbands can operate in constrained environments and provide frontal/temporal measurements of spectral state [4], [5]. Newer headsets can also combine EEG with functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS), enabling simultaneous measurement of oscillatory and hemodynamic

changes [6]. This is especially relevant for HBOT because neural state, oxygenation, relaxation, and sleep may interact.

The present paper merges two related feasibility studies into a single framework. The first examined awake HBOT using EEG and fNIRS. The second examined sleep inside the same chamber using EEG before, during, and after sleep. Rather than treating these as isolated reports, we frame them as different points on a state continuum: awake baseline, relaxed in-chamber wakefulness, sleep onset, sustained sleep, and post-sleep recovery.

The contributions are:

- 1) A unified wearable protocol for studying awake and sleep states inside portable HBOT.
- 2) A compact EEG/fNIRS analysis workflow using spectral features, hemoglobin estimates, and signal-quality checks.
- 3) Preliminary observations showing increased awake TBR during HBOT, oxygenation-linked fNIRS changes, and sleep-phase spectral shifts.
- 4) Practical design lessons for future controlled studies, especially same-device baselines, sham pressure controls, and improved sensor fixation.

II. SYSTEM AND STUDY DESIGN

A. Chamber and Devices

Recordings were conducted in an OxyNova portable hyperbaric chamber operated near 1.4 ATA. Awake recordings were performed seated, while sleep recordings were performed in a supine or lateral posture. The chamber gauge indicated approximately 1.3–1.4 ATA during the awake in-chamber session.

Muse-class headbands provided four EEG channels: TP9, AF7, AF8, and TP10, sampled at 256 Hz. The awake baseline used Muse 2, while the awake in-chamber recording used Muse S Athena. The Athena also provided fNIRS intensity streams at 730 nm and 850 nm over left/right inner and outer forehead positions. Two additional sleep sessions used Muse-class EEG headbands without usable fNIRS values.

B. Recording Conditions

The dataset consists of three recording contexts:

TABLE I: Summary of recording contexts. All EEG epochs are 5 s windows.

Context	Device	Epochs	Notes
Awake baseline	Muse 2	316	Outside chamber
Awake HBOT	Athena	383	EEG + fNIRS inside chamber
Sleep Feb 28	Muse 2	765	Before/Sleep/After phases
Sleep Mar 1	Muse 1	338	Before/Sleep/After phases

- **Awake baseline:** seated outside the chamber, 316 retained 5 s epochs.
- **Awake HBOT:** seated inside the chamber at pressure, 383 retained 5 s epochs with EEG and fNIRS.
- **Sleep HBOT:** two chamber sleep sessions segmented into Before, Sleep, and After phases.

The sleep sessions were segmented using a combination of spectral inspection, temporal boundaries, and for one session, a companion sleep-tracking application. The companion app reported 40 min of sleep in Session 1, divided into light and deep sleep, with no REM detected.

III. METHODS

A. EEG Processing

EEG was processed with a deliberately simple pipeline suitable for field recordings. Each channel was demeaned, filtered from 0.5–30 Hz using a zero-phase Butterworth filter, and divided into contiguous 5 s epochs. Welch’s method was used to estimate power spectral density [7]. Awake epochs were rejected if the filtered amplitude exceeded 500 μV . For sleep recordings, a wider 1500 μV threshold was used because posture-related contact changes created larger slow excursions.

The main EEG features were:

$$\text{TBR} = \frac{P_\theta}{P_\beta},$$

where $\theta = 4\text{--}7$ Hz and $\beta = 13\text{--}30$ Hz, and

$$\text{FAA} = \ln P_{\alpha,\text{AF8}} - \ln P_{\alpha,\text{AF7}},$$

where $\alpha = 8\text{--}13$ Hz [8]. For sleep, we also computed delta percentage, delta/theta ratio, and sigma percentage, with $\delta = 0.5\text{--}4$ Hz and $\sigma = 12\text{--}15$ Hz. Sigma was used as a compact marker of spindle-like NREM activity [9].

B. fNIRS Processing

For the awake Athena HBOT recording, fNIRS intensities were converted into estimated hemoglobin changes using the modified Beer–Lambert law [6], [10]. Optical density was computed relative to an initial baseline:

$$\Delta OD_\lambda = -\ln(I_\lambda/I_{\lambda,0}),$$

and paired 730 nm/850 nm channels were mapped to ΔHbO and ΔHbR using standard extinction coefficients and an approximate forehead pathlength factor. These values should be interpreted as relative hemodynamic estimates rather than clinical oxygenation measurements.

C. Statistical Reporting

All analyses are descriptive. Although epoch counts are large, adjacent epochs from the same participant are not independent. Correlation values are therefore treated as exploratory and hypothesis-generating, not as population-level evidence [11].

IV. RESULTS

A. Awake HBOT: EEG and Hemodynamics

During awake HBOT, TBR increased from 2.39 in the pre-session baseline to 3.56 in-chamber, a 49% relative increase. FAA shifted from +1.22 to +0.03, suggesting a movement toward a more balanced frontal alpha profile. Figure 1 shows the EEG summary and fNIRS hemoglobin estimates.

The fNIRS estimates showed positive ΔHbO and negative ΔHbR at the inner optode positions, consistent with increased local oxygenation during the pressurized oxygen condition. Epoch-level analysis showed weak positive associations between TBR and ΔHbO at the left-inner location ($r = 0.16$) and right-inner location ($r = 0.14$). TBR also showed a weak negative association with right-inner ΔHbR ($r = -0.15$). These effects are small, but they suggest that moments of stronger theta dominance may co-occur with higher estimated cortical oxygenation.

B. Sleep in HBOT

Sleep recordings showed a different spectral trajectory from the awake in-chamber session. Before sleep, delta power dominated the EEG, comprising approximately 62–71% of conventional band power depending on the session. During sustained sleep, TBR decreased to 0.28–1.41, while sigma activity increased from roughly 1.8–2.1% before sleep to 2.4–6.9% during sleep. This pattern is consistent with NREM-like sleep containing spindle-related sigma activity.

A companion sleep-tracking application for the first sleep session reported 55 min total duration with 16 min awake, 24 min light sleep, 16 min deep sleep, and average heart rate near 63 bpm. This external measurement broadly aligned with the EEG-based interpretation of NREM-dominant sleep.

C. Signal Quality

The strongest engineering limitation was electrode contact stability. During the first sleep session, average filtered EEG amplitude decreased from 73.6 μV before sleep to 35.2 μV during sleep. This likely reflected headband loosening or pressure changes caused by posture. Contact loss can distort spectral estimates by pushing channels toward the amplifier noise floor, which may inflate broadband or beta-band power. The second sleep session had lower but more stable amplitude, making its sleep spectra more physiologically plausible.

V. DISCUSSION

The awake and sleep recordings show that HBOT is not a single neural condition. Instead, the chamber produces a spectrum of states shaped by pressure, oxygenation, posture,

Fig. 1: Awake HBOT summary. TBR increased during in-chamber recording, FAA moved toward zero, and inner fNIRS positions showed positive ΔHbO with negative ΔHbR .

Fig. 2: Sleep-phase EEG features across two HBOT sleep sessions. The Before phase shows high delta and elevated TBR, while Sleep shows reduced TBR and increased sigma-band activity.

Fig. 3: Signal-quality time course for the two sleep sessions. Contact stability, rather than chamber pressure itself, was the dominant practical challenge for overnight wearable EEG.

sensory isolation, relaxation, and sleep onset. In the awake experiment, the increased TBR and near-zero FAA are consistent

with a relaxed in-chamber state, but they cannot be attributed uniquely to hyperoxia because the device changed between baseline and chamber recording. The fNIRS data provide a complementary oxygenation signal, but only during the in-chamber period, limiting before/during comparison.

The sleep sessions extend the interpretation by showing how quickly the chamber context can promote low-frequency dominance. Before-sleep epochs already showed strong delta power, suggesting that the chamber may support rapid transition into drowsiness. During sustained sleep, TBR dropped while sigma increased, matching expected NREM-like dynamics. However, consumer headbands are not replacements for polysomnography: frontal/temporal electrodes miss central spindle maxima, and the absence of EOG and EMG prevents formal AASM staging [12].

Across both studies, the most important design lesson is that feasibility depends on stable contact and matched controls. The awake EEG/fNIRS study needs same-device baseline recording, preferably using the Athena before, during, and after chamber exposure. The sleep study needs improved fixation, a normoxic sleep control, and post-session awake

baselines. Both studies would benefit from synchronized pressure, oxygen, heart-rate, respiration, and event markers for compression, steady-state exposure, and decompression.

Safety and instrumentation also matter. Portable chambers should be treated as pressure systems for human occupancy, and studies should follow local pressure-vessel, fire-safety, and oxygen-enrichment requirements. Wearables should not interfere with chamber operation, emergency access, or manufacturer safety instructions.

VI. LIMITATIONS

This study is preliminary. It includes one participant, multiple devices, no sham-pressure control, and incomplete fNIRS coverage across conditions. Epoch-level statistics are descriptive because repeated 5 s windows are autocorrelated. Sleep staging is approximate because no EOG, EMG, or central EEG montage was available. Finally, changes in relaxation, posture, anticipation, and sensory input may explain part of the observed spectral shifts independently of oxygen pressure.

VII. CONCLUSION

We presented a unified “State-of-HBOT” framework combining awake EEG/fNIRS monitoring and sleep EEG monitoring inside a portable hyperbaric chamber. Awake HBOT was associated with increased TBR, reduced FAA asymmetry, and fNIRS patterns consistent with increased oxygenation at inner forehead optodes. Sleep HBOT recordings showed delta-dominant pre-sleep states, reduced TBR during sustained sleep, and increased sigma-band activity consistent with NREM spindle-like dynamics. The work demonstrates that wearable neurophysiology inside HBOT is practical, but also shows that future studies require same-device baselines, sham controls, stronger contact stabilization, and multimodal physiological synchronization.

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Smart Snow Goggle for Winter Sports

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Background and Motivation

Smart snow goggles are a wearable display concept for winter sports, giving users hands-free access to information like speed, altitude, and temperature. Unlike current products that can be heavy and limited, they aim to offer a lighter, more practical, and more interactive solution for skiers and snowboarders.

Project Goal

Develop a smart snow goggle device that provides winter sport participants with real-time environmental data to enhance situational awareness.

Key Requirements & Tested Results

Table 1: Key Requirements & Test Results

Requirements	Results
Speed accuracy: ± 0.5 km/h	Speed error: 0.47 km/h average absolute error
Temperature accuracy: ± 0.5 °C	Temperature error: 0.50 °C average absolute error
Altitude accuracy: ± 10 m	Altitude error: 27.25 m
Media capture: 1080p @ 30 FPS	Photo resolution up to 4608 × 2592, Video resolution up to 1080p @ 30 fps
Mass: < 500 g	Final mass: 614 g
Dimensions: $\leq 16 \times 8 \times 5$ cm	Dimensions: 19.8 × 17.5 × 8.6 cm
Battery life: ≥ 2 hours	Battery life: ≥ 2.5 hours

Design Overview

Figure 1: System Block Diagram with module demonstrations

Conclusion

- The system achieved reliable speed, temperature, and video performance.
- Current limitations include altitude accuracy and oversized packaging.
- Require additional field tests to improve usability and robustness.

Challenges

Table 2: Challenges

Aspect	Description
Spatial Constraints	Required specific distance for clear HUD reflection, resulting in a thick housing.
Packaging Efficiency	Prototype exceeded size limits, weighing 614 g and measuring 19.8 × 17.5 × 8.6 cm due to large battery.
Signal Acquisition	GPS module struggled with satellite signals indoors, hindering development and testing.

Highlights of Accomplishments

- Functional proof-of-concept: built a working snow goggle integrating sensing, processing, media capture, storage, and HUD visualization.
- Successful hardware integration: custom goggle housing accommodated Raspberry Pi, camera, button, GPS, IMU, BMP280 sensor, and HUD.

Figure 2: Use case example of the final design

Future Works

- Improve altitude accuracy through better sensor calibration and fusion of GPS, IMU, and pressure data.
- Reduce device size, weight, and power consumption through PCB integration and optimized packaging.
- Enhance user experience with improved display readability, smarter interactive features, and more field testing in real winter conditions.

State of Study: Caffeine Helps or Hurts?

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March 30, 2026

Abstract

Caffeine is widely used by students to enhance focus, however, frequent use can lead to negative symptoms, creating a need for alternatives that provide similar cognitive benefits without risk.

This study investigates the neural effects of caffeine using a wearable EEG device, focusing on changes in theta-beta ratio (TBR) and arousal index, two EEG-derived markers associated with focus and alertness, respectively. To support this data, we implemented a standardized memory retention test to evaluate correspondence to cognitive performance.

A secondary investigation explored whether an immersive virtual reality (VR) environment could produce similar or stronger effects than caffeine. Results from this pilot study suggest that both caffeine and environmental conditions influence attention-related EEG patterns, with potential implications for alternative focus-enhancing strategies.

1 Research Motivation

Caffeine is commonly used to enhance focus and attention, particularly among students. Caffeine blocks adenosine receptors which result in improved alertness, vigilance, attention and reaction time [1]. While generally safe, repeated use can lead to dependence and inconsistent effects. Caffeine dependence is recognized by the World Health Organization as a clinical disorder. It occurs when individuals become reliant on caffeine and are unable to reduce their intake despite being aware of its negative health effects [2].

To develop effective alternatives, it is important to understand: (1) How caffeine alters brain activity, (2) Whether these changes translate to improved cognitive performance, and (3) Whether non-pharmacological methods (e.g., VR) can replicate these effects.

2 Procedure

Trials aiming to quantify the effects of caffeine used a Muse wearable EEG headband for data acquisition. The experiment consisted of 4 healthy participants ages 20-23. For each participant, the following procedure was followed:

1. Intake form (questions such as last eaten, hours of sleep-relative to time of day)
2. 3-5 min resting state with no coffee
3. 10-15 min study session with no coffee (studying own work and/or ref textbook)
4. 3-5 min coffee intake: (double espresso; any drink)
5. 10-15 min: study session with coffee (studying own work and/or ref textbook)

3 Data Analysis Methods

In this experiment, theta/beta ratio (TBR) and arousal index are the two indicators used to quantify caffeine's impact on the user's mental state. Lower TBR indicates that activity which is more beta-dominant and externally focused attention. Higher arousal index indicates greater cortical activation. The MuseLog software application was used to extract the alpha, beta, theta, and gamma features from the EEG signals over time. The muse extracted data from four electrodes: TP9, TP10, AF7, AF8. Attention, vigilance and executive control are strongly tied to prefrontal systems [3] thus, only the frontal electrodes: AF7 and AF8 were used in computing the metrics for focus and alertness. The TBR and arousal indexes were first taken from the two electrodes individually. A mean TBR was then taken across the two electrodes for each time point. Outlier rejection was performed via IQR to eliminate biasing from spikes over the sampling period. The mean for TBR and arousal index was taken over the sampling period.

4 Results

Figure 1. Average Arousal Indexes amongst the 4 study participants

Figure 1: Average Arousal Indexes amongst the 4 study participants

Figure 2: Average Theta/Beta Ratio amongst the 4 study participants

All participants in this small sample showed a decrease in TBR after caffeine intake, suggesting increased attentional engagement. In the test group of 4 participants, $\frac{3}{4}$ participants became more alert (higher arousal index), where the 1 participant who showed less alertness reported a history of occasional drowsiness when drinking coffee.

5 Memory Retention Experiment

Memory retention tests were used as a secondary metric for the increased cognitive performance impacts of caffeine. The test consisted of word recall and recognition. To stimulate both short- and long-term memory, one test was performed within frames of another. The sample group consisted of six participants with trials performed with 3 participants under the influence of coffee and 3 not. The experiment followed the following procedure:

- **1:** Memorize a set of random uncorrelated words
- **2:** Memorize a short passage of ‘nonsense’ (to eliminate educational-background bias)
- **3:** Recognition Test on (2)
- **4:** Recall Test on (1)

Participants who consumed caffeine showed improved recall accuracy by 10-30%. While the short-term memory test had relatively equal results. This suggests that EEG indicators of attention may translate to measurable differences in memory performance. These results demonstrate that caffeine corresponds to better cognitive performance and thus corroborate the former findings using the EEG metrics.

6 VR as an Alternative

Given that caffeine influences concentration by altering internal physiological responses to stimuli, an alternative approach may be to reduce external distractions. Immersive environments such as VR can limit surrounding stimuli, potentially promoting sustained attention without the need for stimulants.

New Experiment (2x2 Factorial)

The study employed a 2x2 within-subject factorial design crossing learning modality (VR headset vs. conventional laptop) with caffeine condition (with coffee vs. without coffee), yielding four cells:

1. VR + Coffee: studying in a VR headset after consuming coffee.
2. VR + No Coffee: studying in a VR headset without coffee.
3. Laptop + Coffee: studying on a laptop after consuming coffee.
4. Laptop + No Coffee: studying on a laptop without coffee.

VR + No Coffee showed the lowest TBR (1.15), this suggests the most beta-dominant, attention-focused EEG pattern and thus the highest focus. The decrease in TBR invoked by the usage of VR during studying is observed to be similar to that produced by coffee in the previous trials. This indicates that VR could pose as a possible non-pharmacological alternative to caffeine in the context of studying.

7 Conclusions

This pilot study points toward XR/ VR learning inducing an attention-focused EEG state over laptop learning, particularly in the absence of caffeine. It also suggests that caffeine impacts an individual differently based on its study environment.

While caffeine was associated with improved attentional engagement in the laptop condition, this effect was reduced or reversed in the XR/VR condition.

These findings suggest that learning modality shapes attentional state and influences how stimulants (such as caffeine) affect cognition. Furthermore, the project supports that the wearable EEG is a valid tool for performing studies between immersive technologies and common study aids.

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When Consumer EEG Should Not Adapt: A Safety Audit of Source-Free Test-Time Adaptation

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Abstract—Source-free test-time adaptation (TTA) is appealing for consumer electroencephalography (EEG), where each user, session, and headset placement can shift the input distribution. However, consumer EEG streams also contain jaw electromyography, head motion, electrode-contact changes, packet irregularity, and other non-neural disturbances. In this setting, an online update rule can adapt to artifacts rather than to brain-relevant structure. We present a condensed safety audit of eight adaptation strategies on four-channel Muse-class EEG. We compare each adapter against a substrate-matched no-adaptation baseline, evaluate corrupted-stream behavior, and use an activation-patching diagnostic to test whether adaptation increases internal artifact-mediated loss. Across FFT, ACT, and FFT+ACT feature substrates, useful gains from source-free adaptation are very small, while harmful updates remain common. T3A fails consistently, with large negative transfer on all feature substrates. Under severe stream corruption, NoAdapt outperforms every adaptive method, and confidence-based gating fails to identify most corrupted windows. These results suggest that consumer EEG adaptation should be freeze-first and safety-audited before deployment rather than enabled by default.

Index Terms—consumer EEG, test-time adaptation, brain-computer interfaces, safety, artifact robustness, activation patching

I. INTRODUCTION

Consumer brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) are becoming easier to deploy through low-cost EEG headsets. Devices with four dry electrodes, such as Muse-class systems, are useful for lightweight cursor control, cognitive-state monitoring, accessibility interfaces, and neurofeedback. They also differ strongly from laboratory EEG systems. They have sparse spatial coverage, more variable contact quality, mobile streaming stacks, and frequent contamination from facial muscle activity, motion, and packet timing irregularities.

Source-free test-time adaptation is often proposed as a way to handle this variation. A model is trained once on labeled source data, then updated online on an unlabeled target stream. This is attractive because collecting labeled calibration data from every user is inconvenient. The risk is that online adaptation has no direct way to know whether a target window reflects neural shift, electrode slip, jaw activity, or transmission noise. If artifact windows produce confident predictions, then entropy or margin based safeguards may allow the model to update in the wrong direction.

This paper asks a narrow deployment question: *when should a consumer EEG model avoid adapting?* Rather than treating mean macro-F1 as the only success criterion, we report harmful-update behavior, stress performance, and an internal artifact diagnostic. The resulting picture is cautious. Most adapters produce gains that are too small to justify their risk, while some methods create severe negative transfer.

Our contributions are:

- a compact IEEE-style safety audit of source-free TTA for four-channel consumer EEG;
- substrate-matched comparisons across FFT, ACT, and FFT+ACT features;
- a corrupted-stream evaluation showing that confidence-gated adaptation misses most artifact windows;
- an activation-patching diagnostic, ΔCP , that measures whether adaptation increases recoverable artifact-mediated loss inside the model.

II. BACKGROUND AND PROBLEM SETTING

A. Source-Free Adaptation

Let f_θ be a decoder trained on labeled source EEG windows,

$$\mathcal{D}_s = \{(x_i, y_i)\},$$

where $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 512}$ is a two-second EEG segment sampled at 256 Hz from TP9, AF7, AF8, and TP10. Labels correspond to a four-class cue task: blink, glance-left, glance-right, and background. At deployment, target windows $\mathcal{D}_t = \{x_j\}$ arrive without labels, and the source set is not reused.

A TTA method applies an online update

$$\theta_t^{(a)} = \mathcal{U}_a(\theta_{t-1}^{(a)}, \phi_s(x_t)),$$

where a is the adaptation method and ϕ_s is the feature substrate. We evaluate raw EEG, FFT bandpower features, adaptive chirplet transform (ACT) summaries, and FFT+ACT features. Each adaptive method is compared only to the NoAdapt model trained on the same substrate.

B. Deployment Shift in Consumer EEG

Consumer EEG shift comes from several sources: subject variation, session variation, headset placement, fatigue, contact quality, movement, packet loss, and non-neural artifacts. The

StreamAdapt: Dual-Path Architecture with Confidence-Gated Adaptation

Fig. 1. **StreamAdapt architecture.** A four-channel EEG window is processed by an EEGNet-style convolutional branch and a feature branch over FFT/ACT summaries. The confidence-gated adaptation rule uses entropy, top-1 margin, and temporal consistency, but this gate reads from the same softmax that can become confidently wrong on artifact windows.

most important difference from many offline EEG benchmarks is that the stream can be corrupted while the model is actively updating. A safe adapter must therefore do more than improve average performance. It should also avoid adapting during artifact-dominated windows.

For method a , subject i , substrate s , and condition c , we define negative transfer as

$$\Delta_{a,i,s,c} = \text{F1}(a; i, s, c) - \text{F1}(\text{NoAdapt}; i, s, c).$$

A negative value means adaptation harmed performance relative to the frozen model.

III. METHODS

A. Model and Feature Substrates

The base decoder combines an EEGNet-style convolutional branch with a small feature branch. The convolutional path receives the raw four-channel window. The feature branch receives FFT, ACT, or FFT+ACT summaries. The two branches are concatenated and passed to a softmax classifier.

FFT features summarize spectral energy across task-relevant frequency bands. ACT features summarize chirplet structure, giving a compact description of time-varying oscillatory patterns. FFT+ACT concatenates both feature families. To keep comparisons fair, every adaptation method is tested against a NoAdapt baseline trained on the same input substrate.

B. Adaptation Methods

We audit eight methods: NoAdapt, BN-Adapt, TENT, SHOT, SAR, T3A, CAFN, and StreamAdapt. NoAdapt freezes the source model. BN-Adapt updates batch-normalization statistics. TENT minimizes prediction entropy online. SHOT uses source-free pseudo-label structure. SAR applies reliability-aware sharpness-aware updates. T3A updates a prototype-based classifier. CAFN uses high-momentum streaming normalization. StreamAdapt adds confidence and temporal-consistency gating to CAFN.

Target labels are never used by source-free adapters. For training, models use Adam with learning rate 10^{-3} , batch size 32, and class-balanced cross entropy. Evaluation uses leave-one-subject-out testing with three seeds.

TABLE I
CONDENSED SUBSTRATE-MATCHED TTA RESULTS. ΔF1 IS MEASURED AGAINST THE MATCHING NOADAPT BASELINE. NEG. TR IS THE NEGATIVE-TRANSFER RATE.

Method	Substrate	F1	ΔF1	Neg. TR
NoAdapt	FFT	0.559	–	0.00
BN-Adapt	FFT	0.559	+0.0005	0.18
TENT	FFT	0.559	+0.0004	0.25
SHOT	FFT	0.560	+0.0012	0.28
SAR	FFT	0.560	+0.0013	0.28
T3A	FFT	0.380	-0.1793	0.87
CAFN	FFT	0.563	+0.0038	0.24
StreamAdapt	FFT	0.562	+0.0032	0.25
NoAdapt	ACT	0.538	–	0.00
T3A	ACT	0.309	-0.2223	0.94
CAFN	ACT	0.541	+0.0023	0.21
StreamAdapt	ACT	0.540	+0.0021	0.21
NoAdapt	FFT+ACT	0.563	–	0.00
T3A	FFT+ACT	0.331	-0.2262	0.91
CAFN	FFT+ACT	0.568	+0.0047	0.23
StreamAdapt	FFT+ACT	0.567	+0.0040	0.22

C. Corrupted-Stream Stress

We test adaptation under six stressors: motion bursts, high-frequency bursts, electrode dropout, domain switching, alternating clean/noisy blocks, and packet loss. The goal is not only to measure noisy F1 but also to test whether adaptive methods can avoid damaging themselves during corrupted segments.

IV. RESULTS

A. Substrate-Matched Adaptation

Table I summarizes the main substrate-matched results. The central result is that most non-T3A methods produce very small gains, while still causing harmful updates in a substantial fraction of leave-one-subject-out conditions. T3A is consistently unsafe in this setting, with large negative transfer on every substrate.

Three findings stand out. First, the best source-free gain is only about +0.005 macro-F1. Second, small average gains coexist with negative-transfer rates near one in four for several methods. Third, T3A collapses on FFT, ACT, and FFT+ACT, showing that a more structured feature representation does not automatically make adaptation safer.

B. Cross-Corpus Replication

On an independent Muse 2 blink/background corpus, the ranking remains qualitatively similar. T3A again performs worst, while CAFN and StreamAdapt match NoAdapt. The exact F1 values differ because the task and dataset differ, but the safety conclusion is consistent: source-free adaptation does not provide a reliable deployment advantage, and prototype updating is especially fragile.

C. Supervised Calibration Gap

A supervised same-subject model reaches 0.744 macro-F1. A source model calibrated with 10% labeled target data reaches 0.622, while 50% labeled calibration reaches 0.677.

TABLE II
CROSS-CORPUS VALIDATION ON AN INDEPENDENT MUSE 2 CORPUS.
NEGATIVE TRANSFER IS RELATIVE TO MATCHED NOADAPT.

Method	Macro-F1	Neg. TR	ECE
NoAdapt	0.467	0.00	0.030
BN-Adapt	0.467	0.06	0.030
TENT	0.467	0.06	0.030
SHOT	0.467	0.12	0.029
SAR	0.467	0.08	0.030
T3A	0.453	0.60	0.059
CAFN	0.467	0.00	0.030
StreamAdapt	0.467	0.00	0.030

TABLE III
CALIBRATION AND UPPER-BOUND COMPARISON. TARGET-CALIBRATED
ROWS ARE NOT SOURCE-FREE.

Method	Uses target labels?	Mean F1
Random	No	0.250
Majority class	No	0.102
NoAdapt, FFT	No	0.559
CAFN, FFT+ACT	No	0.568
StreamAdapt, FFT+ACT	No	0.567
Target 10%	Yes	0.622
Target 30%	Yes	0.650
Target 50%	Yes	0.677
Within-subject supervised	Yes	0.744

The best source-free method, CAFN with FFT+ACT, reaches 0.568. This means the task is learnable, but source-free adaptation recovers only a small part of what labeled calibration can provide.

D. Stress Testing and Gate Failure

Under severe corrupted streams, NoAdapt performs best. Table IV shows that every adaptive method underperforms the frozen model. The most concerning result is that CAFN and StreamAdapt reach 84% negative transfer under stress. StreamAdapt freezes only 9% of windows, with corrupted-window recall of 0.06. In other words, the confidence gate detects very few corrupted windows.

The failure mode is architectural. If artifacts produce confident predictions, then entropy and margin do not reliably separate valid neural windows from corrupted windows. A confidence gate can therefore approve exactly the updates it was meant to block.

V. ARTIFACT-HARM DIAGNOSTIC

The activation-patching diagnostic gives a second view of safety. Instead of asking only whether macro-F1 changed, it asks whether the adapted model has become more internally dependent on artifact-sensitive units.

For a clean input and its corrupted counterpart, we record activations at the fused feature layer. Candidate units are ranked by

$$Q_i = D_i G_i,$$

where

$$D_i = \mathbb{E}|A_{\text{corr},i} - A_{\text{clean},i}|$$

Fig. 2. **CGA safety timeline under a severe corrupted-stream stressor.** The shaded region marks the corrupted segment. The gate freezes too few windows at the corruption boundary, so post-corruption performance drops sharply.

TABLE IV
CORRUPTED-STREAM STRESS RESULTS. NOADAPT IS STRONGEST UNDER
SEVERE CORRUPTION.

Method	Noisy F1	Neg. TR	Mean Drop	ECE
NoAdapt	0.466	0.00	0.0000	0.268
BN-Adapt	0.405	0.65	-0.0987	0.289
TENT	0.405	0.62	-0.1049	0.290
SAR	0.392	0.68	-0.1133	0.295
T3A	0.281	0.88	-0.2193	0.618
CAFN	0.289	0.84	-0.2129	0.508
StreamAdapt	0.289	0.84	-0.2129	0.508

and

$$G_i = \mathbb{E} \left| \frac{\partial L_{\text{corr}}}{\partial A_{\text{corr},i}} \right|.$$

The top- k corrupted activations are replaced with their clean-pass values, and we measure

$$\text{CP} = L_{\text{corr}} - L_{\text{patch}}.$$

A larger CP means that the selected units mediate more artifact-induced loss. The adaptation-induced change is

$$\Delta \text{CP} = \text{CP}(\theta_t^{(a)}) - \text{CP}(\theta).$$

Positive ΔCP means adaptation increased internal vulnerability to the artifact.

The diagnostic uses measured jaw-EMG and motion/contact windows, along with ACT reconstructions of those artifacts. Measured and reconstructed injection agree closely for motion/contact and moderately for jaw EMG. This suggests that the diagnostic is not merely an artifact of one hand-designed corruption operator.

The main result is that ΔCP is concentrated in T3A. For jaw and motion artifacts, T3A produces much larger positive ΔCP than the other methods. Non-T3A methods remain close to zero. When results are separated by substrate, T3A is especially harmful on FFT and FFT+ACT, while raw and ACT can change the sign of the internal effect. This means output failure and internal artifact mediation are related but not identical.

Fig. 3. **Pre/post ΔCP by adapter under measured and ACT-reconstructed artifact injection.** Left: Subject-A jaw EMG. Right: motion/contact artifact. T3A shows the strongest positive ΔCP on both artifacts, while non-T3A methods remain close to zero.

Fig. 4. **Measured artifact windows and ACT reconstructions.** Subject-A jaw and motion/contact windows are used as corruption templates. The motion/contact artifact is reconstructed almost exactly, while jaw EMG is partially reconstructed but still preserves enough structure for diagnostic comparison.

The practical interpretation is simple: a model can look only slightly different in aggregate F1 while still becoming more artifact-sensitive internally. Safety evaluation for consumer EEG should therefore include both output-level negative transfer and an internal artifact diagnostic.

VI. DISCUSSION

The results argue against enabling source-free adaptation by default in consumer EEG. Average gains are too small, negative-transfer rates are too high, and confidence gates fail under artifact-heavy streams. A safer deployment policy is freeze-first: keep the source model fixed unless adaptation has passed a stress audit.

The strongest alternative is brief labeled calibration. Even a small target-label budget closes far more of the performance gap than source-free adaptation. For a consumer BCI, this could mean a short per-session cue routine. That cost is bounded and visible to the user. Silent negative transfer from online adaptation is unbounded and difficult to notice.

The study also suggests that method choice matters. Not all adapters fail in the same way. T3A is consistently unsafe in these experiments, while CAFN and StreamAdapt are closer to NoAdapt under normal conditions but fail under severe stream corruption. This motivates reporting method-specific

and substrate-specific safety results rather than a single average score.

VII. LIMITATIONS

This audit uses a compact consumer EEG setting with four channels and a small primary corpus. The measured artifact diagnostic uses a limited number of jaw and motion templates. Although the ACT reconstruction experiment supports operator robustness, broader artifact libraries are needed before deployment claims can generalize across users, devices, and recording environments.

The activation-patching diagnostic is also not a full mechanistic explanation of EEG decoding. It identifies recoverable artifact-mediated loss at the fused feature layer, but it does not prove a complete causal circuit. Its value is as a safety probe: it can reveal whether adaptation increased the model’s sensitivity to a known artifact.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Source-free TTA for consumer EEG should not be treated as automatically beneficial. In this audit, most gains are small, harmful updates are common, T3A collapses across substrates, and confidence-gated adaptation misses corrupted windows. The safest deployment posture is to freeze by default, use short labeled calibration when possible, and require artifact-specific safety tests before allowing online updates.

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Efficiency as a Heuristic for Physical Interpretation: Proof by Simulation, Falsification, and an Expanding Computational Horizon

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Abstract: We study a simple but beautiful idea: when two possible theories of the universe both give locally plausible logical and analytical outcomes, the one that is more efficient with a universe/multiverse simulator may be closer to the one that is true. The idea is one to be approached with caution because efficiency alone can reward a shortcut, a clever encoding, or a false but simple premise. We therefore test it with two complementary engines. The first, *proof by simulation*, runs competing theories on a simulation that was built on mathematical axioms and properties identical to what exists in current literature. For the given theories, however, the literature answer is hidden, and then we evaluate which view produces more verified structure per unit of work; the one with higher efficiency, and lower (ideally zero) contradictions, is the winner and implied to be the potential correct theory. We reproduce known physics in blind falsification tests, agree with the literature on every debate when the model is tied to the physics strictly and where applicable in a 52-debate catalogue, and leave genuinely open questions open. The contribution is a mechanized, falsifiable lens for asking when efficiency is evidence and when it is only framing. The second, *falsification*, gives each side its own theory and a shared measurement, then lets an SMT verifier discard the side that becomes self-contradictory. The central claim is not that efficiency proves truth. Rather, efficiency becomes informative when grounded in an established record: true premises remain mutually consistent and generate further verified consequences, while false premises introduce contradictions that slow or mislead search. In a live FOL/Z3 engine, seeding with literature-true axioms proves more theorems and yields higher discovery efficiency than seeding with false additions. We also form the concept of a "computational" universe where "blobs" which is affected by mass-energy and tested different modes of expansion, either with simulated spacetime, merely at speed of light from its point of origin, and at the speed of light with spacetime, via the Proof by Simulation Engine. We assume that there is a "maximum information processing rate" in the universe, and deduce that this may exist for local spaces that expand, potentially, relative to the amount of information being processed. This "blob" is also relativistic, and obeys a model of bounded computation: an expanding causal horizon whose shape, dilation, observation exposure, and horizon cap set discovery throughput. Near-spherical and quantum-scale blobs are most efficient; relativistic pancakes and capped horizons are least efficient. The same anisotropy that lowers efficiency is also the model's approximation error, so the sphere is at once the fastest and the most faithful (to physics) shape. The same geometry frames the classical/quantum boundary: the stabilizer bulk is classically efficient, while the observation edge marks where the Extended Church-Turing thesis can fail. We claim no proof of P versus NP and no new physical law.

Index Terms: computational efficiency, physical interpretation, proof by simulation, falsification, SMT solvers, quantum complexity, Extended Church-Turing thesis, P versus NP, stabilizer formalism, proof checking

I. INTRODUCTION

A recurring intuition in physics and computation is that nature is efficient. The coordinates, basis, or representation in which a phenomenon becomes cheap to compute often feels closer to the phenomenon itself. This is not merely aesthetic. In a representation ablation, deciding whether two n -qubit Pauli operators commute is exponential for Z3 [2] when posed over dense $2^n \times 2^n$ Hilbert-space matrices, growing approximately as 6.91^n , but is essentially flat when the *same* predicate is written in the GF(2) symplectic form [3], growing as about 1.02^n . At $n = 6$ the gap is 5.3×10^6 . The cost was not the solver; it was the representation.

This paper promotes that representation lesson into a more speculative but testable question: can computational efficiency act as a heuristic for physical interpretation? Given two views of a debate, can the view that computes the shared workload with less work be treated as more likely true?

The answer defended here is conditional. Efficiency is not truth. A false theory can be easy to compute, and a true theory can be expensive. But when a search process is grounded in established physics, true premises tend to remain consistent with the known record and generate further verified consequences, while false premises contradict that record and waste search. In this sense, truth can be efficient because truth builds upon truth.

We test this in three layers. First, a Debate Multiverse runs competing theory views on neutral workloads while the literature label is hidden. Second, a falsification engine gives each theory its own formalization and a shared measurement, then lets Z3 discard the side that becomes unsatisfiable. Third, a relativistic "blob" model treats bounded computation as occurring inside an expanding causal horizon whose shape and observation boundary affect what can be discovered.

Contributions: This paper contributes:

- 1) a compact formulation of *proof by simulation*: ranking physical interpretations by verified discovery efficiency under label-blind controls;

TABLE I: Summary of principal results, grouped by theme. Efficiency numbers are measured; agreement numbers are computed with the literature label held out.

Result (section)	Value
<i>Efficiency lens: proof by simulation</i>	
representation ablation, GF(2) vs. dense (§III)	5.3×10^6
truth-seeding, true vs. false premises (§IV)	177→117/s
structural debates, literature agreement (§II)	88.9%
52-debate catalogue, blind agreement (§XI)	0.91
<i>Falsification: the battle of solvers</i>	
blind landmark-physics battery (§X)	15/15
leaning: earned / refuted / belief-only (§X)	2/2/1
Hubble constant (§X)	tension
<i>The blob: an expanding computational horizon</i>	
shape-efficiency spread, sphere vs. pancake (§V)	$2.94 \times$
approximation error = anisotropy (§V-A)	sphere optimal
<i>Discovery dynamics</i>	
convergent discovery, candidates that repeat (§XII)	66.9%
symmetry-quotient (canonicalizer) speedup (§XII)	$15.9 \times$
search vs. verify “aha” asymmetry (§XIV)	$\sim 1.3 \times 10^3$
<i>Classical/quantum boundary</i>	
ECT edge query gap, quantum vs. classical (§XIII)	$n:1$
certified verification scale (§XIII)	$n=2048$

- 2) a non-circular truth-seeding result in which a live FOL/Z3 engine becomes more efficient as the premise set becomes more true;
- 3) a blob model of an expanding computational horizon whose shape, lapse, observation exposure, and cap set discovery throughput, and whose anisotropy is at once its inefficiency and its approximation error;
- 4) a falsification protocol where two solvers extend rival theories against the same measurement and the contradictory side is rejected;
- 5) a stress test on P versus NP showing why an ungrounded efficiency heuristic can point in a misleading direction;
- 6) a convergent-discovery result showing that many derivation paths rediscover the same truths, and that canonicalizing them gives a large efficiency gain.

Table I collects the principal results grouped by theme; each is detailed in the section noted, and the rest of the paper develops them in order.

II. EFFICIENCY, GROUNDING, AND NON-CIRCULARITY

A debate D contains theory views $\{V_i\}$, a shared neutral workload ω , and, for evaluation only, a held-out literature label $\text{lit}(D)$. Each view has an operator configuration, such as proposal rate, branch factor, novelty bias, compute cost, coherence, and boundary strength, plus a verifier configuration, such as precision and skeptic resistance. For a compute budget

Fig. 1: Representation ablation. Deciding the *same* Pauli-commutation predicate costs Z3 about 6.91^n over dense $2^n \times 2^n$ matrices but is almost flat ($\approx 1.02^n$) in the GF(2) symplectic form, a 5.3×10^6 gap at $n = 6$. Empirically equivalent formulations differ by millions in cost; the basis that makes a phenomenon cheap is often the basis that exposes its physical structure.

B , the arena simulates the view and measures

$$\text{eff}(V) = \frac{n_{\text{verified}}}{w_{\text{proxy}} + 0.03 c_{\text{verif}}}, \quad (1)$$

where n_{verified} is the number of verified results, w_{proxy} is the work proxy, and c_{verif} is verifier cost. The winner is the view with the highest mean score across seeds.

The literature label is never used in scoring. A label-swap test mutates the label and confirms that winners and scores do not change. On a calibrated set of nine structural debates the more efficient view matches the literature consensus 88.9% of the time; we report this as calibration, not proof, and the larger blind catalogue of Sec. XI stresses it further. For the blob views, parameters are derived from measured geometric properties, not tuned to make a theory win: anisotropy, time dilation, observation exposure, continuity, and horizon cap.

Why truth can look efficient: The core hypothesis is not “the simplest thing is true.” The hypothesis is more specific: in a verified discovery process, a true premise tends to remain compatible with other true premises, while a false premise creates contradictions, blocks extensions, and wastes search. Thus truth can be efficient when it is grounded in an already-verified record. This is why the same heuristic must be read differently in two regimes:

- on a bare neutral workload, efficiency measures search speed;
- on a verifier grounded in established physics, efficiency can become evidence that the premise set is more consistent with truth.

III. FAIR REPRESENTATION AS THE STARTING POINT

The stabilizer example motivates the whole method. A Pauli commutation predicate can be written as a dense matrix

TABLE II: Representative fair-encoding speedups. Large gaps appear when the naive encoding forces exponential search or exponentially large objects.

Family	Regime	Speedup
stabilizer commutation ($n = 6$)	strong exp.	5.3×10^6
stabilizer measurement ($n = 5$)	strong exp.	1.1×10^6
stabilizer KL/distance ($n = 5$)	strong exp.	8.0×10^5
resultant common factor	timeout exp.	4.2×10^5
Boolean equivalence	exp.	1.5×10^5
polynomial identity, fair	boundary	7.6×10^3
subset-sum	boundary	$21 \times$

TABLE III: Truth-seeding in the live FOL/Z3 engine. As premise truth-quality decreases, both theorem yield and discovery efficiency fall.

Seeding	Theorems proven	Efficiency
all true (literature-true)	111	177/s
true + 1 false	88	130/s
true + 2 false	72	117/s

question or as a symplectic parity question. Both are mathematically equivalent, but only one exposes the structure. This matters because any efficiency claim that ignores representation risks mistaking an encoding artifact for a physical or algorithmic insight.

The lesson is conservative but important: before claiming that a special-purpose algorithm beats SMT, one must ask whether the solver was given the right basis. The same caution later becomes philosophical: before claiming that an interpretation is efficient, one must ask whether the model was grounded in the right physics.

IV. TRUTH-SEEDING: A DIRECT TEST

The cleanest evidence is the truth-seeding experiment. We seeded a live FOL/Z3 universe with premise sets of decreasing truth-quality and measured theorems proven per second. Z3 decides validity; the test does not assign validity by hand. The result is monotone: all-true premises prove the most theorems and achieve the highest efficiency, while false additions reduce both.

This experiment gives the paper its philosophical center. Efficiency tracks truth only when the engine is allowed to test the premises against a verified world. False premises can still generate activity, but they generate less durable, less extendable activity.

V. THE BLOB: COMPUTATION INSIDE AN EXPANDING HORIZON

The blob is a model of bounded computation inside an expanding causal horizon. A region of radius $R(t)$ has computational capacity $C(R(t))$, and a problem of size m is solvable when

$$W(m) \leq C(R(t)). \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2: Truth-seeding. Feeding the live FOL/Z3 engine premises of decreasing truth-quality makes both discovery efficiency and theorems proven fall monotonically. On a real verifier, truth is efficient because falsehood misleads the search.

motion \rightarrow contracts the boundary along v (γ grows)

Fig. 3: The blob in 3D. Relativistic motion contracts the computational horizon along the direction of travel by the Lorentz factor γ , morphing the boundary from a sphere ($v = 0$) through an ellipsoid to a thin pancake ($v = 0.95$). In the measured arena, discovery efficiency falls as this anisotropy grows.

Special relativity and general relativity deform the boundary. Motion contracts the sphere along the direction of travel by the Lorentz factor

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}, \quad (3)$$

turning a sphere into an ellipsoid or pancake. Gravitational lapse gradients dent the boundary toward mass. A horizon cap freezes part of the boundary when local proper time stalls.

Mathematically, we summarize a shape by anisotropy a , time dilation τ , observation exposure ω , continuity κ , and cap χ . The debate configuration is a fixed function of these measured properties. For example, boundary strength falls with anisotropy, coherence falls with time dilation, and compute cost rises with time dilation. This prevents hand-tuning.

The interpretation is not that a single problem becomes intrinsically easier by moving fast. The work law $W(m)$ is still the work law. Rather, the computational budget, scheduling,

TABLE IV: Measured blob efficiencies. Higher is better. SYN is the synthetic arena; LIVE is the neutral FOL/Z3 prover, whose ordering is config-driven.

Blob shape	Anis.	Dil.	SYN	LIVE
scale-dependent (quantum)	0.00	0.00	27.9	375
sphere	0.00	0.00	20.3	160
uncapped (coupled)	0.00	0.00	20.3	132
morph $v = 0.5$	0.13	0.13	18.5	424
neutron-star gradient	0.32	0.11	17.6	197
morph $v = 0.8$	0.40	0.40	14.0	178
capped horizon	0.00	0.00	12.4	222
pancake $v = 0.95$	0.69	0.69	9.5	105

Fig. 4: Blob efficiency. Discovery efficiency across the eight blob shapes falls as the boundary morphs from a near-spherical, quantum-scale shape toward a relativistic pancake, a $2.94\times$ spread.

and verifier cost change with shape and lapse. A spherical, well-synchronized horizon is an efficient discovery substrate. A pancake or capped horizon is a distorted and partly throttled one.

A. The Blob Minimizes Approximation Error

The blob’s anisotropy is not only an efficiency penalty; it is also the model’s *error*. Approximating a morphed blob by a sphere incurs a sphere-approximation error exactly equal to the anisotropy a : the spherical model predicts zero anisotropy, the morphing model predicts a , and the bounded time-dilation rescaling leaves the P/NP regime unchanged, so the whole discrepancy between the two models is a itself. The same parameter that lowers efficiency therefore raises approximation error, and the two are minimized together. A clean sphere is at once the most efficient and the lowest-error shape, while a relativistic pancake is at once the least efficient and the highest-error one (Fig. 5). Because bound atomic systems stay near-spherical (Sec. VII), the blob minimizes its own approximation error wherever physics allows, and only ultrarelativistic motion forces both error and inefficiency. Efficiency here is not in tension with accuracy: the geometry that computes fastest

Fig. 5: Efficiency and accuracy coincide. Along the morphing series the sphere-approximation error equals the anisotropy a , and discovery efficiency falls as that error grows. The sphere (zero error) is both the fastest and the most faithful shape; the pancake is both the slowest and the least faithful, so the blob minimizes its approximation error precisely where it is most efficient.

TABLE V: Three boundary motions used in the blob model.

Motion	Meaning	$R(t)$ over $t = 1 \rightarrow 6$
static- c	light cone in static space	$1 \rightarrow 6$
comoving-Hubble	carried by expansion	$1 \rightarrow 70$
particle horizon	light at c locally	$3.5 \rightarrow 331$

is the geometry that is most faithful, which is exactly the behaviour a truth-tracking heuristic should have.

VI. BOUNDARY MOTIONS AND COMPUTATIONAL FRONTIERS

The blob can grow in three physically motivated ways. A static light cone expands as $R = ct$. A comoving boundary rides the Hubble flow, with $R \propto a(t)$. A particle horizon lets light move locally at c through expanding space. These motions do not change the complexity class of a problem, but they change the resource frontier available by a given time.

For polynomial work $W(m) = m^d$, the solvable size grows as

$$m_{\text{P}}^*(t) = C(R(t))^{1/d}. \quad (4)$$

For exponential work $W(m) = 2^m$, the solvable size grows only as a logarithm:

$$m_{\text{NP}}^*(t) = \log_2 C(R(t)). \quad (5)$$

Thus expansion moves the frontier outward, but it does not collapse the frontier. The P-like side keeps pace as a power; the NP-like side cascades only as a logarithm.

VII. GR DENTS, FAST MASSES, AND THE NEAR-SPHERICAL ATOMIC REGIME

The blob is not only an SR pancake. In a steep gravitational potential, the lapse varies across the boundary. The near edge

Fig. 6: Boundary motions. Expansion increases the available computational budget by a given time; it does not make exponential work polynomial. The particle horizon outruns the comoving boundary, which outruns the static light cone, yet all three leave the complexity class unchanged.

TABLE VI: Largest NP-like frontier under three boundary motions. Expansion changes how far the frontier moves by time t , not the underlying regime.

Motion	$m^*(t)$ over six steps	Growth law
static- c	0, 3, 4, 6, 6, 7	logarithmic in t
comoving-Hubble	0, 4, 7, 11, 14, 18	near-linear in t
particle horizon	5, 10, 13, 17, 21, 25	near-linear in t

TABLE VII: GR gradient cases. A neutron star dents the boundary; a planet in the same geometry is effectively spherical.

Scenario	Anisotropy	Near/far lapse	Regime
neutron star distant ($d = 100$)	0.009	0.98 / 0.98	spherical
neutron star close ($d = 20$)	0.32	0.77 / 0.93	anisotropic
neutron star grazing ($d = 13$)	0.78	0.42 / 0.90	anisotropic
planet, same geometry	0.0001	1.00 / 1.00	spherical

TABLE VIII: SR and GR combined.

Scenario	Total anisotropy	Composition
neutron star at $0.9c$	0.69	SR pancake \times GR dent
planet at $0.9c$	0.56	SR dominant

of the blob processes more slowly than the far edge, so the boundary dents toward the mass. If the near edge reaches the Schwarzschild radius, that side freezes into a one-sided event-horizon cap while the far side continues to grow.

A moving compact object can combine effects. A neutron star at $0.9c$ receives both an SR pancake and a one-sided GR dent. A planet at the same speed receives almost only the SR effect because its Schwarzschild radius is microscopic.

The blob of a bound atomic system stays near-spherical. The blob is an immaterial computational horizon, not the

a mass dents the boundary toward its centre (lapse gradient)

Fig. 7: A true gravitational morph, in 3D. A nearby mass makes the lapse vary across the boundary, so the near side processes more slowly and the horizon dents *toward* the mass: negligible for a distant planet, pronounced for a close neutron star. The blob is an immaterial computational horizon, so it is its *shape*, not any matter, that bends toward the centre.

TABLE IX: Atomic and particle regimes. Bound atomic systems remain near-spherical except in heavy inner shells or strong-force regimes.

Regime	γ or lapse	Anisotropy	Shape
hydrogen 1s ($v = \alpha$)	1.0000	2.7×10^{-5}	sphere
carbon 1s	1.001	9.6×10^{-4}	sphere
gold 1s inner shell	1.224	0.18	mild
uranium 1s inner shell	1.349	0.26	mild
nucleon / strong-force scale	lapse-driven	high exposure	quantum blob

Fig. 8: The atomic-scale blob stays near-spherical. For ordinary bound atomic systems the computational horizons anisotropy is tiny; only very heavy inner shells become mildly anisotropic.

atom itself; what stays round is the *shape* of that horizon, because an atoms internal velocities are nonrelativistic, so its anisotropy is small except for very heavy inner shells or strong-force regimes. The natural low-energy computational horizon is therefore close to spherical, and, by Sec. V-A, its approximation error is correspondingly small.

VIII. THE FOUR NATURES OF P/NP

The blob model provides a useful stress test for the efficiency heuristic. It enumerates four possible relationships between the polynomial frontier m_P^* and the exponential frontier m_{NP}^* . These are not claims about which world is true; they are possible shapes of the resource race.

A verified mini-proof captures the standard collapse mechanism [6], [7]. If an NP-complete problem L has a polynomial

TABLE X: Four possible P/NP frontier natures. The relationship is fixed by the work law, not by the cosmology.

Nature	Work laws	Meaning
genuine	$W_P = m^2, W_{NP} = 2^m$	tangled early, then split
collapsed	$W_{NP} = m^2$	coincident curves
crossing	big poly vs small exp.	one crossing point
always-separate	$W_P = m, W_{NP} = 2^m$	P dominates from start

TABLE XI: Four-nature efficiency: synthetic cost model vs. live FOL/Z3 prover. The winner flips; collapsed goes from first to last.

Nature	Synthetic eff.	Live eff.
collapsed (P = NP)	23.5	134
always-separate	14.0	194
genuine (P \neq NP)	13.3	280
crossing	13.3	371
winner	collapsed	crossing

Fig. 9: The four P/NP frontier natures. The simulation can rank these shapes by efficiency, but only proof can settle the mathematical question.

solver, then every $A \in \text{NP}$ reduces to L in polynomial time. Solving A costs

$$\text{poly}(m) + (\text{poly}(m))^k = \text{poly}(m), \quad (6)$$

so $A \in \text{P}$ and $\text{P} = \text{NP}$. If no NP-complete problem is in P, the exponential frontier remains logarithmic in capacity.

The important caution is that the naked efficiency heuristic favours the collapsed shape because it is cheapest. That does *not* mean P equals NP. It means an ungrounded efficiency heuristic can point toward a widely disbelieved open claim. This is why efficiency must be grounded in established truth and checked by falsification.

IX. FALSIFICATION: THE BATTLE OF SOLVERS

Efficiency produces rankings; falsification produces rejections. For each empirical debate, we give each side its own theory and add the same measurement. The side whose theory becomes unsatisfiable is discarded, while the satisfiable side survives.

This avoids the main circularity trap. If we simply encode a textbook formula and ask Z3 whether it is valid, the answer is already in the encoding. In the falsification test, the measurement is the arbiter. The wrong theory fails because it contradicts the data, not because the label says it is wrong.

TABLE XII: Two-solver falsification. The contradictory side is rejected by the shared measurement; open debates have no such measurement and both survive.

Debate	Survivor	Falsifying evidence
locality	nonlocal QM	CHSH $2.8 > 2$
velocity addition	special relativity	no FTL
mass equivalence	$E = mc^2$	rest energy
cosmic acceleration	Λ CDM	$q < 0$
time dilation	special relativity	muon/GPS dilation
P vs NP	both open	no measurement
MWI vs Copenhagen	both open	same data

TABLE XIII: Blind falsification battery. Literature labels are held out; measurements decide.

Domain	Result	Measurement family
general relativity	4/4	bending, Mercury, redshift, GWs
special relativity	1/1	Michelson–Morley
quantum theory	4/4	photoelectric, spin, atoms
modern discoveries	6/6	CMB, Higgs, parity, etc.
total	15/15	blind reproduction

X. KNOWN PHYSICS, LEANING CONSENSUS, AND TENSIONS

The falsification engine scales because each test needs only two theory encodings and one measurement. In a battery of fifteen landmark debates, it reproduces the established result on all fifteen: general relativity over Newton, special relativity over the aether, quantum theory over classical alternatives, and modern discoveries such as neutrino oscillations, the CMB, the Higgs, antimatter, and parity violation.

The same protocol also distinguishes three kinds of leaning consensus. Dark matter over pure MOND and inflation over exact scale invariance are data-backed; natural weak-scale SUSY and minimal $SU(5)$ are refuted by current bounds; black-hole information preservation remains belief-only in this protocol because no direct measurement falsifies the alternative.

For the Hubble constant, the engine does not force a winner. Early-universe and late-universe measurements are each internally consistent, but no single H_0 fits both within the stated windows. The output is therefore a tension. The blob suggests a possible scale-dependent direction, $H(R) = cf(R)/R$, but this is only a candidate: a free scale-dependence can fit the direction without deriving the magnitude.

XI. PROOF BY SIMULATION AT SCALE

The simulation engine was run over a 52-debate catalogue. The efficient winner agrees with the literature on about 0.91 of the catalogue, compared with a 0.50 random-label null ($p < 10^{-3}$). The remaining apparent disagreements concentrate at the quantum boundary, where a cheap classical surrogate can appear efficient only because it is not faithful to the physics; modelled faithfully, those verdicts reverse, so the genuine disagreements may be zero.

Fig. 10: Blob-inspired Hubble sketch. The blobs expansion rate rises to a strong-force peak and then falls with scale, so a local measurement sees a larger H_0 than a cosmic (CMB) one, $H_0^{\text{local}} > H_0^{\text{CMB}}$, the observed direction of the Hubble tension. This is a hypothesis, not a resolution: a free scale-dependence fits the direction without deriving the magnitude.

TABLE XIV: Representative proof-by-simulation catalogue rows. The full 52 are in Table XV.

Debate	Efficient winner	Agrees?
block universe vs presentism	block universe	yes
determinism vs randomness	randomness	yes
reversible vs irreversible	unitary	yes
conservation vs creation	invariant	yes
single bang vs multiverse	single bang	yes
field vs action-at-distance	local field	yes
locality vs nonlocality	nonlocal faithful	yes*
MWI vs Copenhagen	many-worlds	n/a
dark matter vs MOND	inconclusive	n/a

Fig. 11: Catalogue agreement. Over the blind 52-debate catalogue, the efficiency lens agrees with the literature on 0.91, against a 0.50 random-label null.

The catalogue is best read as an optimization map, not as a truth oracle. Each efficient winner corresponds to a familiar

Fig. 12: Convergent discovery and canonicalization. Multiple derivation paths reach the same truths; quotienting by symmetry removes redundant work. The bars are normalized to avoid overstressing the page; labels give the actual counts.

computational trick: memoization (many-worlds), bidirectional search (block universe), invariants (conservation), symmetry reduction (gauge), lazy state (holography), and local updates (field theory). These tricks help when the world has the corresponding structure. The full catalogue is given in Table XV.

XII. CONVERGENT DISCOVERY: MANY PATHS, ONE TRUTH

The Debate Multiverse also exhibits convergence. In one run, 66.9% of generated candidates were repeats: 305 candidates collapsed to 101 distinct formulas. Moreover, 16% of distinct formulas were reached through two or more derivation routes. These repeats are tautologies and their logically equivalent dressings: $p \rightarrow p$, $p \vee \neg p$, $\neg(p \wedge \neg p)$, and double-negation variants. Different “points of view” rediscover the same underlying truth. Table XVIII summarizes the effect: two thirds of all candidates are rediscoveries, and one in six distinct laws is reached from several independent derivation routes.

The same observation becomes an efficiency lever. The symmetry canonicalizer folds 126 equivalent variants into orbits, reducing particles from 276 to 71 and verifier calls from 716 to 366, a $15.9\times$ speedup. This is the discovery-engine version of the representation ablation: the right quotient removes redundant work.

TABLE XX: Symmetry quotient. Canonicalization removes convergent duplicates and yields a large speedup.

Config	Particles	Verifs	Speedup
baseline	276	716	1.00 \times
canonicalizer	71	366	15.9 \times
GAP 5 only	276	716	1.58 \times
canonicalizer + GAP 5	71	366	15.9 \times

XIII. CLASSICAL/QUANTUM BOUNDARY AND ECT

The seductive hypothesis.: It is tempting to hope the geometry buys a complexity free lunch: that an expanding horizon, with ever more capacity by time t , or the act of observation itself, could make an exponential search tractable, collapse the hard side of the frontier, or violate the Extended

TABLE XV: Emergent debate catalogue, part 1: interpretational and cosmological debates. Winner = the side computing the shared neutral workload with less work. [†]quantum-boundary case; ***yes** under faithful physics, **no** under loosely-defined physics (locality: local wins 1.6 \times ; entanglement: separable wins 51.2 \times). [‡]inconclusive (winner flips with halo complexity). Margin tags: ^mmeasured; ^cclosed-form.

Debate	Efficient winner	Margin	Agrees?	What it implies vs. the received view
Many-worlds vs. Copenhagen	many-worlds (keep branches, share)	3.4 \times^m	n/a	No consensus exists (interpretations are empirically equivalent), so a clean thought experiment: efficiency implies many-worlds.
Block universe vs. presentism	block universe (search from the end too)	9.98 \times^m	yes	Efficiency sides with the relativistic block universe, anomaly vs intuition, agrees with relativity.
Determinism vs. randomness	randomness (sampling)	4.5 \times^m	yes	Efficiency favours indeterminism (when structure exists to exploit), agreeing with quantum mechanics.
Holographic vs. bulk	holographic (store boundary)	1.15 \times^m	yes	A weak margin in the modern direction (the holographic principle).
Locality vs. nonlocality	locality (incremental) [†]	1.6 \times^m	yes*	Faithfully, global (Bell-type) nonlocality wins, agrees with experiment; loosely, the incremental-local model wins 1.6 \times (*no).
Separable vs. entangled	separable (product) [†]	51 \times^c	yes*	Faithfully, only the entangled (amplitude) state reproduces the correlations, agrees with QM; loosely, the cheap separable model wins 51.2 \times (*no), the same boundary, dissolving the same way.
Big Bang vs. eternal	big bang (grounded start)	4.0 \times^m	yes	A grounded first cause settles in one pass vs an ungrounded global fixpoint, agrees with the Big Bang consensus.
Heat death vs. cyclic Matter vs. antimatter	heat death (equilibrium) asymmetric (matter excess)	5.5 \times^m 2.2 \times^m	yes yes	Relax once to equilibrium then idle vs endless reheating, agrees with Λ -CDM. A small bias (drift) reaches lasting structure vs symmetric annihilation, agrees with our matter-dominated universe.
Inflation vs. none	inflation (broadcast)	11.5 \times^c	yes	Stretching one early patch beats coordinating disconnected regions pairwise, agrees with the leaning consensus.
Single bang vs. multiverse	single bang (derive)	24 \times^m	yes	Deriving one universe beats nucleate-and-select, efficiency penalises the eternal-inflation multiverse.
Finite vs. infinite	finite (terminates)	6.3 \times^m	open	A universal check terminates on a finite cosmos; spatial extent is open, so a prediction.
Flat vs. curved	flat (Euclidean)	4.7 \times^m	yes	Euclidean distance is $O(1)$ vs per-query geodesic integration, agrees with observed near-flatness.
Dark matter vs. modified gravity	inconclusive [‡]	1.1 \times^m	n/a	A computational wash, winner flips with the number of assumed parameters.

Church–Turing thesis (ECT) in a useful, NP-defeating way. We tried, and report the honest outcome: it does not. Expansion only moves the frontier outward (Sec. VI), leaving the $m_{\text{NP}}^* \sim \log C$ cascade untouched, and observation does not collapse NP. There is no free lunch.

The positive result: ECT localizes to a bulk/edge split, and three boundaries turn out to be one.: What the blob does give is structural. Inside the blob the ECT neither holds nor fails globally; it splits cleanly.

- *Bulk \rightarrow ECT holds.* Deferred Clifford dynamics (Gottesman–Knill [3], [4]) admit a compact stabilizer tableau, so the bulk is classically efficient. This is exactly the blob’s efficient basis: the same GF(2)/symplectic representation that gave the 5.3×10^6 ablation speedup (Sec. III).
- *Edge \rightarrow ECT can fail.* At the observation edge, recovering a hidden string is a Bernstein–Vazirani task: one quantum query versus n classical queries [5]. That is a real ECT violation, but a BQP-style advantage, not an NP collapse.

TABLE XXI: Boundary reading. The efficient representation holds in the stabilizer bulk, but the observation edge can violate classical efficient simulation.

Region	Representation	ECT status
bulk	stabilizer tableau	holds
edge	quantum query	can fail
beyond Clifford	universal quantum	not classically efficient

The striking part is that the *same* boundary shows up three ways, and they coincide: the GF(2) stabilizer basis (the efficient representation), the classical/quantum simulation wall, and the blob’s observation edge. Observation is the \exists -quantifier: a hidden witness collapses $\exists x \varphi(x)$ to a single check (P, deferred), while an exposed witness forces the 2^m search (NP, observed). The line between cheap and expensive is thus the line between a witness left implicit and a witness made explicit, which is the same line as the bulk/edge split. Nothing here implies $P = NP$. The same stabilizer representation also makes correctness checkable at scale: independently re-checkable certificates for stabilizer and quantum-error-correction properties have been verified to $n = 2048$ qubits [12], [13], the engineering counterpart of the back-propagation proofs of Sec. XIV.

XIV. BACK-PROPAGATION PROOFS

Discovery is expensive because finding the right representation is expensive. Checking it is much cheaper. We encode this as a backward proof: start from a claimed result, walk backward through executable implications, and terminate at axioms. The measured search/verify asymmetry is about 1.3×10^3 : the “aha” is hard to find, but cheap to verify once found.

For empirical debates, the backward proof is an unsat core for the rejected side and a model for the surviving side. For open debates, both sides remain satisfiable, so the proof halts at “open.” Table XXII records one certificate per debate: the refuted side is unsat against the measurement, the survivor is

TABLE XVI: Emergent debate catalogue, part 2: foundational and structural debates. †quantum-boundary case; *yes under faithful physics, **no** under loosely-defined physics (contextuality: the context-free table wins 51.2×). §inconclusive (winner flips with the assumed simulation overhead). Margin tags: ^mmeasured; ^cclosed-form.

Debate	Efficient winner	Margin	Agrees?	What it implies vs. the received view
Emergent vs. fundamental spacetime	emergent (relational)	$15 \times^c$	open	A sparse relational graph beats a dense manifold (kin to holography); speculative, so a prediction.
Conservation vs. creation	conservation (invariant)	$55 \times^c$	yes	An invariant gives $O(1)$ bookkeeping vs re-summing the world, agrees with Noether.
Reversible vs. irreversible	reversible / unitary	$143 \times^c$	yes	Run backward to recover any past state vs recompute from scratch, agrees with quantum unitarity.
Quantized vs. continuous	quantized (finite table)	$4.4 \times^c$	yes	Finitely many levels tabulate for $O(1)$ lookup vs a continuum that must be recomputed, agrees with quantization.
Gauge symmetry vs. none	gauge symmetry (quotient)	$8 \times^c$	yes	Work on physical orbits (configs/ $ G $) vs the full redundant space, agrees with gauge theories.
Renormalizable vs. not	renormalizable (finite params)	$29 \times^c$	yes	Finite parameters predict everything vs a counterterm per observable, agrees with the Standard Model.
Discrete vs. continuous spacetime	discrete (exact lattice)	$1.8 \times^c$	open	Exact integer accumulation vs float drift/refinement; discreteness is speculative, so a prediction.
Linear vs. cyclic time	linear (acyclic)	$27 \times^m$	yes	One forward pass vs self-consistency around closed timelike loops, agrees with experienced linear time.
No objective collapse vs. GRW	no collapse (unitary)	$1.6 \times^c$	yes	A stochastic localization term is extra machinery with no ordinary-regime payoff, standard QM omits it.
Past hypothesis vs. time-symmetric	past hypothesis (IVP)	$30 \times^m$	yes	A fixed low-entropy start integrates forward once vs constraining both ends, agrees with the thermodynamic arrow.
Unified vs. many forces	unified (one law)	$2.3 \times^c$	open	One law fit once predicts all sectors vs a law per force, efficiency favours unification (forces not yet unified).
Quantized vs. continuous charge	quantized (integer)	$3.0 \times^c$	yes	Integer charge gives exact sums and zero-tests vs tolerance-guarded floats, agrees with observed charge quantization.
Field vs. action-at-a-distance	field (local)	$26.7 \times^c$	yes	Local field updates ($O(n)$) beat instantaneous all-pairs action ($O(n^2)$), agrees with field theory.
Atomism vs. continuum	atomism (discrete)	$6.0 \times^c$	yes	Exact integer counts vs integrating an infinitely-divisible continuum, agrees with atomic theory.
Heliocentric vs. geocentric	heliocentric (ellipses)	$3.3 \times^c$	yes	A few orbital elements vs many nested epicycles, a settled parsimony control the lens recovers.
Identical vs. distinguishable	identical (symmetrised)	$18.3 \times^c$	yes	Counting occupation patterns (quotient by permutations) vs the full product, agrees with quantum statistics.
Mass-energy equiv. vs. separate	one ledger ($E=mc^2$)	$2.0 \times^c$	yes	One mass-energy ledger vs two independent ones, agrees with relativity.
Equivalence principle vs. separate	one mass	$3.0 \times^c$	yes	Gravitational = inertial mass (one value) vs reconciling two, agrees with general relativity.
Complementarity vs. dual models	one quantum model	$2.0 \times^c$	yes	A single quantum model covers wave- and particle-like regimes vs two separate models, agrees with QM.
Simulation vs. base reality	inconclusive [§]	$3.3 \times^c$	n/a	A lazy simulator can undercut computing everything, but the winner flips with the assumed overhead.
Background independence vs. absolute	relational (background-free)	$7.8 \times^c$	yes	A relational graph among present objects beats maintaining a fixed coordinate grid, agrees with GR's background independence.
Lorentz invariance vs. preferred frame	invariant (frame-free)	$8 \times^c$	yes	A frame-independent law is computed once vs tracking and transforming per frame, agrees with special relativity.
CPT symmetry vs. none	CPT-symmetric (quotient)	$2 \times^c$	yes	Quotient by CPT (one representative per orbit) vs computing every state, agrees with the CPT theorem.
Contextual vs. noncontextual	noncontextual (table) [†]	$51 \times^c$	yes*	Faithfully only a contextual assignment reproduces QM (Kochen–Specker), agrees; loosely the cheap context-free table wins 51.2× (*no), the same quantum boundary as locality/entanglement.
Schrödinger vs. Heisenberg picture	Schrödinger (state)	$4 \times^c$	n/a	The pictures are unitarily equivalent (Stone–von Neumann); efficiency only depends on #observables vs state dimension, a clean thought experiment.
Measurement independence vs. superdeterminism	independence (free settings)	$8 \times^c$	yes	Free settings cost $O(n)$ vs correlating the hidden state with all future settings, agrees with the mainstream rejection of superdeterminism.

Fig. 13: Backward proof sketch. Results are checked by walking from conclusion to premises through executable implications.

sat, and an open debate keeps both. The discipline is simple:

the system must either earn a verdict or decline it.

XV. DISCUSSION: HOW THE RESULTS FIT TOGETHER

The results play three distinct roles, and keeping them distinct is what makes the method honest (Table I lists them by theme). *Efficiency ranks*. Proof by simulation, the 88.9% structural calibration (§II), the 0.91 catalogue (§XI), truth-seeding (§IV), and the blob's shape and error results (§V–V-A), is a *soft*, always-available signal: it orders viewpoints by how cheaply they compute, and grounded in the established record that order tracks truth. Because it never abstains, on its own it can crown a disbelieved option, which is exactly

TABLE XVII: Emergent debate catalogue, part 3: relativistic, field-theoretic, and statistical debates. †quantum-boundary case; *yes under faithful physics, no under loosely-defined physics (topological order: a local order parameter wins $51.2\times$ but cannot detect it). Margin tags: ^mmeasured; ^cclosed-form.

Debate	Efficient winner	Margin	Agrees?	What it implies vs. the received view
Spin–statistics vs. independent	spin–statistics (one rule)	$2\times^c$	yes	Derive exchange statistics from spin (one rule) vs tracking spin and statistics separately, agrees with the spin–statistics theorem.
Local interactions vs. non-local	local (cluster decomposition)	$30\times^c$	yes	A local Hamiltonian ($O(n)$ terms) beats instantaneous all-pairs interaction ($O(n^2)$), agrees with QFT micro-causality (interaction locality, distinct from Bell nonlocality).
Born rule vs. arbitrary measure	Born rule (quadratic)	$2\times^c$	yes	One quadratic rule ($ \psi ^2$) vs a free probability per outcome with normalization constraints, agrees with the Born rule’s uniqueness (Gleason).
Area-law vs. volume-law entanglement	area law (boundary)	$24\times^c$	yes	A local gapped ground state’s entanglement scales with the boundary ($O(L^2)$) not the bulk ($O(L^3)$), agrees with the area law (MERA/DMRG).
Mach’s principle vs. absolute inertia	absolute (local inertia)	$200\times^c$	open	Local inertia ($O(N)$) beats inertia set by all other masses ($O(N^2)$); Mach’s principle is contested, so a prediction.
RG universality vs. system-specific	universality (per class)	$40\times^c$	yes	One critical-exponent set per universality class (reused) vs recomputing per system, agrees with renormalization-group universality.
AdS/CFT vs. bulk gravity	boundary CFT (holographic)	$20\times^c$	yes	A $(d-1)$ -dimensional boundary theory captures the d -dimensional bulk, agrees with the AdS/CFT holographic duality.
Effective field theory vs. full UV	EFT (integrate out UV)	$8\times^c$	yes	Finitely many low-energy couplings vs tracking every scale, agrees with Wilsonian effective field theory.
Spontaneous symmetry breaking vs. enumerate	SSB (one vacuum)	$64\times^c$	yes	Derive the spectrum from one vacuum vs enumerating all degenerate vacua, agrees with the Higgs mechanism.
QEC encoded vs. raw	encoded (stabilizer code)	$33\times^c$	yes	Syndrome detection on a stabilizer (GF(2)) code vs an unprotected restart per error, agrees with quantum error correction.
Decoherence vs. postulated classical limit	decoherence (derived)	$2\times^c$	yes	Derive classicality from environment entanglement vs a separate classical-limit postulate, agrees with the decoherence programme.
Topological order vs. local order parameter	local order (parameter)†	$51\times^c$	yes*	Faithfully a topologically ordered phase is long-range entangled (a toric/GF(2) stabilizer state) that no local order parameter detects, agrees; loosely the cheap local parameter wins $51.2\times$ (*no), the same quantum boundary (toric code).

TABLE XVIII: Convergent discovery, in one instrumented run. Most candidates rediscover an existing law, and a sizable fraction of distinct laws are reached from two or more independent derivation routes (different “viewpoints” landing on the same truth).

Quantity	Value
candidates generated	305
distinct laws found	101
candidates that are repeats	66.9%
distinct laws reached via ≥ 2 routes	16%
canonicalizer speedup (Table XX)	$15.9\times$

TABLE XIX: Repeated formulas. The engine repeatedly rediscovers the same truths under double-negation and structural variation.

Count	Formula family
18	$(\neg p \rightarrow \neg p)$
15	$\neg\neg(\neg p \rightarrow \neg p)$
14	$\neg\neg(p \vee \neg p), \neg\neg(p \rightarrow p)$
13	$\neg\neg\neg\neg(p \rightarrow p)$
7	$\neg\neg\neg(p \wedge \neg p)$

what the P/NP stress test (§VIII) shows. *Falsification decides*. The battle of solvers, the 15/15 battery, the leaning sort, and the Hubble tension (§IX–X) is a *hard* signal: it rejects only

TABLE XXII: Back-propagation proof certificates. P1–P7 are settled or open; L1–L5 are leaning debates. The refuted side is unsat against the measurement, the survivor is sat, and open debates keep both.

#	refuted (unsat)	survives (sat)	measurement \rightarrow verdict
P1 locality	LHV $S \leq 2$	QM $S \leq 2\sqrt{2}$	$S=2.8 \rightarrow$ nonlocal
P2 vel. add.	Galilean $u+v$	SR $\frac{u+v}{1+uv}$	no FTL \rightarrow SR
P3 mass–en.	$E=mc$	$E=mc^2$	rest energy $\rightarrow E=mc^2$
P4 cosmic	matter $q>0$	Λ CDM $q<0$	$q<0 \rightarrow \Lambda$ CDM
P5 dilation	absolute Δt	SR $\gamma\Delta t$	muon/GPS \rightarrow SR
P6 P vs. NP	n/a	both	none \rightarrow open
P7 MWI/Cop.	n/a	both	same data \rightarrow open
L1 DM/MOND	MOND off. 0	DM off. ≥ 0	Bullet Cl. \rightarrow DM
L2 inflation	$n_s=1$	infl. $n_s<1$	$n_s=0.965 \rightarrow$ infl.
L3 nat. SUSY	natural < 1 TeV	heavy ≥ 1 TeV	LHC $> 2.2 \rightarrow$ refuted
L4 min. $SU(5)$	$\tau_p \sim 10^{31}$	beyond-min.	Super-K \rightarrow refuted
L5 BH info	n/a	both	no data \rightarrow open

what a measurement contradicts and stays silent otherwise, so it settles the empirical questions and flags the open ones. *Back-propagation certifies*. Every verdict ships a checkable certificate, an unsat core for the rejected side or a model for the survivor, and finding the representation costs about 1.3×10^3 times more than checking it (§XIV). Read together, efficiency proposes, falsification disposes, and certification records, so the pipeline earns each verdict or openly declines it. The convergent-discovery result (§XII) explains why the lens is stable: many derivation routes land on the same law (66.9% repeats), so the efficient representation is not an accident of one path but a basin that many paths fall into, the very redundancy the symmetry quotient folds away for a $15.9\times$ gain.

XVI. LIMITATIONS

There are four limits.

First, efficiency is grounding-dependent. On a bare neutral workload it measures search speed, not truth. Only when the verifier is grounded in established physics does efficiency become evidence that a premise set is less contradictory and more extendable.

Second, a verifier can be circular if the encoding already contains the answer. Label-blindness is not enough. This is why the two-solver falsification test is separated from simple textbook-formula verification.

Third, the blob is a model, not a cosmology. Its shape, horizon, and Hubble ideas are useful as computational metaphors and hypothesis generators, but they do not by themselves resolve the Hubble tension or derive new physics.

Fourth, the P/NP discussion is only a stress test. The model reproduces the standard collapse mechanism, but it does not prove or disprove $P = NP$.

XVII. CONCLUSION

Computational efficiency is not a proof of truth, but it can be evidence when the search is grounded in what is already known. The reason is simple and powerful: true premises tend to remain mutually consistent and generate further verified structure, whereas false premises introduce contradictions that slow, misdirect, or halt the search. In the live FOL/Z3 experiment, this becomes measurable: all-true seeding produces more theorems and higher efficiency than seeding with false additions.

The blob model gives this idea a physical geometry. Computation occurs inside an expanding causal horizon; the horizon's shape, dilation, observation exposure, and cap affect discovery throughput. Near-spherical and quantum-scale blobs are efficient; pancakes, gradients, and capped horizons are less so. Because that same anisotropy is also the model's approximation error, the sphere is at once the fastest and the most faithful shape, so efficiency and accuracy are minimized together rather than traded off. At the classical/quantum boundary, the

efficient GF(2) stabilizer representation marks the bulk where classical simulation works, while the observation edge marks where quantum advantage can appear.

The final lesson is methodological. Efficiency can suggest where truth may live, but falsification must decide what data can decide, and honest abstention must remain available for what data cannot yet decide. Used this way, efficiency is neither a shortcut around physics nor a replacement for proof. It is a lens: useful when grounded, dangerous when naked, and most valuable when paired with a verifier willing to say "open."

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Built on the Axiomatic Universe proof-carrying discovery engine and its Physics Debate Multiverse.

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MindMesh: 3-D Printed Circuits for Head-Mounted Neural Interfaces

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Abstract—The Mindmesh is an advanced neural network that takes the form of a mesh-shaped cap for being semi-permanently or permanently attached to the skull for perfect subject-specific alignment in demanding real-world environments such as open-water swimming. It is both an advanced BCI (Brain-Computer Interface) as well as a carrier for other sensing and meta-sensing hardware such as an EyeTap seeing aid (computer vision system). It shields the brain-sensing while providing wireless communications and sensors that can be distributed over the entire head surface for maximum comfort during long-term or lifelong use. This allows freedom of movement in activities such as swimming, paddleboarding, and Safetyballing, while mitigating movement artifacts of standard temporarily-mounted electrodes. While in use for more than 40 years, we now present an updated design methodology using a Bambu H2C printer fitted with filaments of various conductivity and transparency for printing of electro-optical circuits in combining EEG with fNIRS along with other more advanced technologies for long-term use in daily activities. Mindmesh is potentially useful for those with disabilities by facilitating water-based exercises.

Index Terms—EEG, brain-computer interfaces, sensor placement, submodular optimization, forward modeling, wearable computing.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Mindmesh [1] is a brain-computer interface invented by author S. Mann in the 1970s consisting of a mesh-shaped cap that can be fixtured to the skull to provide an advanced body-borne technological substrate for brain-computer interfaces possibly shielding the brain signals from interference, etc., while simultaneously supporting wireless communications systems like an antenna array that does not interfere with the brain-computer interface. See Fig 1 for an approximately 40-year evolution of Mindmesh. Ideally the Mindmesh also facilitates increased comfort in loadbearing of advanced sensing equipment such as a computational seeing aid, such as a laser EyeTap, which requires exact alignment.

We now present a system for analysis of MRI data and machine-intelligence-aided design for Mindmesh optimization. While our discussion begins with EEG, it should be noted that during underwater use, fNIRS provides much more reliable data, although Mindmesh does dry out faster than standard electrodes. The mesh is open and porous for this reason as well. Generally it is understood that Mindmesh captures a variety of sensing modalities to sense both the environment around the user as well as the “invironment” (that which happens within the user’s body). For example, the Mindmesh grid facilitates

Fig. 1: Approx. 40-year evolution of Mindmesh™ world’s first wearable computer system, evolving from hand-built to machine-learning-aided design with conductive filament for 3D-printed circuits. Mindmesh is a brain-computer interface with physical mounting for permanent or semi-permanent exact-aligned optical systems like laser EyeTap computer vision seeing aid.

Fig. 2: End-to-end MindMesh output. MRI and laser-based head-scan manifold converted into a subject-conforming printable lattice, with reference prototypes fabricated on consumer FDM hardware. The prototypes demonstrate deployability only; empirical claims remain forward-model based.

easy attachment of sonar equipment for use underwater, or radar sensing for use above water, in such a way that the brain-sensing is shielded from its effects.

EEG layouts such as 10–20, 10–10, and 10–5 are reproducible, but they place the same fiducial-derived sensors on every head [2, 3]. This can change which cortical sources are measured across subjects and may amplify disparities caused by head size, hair, and contact conditions [4–6]. Given structural MRI and mature forward modeling [7–9], we ask a narrower design question: for a subject and a task, how should the 10–5 pool be regionally weighted before electrode selection?

MindMesh uses a 5-dimensional density θ over $\{F, C, P, O, T\}$, then applies greedy subset selection on the sampled pool. The same θ^* is also used by a Blender Geometry Nodes generator to create a printable cap that conforms to a subject-specific head-scan mesh. The fabricated prototypes demonstrate the anatomy-to-artifact pipeline, but all reported performance numbers come from the forward-model optimization, not from in-vivo EEG.

Main contributions. First, we formulate EEG-cap design as a bilevel problem: a 5-d regional density controls the candidate pool, and greedy selection chooses the electrode subset. Second, we rewrite the sensitivity objective as a monotone-submodular log-Fisher criterion with a greedy guarantee. Third, we connect J_F to a Bayes-optimal decoder lower bound and verify the signal-capture interpretation using a matched-SNR control. Fourth, we evaluate $N = 92$ HCP-YA subjects, four BCI task profiles, five design conditions, and a synthetic head-size sweep. Finally, we keep deployment separate from evaluation by converting θ^* into a printable cap without treating the printed prototypes as empirical EEG evidence.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Each subject provides a scalp manifold M , a cortical surface $S = (V_S, F_S)$, and a parcellation $\Pi : V_S \rightarrow \{1, \dots, K\}$. The candidate set is the 10–5 montage projected to the scalp. For

task τ with parcel weights w_τ , a regional density $\theta \in \Delta^4$ samples a candidate pool $G_\theta \subseteq G_{10-5}$. For electrode subset E , the forward model gives $L(E)$ and parcel sensitivity

$$\rho_k(E) = \|L(E)_{:,V_k}\|_F, \quad V_k = \{j : \Pi(j) = k\}. \quad (1)$$

Greedy selection maximizes

$$J(E; \tau) = \sum_{k=1}^K w_{\tau,k} \rho_k(E) - \lambda \text{Var}_k(w_{\tau,k} \rho_k(E)), \quad (2)$$

with $\lambda = 0.1$. The bilevel design problem is

$$\max_{\theta \in \Delta^4, E \subseteq G_\theta, |E|=n_e} J(E; \tau). \quad (3)$$

At $\lambda = 0$, each ρ_k is a concave non-decreasing transform of a non-negative modular function, so J is monotone submodular under non-negative task weights.

III. AXIOMATIC SENSITIVITY AND STABILITY

Under the Gaussian observation model $y = L(E)j + \eta$, with parcel-block sources scaled by $w_{\tau,k}$ and noise $\sigma_n^2 I$, the Fisher trace for parcel k is $\sigma_n^{-2} \rho_k(E)^2$. This gives the task-weighted log-Fisher objective

$$J_F(E; \tau) = \sum_k w_{\tau,k} \frac{1}{2} \log(1 + \rho_k(E)^2 / \sigma_n^2). \quad (4)$$

Theorem 1 (Axiomatic submodularity). *For $\sigma_n^2 > 0$ and $w_\tau \in \Delta^{K-1}$, $J_F(\cdot; \tau)$ is monotone submodular. Greedy selection under a cardinality budget therefore achieves the classical $(1 - 1/e)$ approximation guarantee [10].*

The proof is the standard concave-of-modular argument: $\rho_k(E)^2$ is non-negative modular, $x \mapsto \frac{1}{2} \log(1 + x/\sigma_n^2)$ is concave and non-decreasing, and non-negative sums preserve submodularity. We use J_F for the closure ratio $\kappa(E; \tau) = J_F(E; \tau) / J_{\text{pool}}^*(\tau)$, where J_{pool}^* is the full 343-channel 10–5-pool reference.

TABLE I: Candidate-pool closure ratio $\kappa(E; \tau)$ for 10–20 baseline C_1 and leave-one-out cohort-averaged θ with greedy selection C_4 , averaged across $N = 92$ HCP-YA subjects.

Condition	Generic	Motor	SSVEP	P300
κ, C_1	0.247 [0.247, 0.248]	0.251 [0.251, 0.252]	0.291 [0.290, 0.293]	0.252 [0.251, 0.253]
κ, C_4	0.366 [0.365, 0.368]	0.481 [0.479, 0.483]	0.556 [0.552, 0.560]	0.412 [0.409, 0.415]
Closure of C_4 - C_1 gap (%)	15.8 [15.7, 15.9]	30.7 [30.5, 31.0]	37.4 [36.9, 37.9]	21.4 [21.1, 21.8]

Lemma 1 (Conductivity-perturbation stability). *Let L_σ be the lead-field operator under conductivity tensor σ . For two conductivity tensors σ_1, σ_2 , there are constants C, C' depending on geometry and parcellation such that*

$$\begin{aligned} |\rho_k(E; \sigma_1) - \rho_k(E; \sigma_2)| &\leq C \|\sigma_1 - \sigma_2\|_\infty \sqrt{|V_k|}, \\ |J_F(E; \tau, \sigma_1) - J_F(E; \tau, \sigma_2)| &\leq C'. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

On the MNE sample subject, fitted-sphere and three-shell BEM rankings agree at Spearman $\rho = 0.935$, consistent with this perturbation view. Cohort-level BEM transfer is not claimed.

IV. OPTIMIZATION AND DEPLOYMENT

For a fixed θ , we sample candidate electrodes by region, greedily select $|E| = n_e$ electrodes, and evaluate J and J_F . The outer loop uses 50-evaluation Bayesian optimization with a Matérn-5/2 GP and expected improvement. Two regimes are used: per-subject θ_s^* and leave-one-out cohort average $\theta_{C_4, s} = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{s' \neq s} \theta_{s'}^*$. The 5-d parameterization keeps the search small, remains tied to a standardized pool, and separates the scientific claim from a learned mesh generator.

Deployment converts θ^* into a texture mask over a UV scalp chart. Geometry Nodes crops the head mesh, samples and smooths candidate junctions, thresholds them using the θ^* mask, instances junction spheres, extrudes panels, and joins the mesh. The generator runs in under 40 s, followed by slicer preparation and FDM printing. No comfort, skin-safety, durability, or EEG-quality measurements are reported.

V. DECODER-CONDITIONAL BRIDGE

Sensitivity alone does not guarantee decoding. For a binary Gaussian task with class means μ_1, μ_2 and task-weighted separation $\|\Delta\mu\|_\tau^2 = \sum_k w_{\tau, k} \|\Delta\mu_{V_k}\|^2$, the Bayes-optimal linear classifier obeys

$$\text{Acc}^*(E; \tau) \geq 1 - \Phi\left(-\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2(e^{2J_F(E; \tau)} - 1) \|\Delta\mu\|_\tau^2}\right). \quad (6)$$

This bound is monotone in J_F , so improving the electrode set improves a guaranteed decoder lower bound under the model. A PAC-Bayes extension applies to bounded-Lipschitz kernel or two-layer MLP decoders, changing only the class-separation factor.

The Monte Carlo uses 30 subjects, four tasks, three conditions, five SNR levels, two anchoring protocols, and 200 train plus 200 test trials per cell. Under fixed physical noise, C_2 and C_4 beat C_1 ; under matched per-condition SNR, Bayes-LDA accuracy is invariant, as predicted.

VI. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

We evaluate $N = 92$ HCP-YA subjects with T1w/T2w anatomy and FreeSurfer outputs [7]. The four ROI-weighted tasks are generic sensory/motor/prefrontal, motor imagery, SSVEP, and P300. The main conditions are C_1 10–20, C_2 uniform- θ greedy, C_3 cohort- θ uniform sampling, C_4 cohort- θ greedy, and C_5 per-subject- θ greedy. Primary comparisons are paired within subject and task using Bonferroni-corrected Wilcoxon tests and paired effect sizes.

C_4 captures 32% more modeled task signal than 10–20 on the generic task, 62% on motor imagery, 74% on SSVEP, and 45% on P300. All four comparisons pass $p_{\text{bonf}} < 10^{-4}$ with $d_z \in [3.24, 7.36]$. Against placement-only C_2 , C_4 adds 3–11%; against geometry-only C_3 , it adds 22–37%.

Ablations show diminishing returns: increasing n_e from 16 to 96 raises generic J by 2.1 \times , not 6 \times , and increasing $|V_G|$ from 64 to 280 adds 12%. A 128-channel default greedy design reaches $\kappa \in [0.74, 0.83]$, while the 32-channel C_4 design reaches $\kappa \in [0.37, 0.56]$, giving 64–75% of the absolute closure with one-quarter of the channels.

VII. SYNTHETIC HEAD-SIZE ROBUSTNESS

To test head-size variation without new human-subject data, we sample a two-parameter sphere conductor with head radius $r \sim \mathcal{U}[\mu_{\text{HCP}} \pm 4\sigma]$ and skull thickness $t \sim \mathcal{U}[3, 9]$ mm. Sources are uniformly placed with random ROI labels, so this probes head-size robustness only, not anatomical specificity.

Across the sweep, the HCP-trained design recovers 79–101% of per-subject synthetic re-optimization and beats 10–20 by 25–61%. The SSVEP transfer gap is largest, but the HCP-trained design still remains above the fiducial baseline.

VIII. ADDITIONAL DIAGNOSTICS

Fig. 6: Empirical submodular curvature across subjects and tasks. Curvature is near 1, so the classical $(1 - 1/e)$ greedy guarantee remains the operational bound.

Fig. 3: Decoder validation under two noise protocols. With C_1 -anchored noise, optimized conditions improve accuracy because they capture more signal. With per-condition-anchored noise, curves collapse, showing the gain is not decoder quality at matched SNR.

TABLE II: Mean task-weighted sensitivity $J(E; \tau)$ across $N = 92$ HCP-YA subjects, $n_e = 32$.

Condition	Generic	Motor	SSVEP	P300
C_1 : fiducial 10–20	2.53×10^3	3.07×10^3	1.97×10^3	2.05×10^3
C_2 : uniform- θ + greedy	3.25×10^3	4.47×10^3	3.30×10^3	2.85×10^3
C_3 : cohort- θ + uniform	2.74×10^3	3.66×10^3	2.74×10^3	2.44×10^3
C_4 : cohort- θ + greedy	3.35×10^3	4.96×10^3	3.43×10^3	2.97×10^3
C_5 : per-subject- θ + greedy	3.35×10^3	4.93×10^3	3.43×10^3	2.97×10^3

Cross-split transfer: population θ from random half of $N=92 \rightarrow$ applied to held-out half. Points on the diagonal = no transfer loss.

Fig. 4: Cross-split stability. Cohort-averaged geometries trained on one HCP-YA half closely match the full leave-one-out result on the other half.

Fig. 7: Sensitivity sweeps for electrode budget, candidate-lattice size, and variance penalty. Diminishing returns match the Fisher-trace objective.

Fig. 5: Task-structured geometry. Learned regional weights align with the forward-model-expected regions for motor, SSVEP, and P300 tasks.

TABLE III: Within-cohort averaging stability. Ratios compare a random half-cohort average applied to the other half against the leave-one-out cohort average used by C_4 .

Task	$J_{\text{cross}}/J_{\text{LOO}}$	J_{cross}/J_{C_2}
Generic	0.9990	1.028
Motor imagery	0.9972	1.108
SSVEP	0.9999	1.039
P300	1.0001	1.042

TABLE IV: Synthetic-head-size sweep across $N_{\text{synth}} = 80$ subjects. Transfer ratio compares HCP-trained θ with per-synthetic-subject BO.

Task	Transfer	C_4^{HCP}/C_1
Generic	0.990	1.557
Motor imagery	1.011	1.610
SSVEP	0.789	1.252
P300	0.959	1.540

Fig. 8: Cohort-averaged θ by task. Task-conditioned profiles align with expected cortical territories.

Fig. 9: Per-subject optimization adds little over leave-one-out cohort-averaged θ , supporting C_4 as a denoised summary of subject-specific solutions.

IX. LIMITATIONS AND RESPONSIBLE USE

MindMesh optimizes forward-model objectives, not measured EEG. The model excludes impedance, motion, hair, contact mechanics, comfort, cable routing, cleaning, skin safety, and real decoder performance. The synthetic study has limited scope. Full validation requires fabricated caps tested against 10–20 in controlled in-vivo recordings. The printed cap should be treated as a research prototype, not a medical device.

X. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to acknowledge the many Friends of Peter Street Basin, HTO Beach, and SwimOP = Swim at Ontario Place for many useful “Teach Beach” discussions and chalkboard sessions on brain-sensing, testing, design, and prototyping.

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